

INFINITE

BUILDINGRENOVATION

Industrialised envelope solutions

D4.8

Guidelines on LCA-LCC and design for assembling/ disassembling

Final deliverable - Public Report

Date - 29/02/2024

INFINITE/Industrialised durable building envelope retrofitting by all-in-one interconnected technology solutions project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No **958397**

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Acknowledgements

Document details

Deliverable No: D4.8

Dissemination level: Public

Work Package: WP4

Lead beneficiary: GreenDelta

Date of publication: 29/02/2024

Version: 3.0

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Project information

Title: Industrialised durable building envelope retrofitting by all-in-one interconnected technology solutions (INFINITE)

EC Grant Agreement Number: No 958397

Duration: November 2020 until May 2025 (54 months)

Coordinator

eurac
research

Project Partners

GreenDelta

RUBNER

About the project

Off-site prefabrication of multifunctional envelopes has been shown to be a technically viable approach to increase rate and quality of deep renovation of residential buildings. However, several barriers are still preventing a massive adoption of prefabricated solutions.

INFINITE aims at boosting the building renovation sector through the so-called "**Renovation4.0**" approach, which leverages on both digitalisation and industrialisation to offer **tailor-made solutions** with a high level of **design freedom, decrease retrofit costs and time** thanks to the optimisation of the value-chain and **foster the adoption of eco-compatible long-lasting products** and systems.

To do so, the INFINITE Project relies on three main pillars:

1. cross-fertilisation from digitalisation trends in other markets (i.e. Industry4.0),
2. exploitation of industrial capabilities and coupling with LC-thinking approach
3. experience gained from the 1st generation of multifunctional prefabricated envelopes

INFINITE promotes a life cycle approach that allows for comprehensive design, optimisation of the O&M and depletion of end-of-life residual value.

INFINITE partners cover the whole renovation value-chain. Together, they will develop a new generation of residential building renovation products and actions centred on the all-in-one industrialised Life-Cycle-based approach. Expected outputs include:

- a set of multi-user and **multidisciplinary design tools**,
- **process-optimised all-in-one industrialised eco envelope kits**,
- **adaptive control systems**,
- set of **demand- and industry-side matched business models** to show the Renovation4.0 market potential,
- a **structured framework of entities and knowledge** able to clearly and widely demonstrate the Renovation4.0 benefits.

INFINITE will unleash the potential of the renovation industry by increasing the market penetration of sustainable, high-quality and long-lasting building retrofitting products and methods. This will ultimately contribute to the decarbonisation of the European building stock.

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Abbreviations

BIPV: Building Integrated Photovoltaic
BIST: Building Integrated Solar Thermal
DfD/A: Design for Assembling/Disassembling
EF method: Environmental Footprint Impact Assessment method
EPD: Environmental Product Declaration
EPP: Expanded PolyPropylene
EPS: Expanded Polystyrene
EoL: End of Life
ETICS: External Thermal Insulating Composite Systems
FAETP: Freshwater Aquatic Ecotoxicity Potential
FU: Functional Unit
GHG: Green House Gas
GLW: Green Living Wall
GWP: global warming potential
HPL: High Pressure Laminate
HTP: Human Toxicity Potential
IGU: Insulated Glazing Unit
ITO glass: Indium Titanium Oxide glass
kWp: kilowatt-peak
LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
LCC: Life Cycle Costing
LGW: Living Green Wall
MVU: Mechanical Ventilation Unit
PCB: Printed Circuit Board
PLSMC: Plasmochromic
PVCC: photovoltachromic
RHB: Rubner Holzbau
SCC: Societal Cost of Carbon
Tbd: to be defined
XPS: Extruded Polystyrene

Executive Summary

This deliverable is written as part of the INFINITE project Task 4.8 *LCC-LCA and Assembling-Disassembling support for the technological development*, and focuses specifically on LCA, LCC as well as the support works on design for disassembly and assembly (DfD/A) for the INFINITE kits.

The LCA/LCC study arises in the context of the validation of the sustainability of the INFINITE all-in-one envelope kits technologies developed within the project. The main goal is to support the developers of the different components and kits in the technological design of the products, taking into account the sustainability performance in parallel to the technical one. Therefore, the aim is to provide the technical partners with sustainability information regarding the kits and their potential benefits and drawbacks for the environmental and economic dimensions. Furthermore, sustainability information can be useful for product commercialisation and communication to customers and other stakeholders involved in the renovation process.

The goal and scope of the LCA and LCC study of the INFINITE kits has been drafted following the ISO standards 14040 and 14044. A literature review has been performed to identify hotspots and recurring environmental and economic issues or potentials associated with the technologies tackled by INFINITE. Finally, LCA and LCC results are presented for the different components developed by the technology providers. Such components are combined to deliver the INFINITE kits. Therefore, the sustainability assessment of the kits builds on the current LCA and LCC data and models for the components. Depending on the component maturity level and the availability of data from suppliers, the LCA and LCC results are based on primary data or secondary generic information and literature or a combination of both. The following conclusions could be drawn from the assessments:

- Kit 0, RHB façade: insulation, cladding, and outer planking are the main environmental hotspots of a standard Rubner façade.
- Kit 1, green envelope: metal profiles and maintenance needs have the most environmental impacts for greening systems.
- Kit 2, energy and fresh air distribution: centralized systems and polyethylene pipes are more eco-friendly than decentralized units and steel ducts.
- Kit 3, smart window: electricity for module manufacturing and transport of ITO glass and inks are the main environmental and economic hotspots; recycling and reuse of IGUs and power bars are key aspects for end of life.
- Kit 4, BIPV: photovoltaic cells and solar glass are the main environmental and economic hotspots; aluminium brackets and back rails also contribute to environmental impacts.
- Kit 5, BIST: manufacturing and installation of the panel are the most impactful life cycle stages, due to aluminium layers.

In addition, the objectives of this task are to analyse the kits in terms of DfD/A, challenge and support the kit developers, and improve their solutions on DfD/A aspects. Best DfD/A have many benefits, such as:

- Reducing Construction and Demolition (C&D) wastes and environmental impacts of the construction solutions,
- Increasing reusability and recyclability of the kit's components,
- Facilitating maintenance processes and improves durability,
- Reducing costs of implementation, maintenance, and end-of-life treatment.

The deliverable presents a synthetic review of the main DfD/A assessment methodologies applied in the INFINITE project.

First, a short literature review on two aspects is presented: existing DfD/A methods and reuse-recycling current practices on studied kit typologies. Second, a detailed overview of the methods and tools used and developed in this project is made. Then, the application of these methods and tools on the 5 INFINITE kits designs is carried out, using guidelines for a better implementation of DfD/A principles in the kits' design:

- Determination the high value elements, as it can give an economic purpose to the DfD/A approach, in addition to an environmental benefit to improve circular economy.
- Design with standardisation, as standard elements have benefits during maintenance operations (easily and locally replaceable), and at the end of life (standard elements will find a new use more easily due to their large-scale use and potential valorisation chains already in place).
- Design for best durability, as it allows to extend the lifespan of the kit as well as open end-of-life valorisation.
- Design of connections, which is the main part of DfD/A, by focusing on finding the best connections between elements and facilitating disassembly during both maintenance and end-of-life disassembling;
- Considering maintenance: dismantling should be minimised during maintenance operations. Visible and accessible systems are therefore recommended.
- Design of disassembly processes and tools, by preferring standard, and easy-to-use tools and by creating a clear dismantling procedure that allows to separate all elements without damage.
- Considering end-of-life valorisation, by preferring materials or components that are easiest to sort and already have operational reuse or recycling chains.

Finally, a final assessment is made on selected kits through a DfD/A assessment tool developed for the needs of the project, taking into account Disassembly for Maintenance, Reconditioning and Recycling.

1. Introduction

This report addresses Life Cycle Assessment/Life Cycle Costing (LCA/LCC) and Design for assembling/disassembling (DfA/D) of the INFINITE kits. These two main aspects are studied in parallel but keeping in mind that they are also connected. The aim is to support the technology providers in the development of the kits from a sustainability and DfA/D point of view.

A clarification of terms is provided below in order to understand the different scales and perimeters:

- **Component:** “an element manufactured as independent unit that can be joined with other elements”, such as a photovoltaic panel.
- **Kit:** a construction product placed on the market by a single manufacturer as a set of at least two separate components that need to be put together to be incorporated in the construction works (EU Regulation No 305/2011)
- **All-in-one envelope solution:** a combination of the different kits (façade and roof modules) that form the retrofit intervention of the building envelope.
- **Building:** the building level is not considered in the analyses described in this report.

2. LCA and LCC study

2.1 Goal and scope of the study

This document presents the goal and scope for the LCA and LCC performed in Task 4.8. The link with Task 6.4 is explained as well. Defining goal and scope is the first and one of the very key steps when performing life cycle assessments and similar analyses. The idea is to clearly specify “what the analysis and modeling will cover, for whom it is intended, and how it is planned to be used.” ISO 14040 lists the elements that are expected in a goal and scope specification of an LCA.

2.1.1 Goal of the LCA/LCC

2.1.1.1 Goal and intended application

This study arises in the context of the **validation of the sustainability of the INFINITE all-in-one envelope kits**, and of their technical design and evaluation performed by other tasks in WP4. The main goal is to support the developers of the different components and kits in the technological design of the products, taking into account the sustainability performance in parallel to the technical one. Therefore, the aim is to **provide the technical partners with sustainability information** regarding the kits, specifically concerning potential benefits and drawbacks as well as recommendations for improvement for the environmental and economic dimensions. This information relies on the results of the environmental Life Cycle Assessment and Life Cycle Costing and DfA/D studies. Social aspects are addressed in WP2.

Specifically, the study aims at answering the following questions:

- To which extent are the INFINITE solutions sustainable?
- How do the INFINITE solutions perform in comparison to a baseline scenario (if applicable)?
- How do the new INFINITE technologies perform over the entire life cycle?
- What are the key drivers for environmental and cost impacts of the solutions designed in the INFINITE project?
- How can the environmental and cost aspects be further improved?
- How can the results be communicated to different stakeholders in an effective way?

As a result of the study, guidelines will be delivered to the different WP4 partners (GSG, VORTICE, RHB, LEITAT, PHYSEE, SUNAGE, NBK, SERNEO) for an LCA and LCC driven design and optimization of the kits. These guidelines will also include Design for Disassembling and Construction-Demolition-Waste aspects investigated by NBK. A public version of these Guidelines is expected to provide more general recommendations for the design of industrialized technologies, beyond the specific kits developed in INFINITE.

Furthermore, results of the study are intended to be disclosed to the public in conferences and publications.

2.1.1.2 Reasons for carrying out the study

The main reason for conducting the study is to **investigate the technological solutions (kits) provided by INFINITE from a sustainability point of view, considering environmental and economic aspects,**

and in parallel to the design process. This would enable technological developers to apply sustainability performance as a development driver, for instance in the choice of materials. Thus, the results of the environmental LCA and LCC are planned to integrate the other technical outcomes and on-site testing, hence offering a comprehensive and meaningful description of the INFINITE kits and their advantages and disadvantages.

2.1.1.3 Intended audience

The intended audience is formed by INFINITE partners participating to the design and implementation of the INFINITE kits at first. Secondly, the results of the study are foreseen for a broader target audience, such as academia, industry and end-customers.

2.1.2 Scope of the LCA

2.1.2.1 Product systems and function of the product systems

Different product systems will be assessed in the study, following the **goal of supporting** 1) each partner in the development of the **single components and kits** and 2) Rubner Holzbau (RHB) in the **development of the all-in-one envelope solutions**, where the individually developed kits are combined.

Therefore, the product systems corresponding to the different kits to be assessed are summarized below (as results R2.X). For every kit, the different components are reported.

- R2.1 (developed in T4.1 by GSG, LEITAT, RHB, EURAC): eco-compatible green envelope kit (a Green Living Wall solution is considered in the assessment).

Table 1: Eco-compatible green envelope kit

Eco-compatible green envelope kit (façade)	
Component	Provider
1.Timber-based façade	RHB
2.Green system: Green Living Wall	GSG

- R2.2 (developed in T4.2 by VORTICE, RHB, EURAC): Energy and fresh air distribution envelope kit.

Table 2: Energy and fresh air distribution envelope kit

Energy and fresh air distribution envelope kit (façade)	
Component	Provider
1.Timber-based façade	RHB
2.Energy and fresh-air distribution module	VORTICE

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- R2.3 (developed in T4.3 by LEITAT, PHYSEE, RHB, EURAC): Integrated smart window kit, two options: R2.3.1 Plasmochromic Insulated Glazing Unit (IGU) and R2.3.2 Sensor and solar control technology integrated with integrated IGU blinds.

Table 3: Integrated smart window kit

Integrated smart window kit (façade)	
R.2.3.1	
Component	Provider
Plasmochromic IGU	LEITAT
R.2.3.2	
1. Sensor and solar technology (including control functionalities)	PHYSEE
2. Integrated IGU blinds	Pellini

- R2.4 (developed in T4.4 by SUNAGE, RHB, EURAC): Energy generation BIPV (Building Integrated Photovoltaic) kit.

Table 4: BIPV kit

Energy generation BIPV kit (roof and façade)	
Component	Provider
1. Timber-based façade	RHB
2. PV module	SUNAGE

- R2.5 (developed in T4.5 by SERNEO, NBK, RHB): Energy generation BIST (Building Integrated Solar Thermal) kit.

Table 5: BIST kit

Energy generation BIST kit (façade)	
Component	Provider
1. Timber-based façade	RHB
2. Solar thermal panels	NBK, SERNEO

In addition, it is also possible to consider the timber-based façade and -roof with passive cladding developed by RHB as a kit itself, the kit “0”. In this view, also for the RHB façade and roof it is possible to distinguish components that can be optimized with the LCA and LCC support, see table below.

Table 6: Wooden-based kit

Timber-based system for façade/roof kit	
Component	Provider
1.Layers	RHB
2.Connectors	RHB

Different options are compared for the different product systems. This includes a comparison of different **materials, connections and configurations** (e.g. one additional layer, component). The different kits are compared against a baseline solution. Following individual meetings with kit developers, it was possible to define which alternatives and baseline would be investigated for the different kits and components.

Table 7 and Table 8 report a description of the different kits and investigated options for both façade and roof solutions. For more details, see the section concerning system boundaries in chapter 2.1.3.2 and the respective kit LCA and LCC sections in chapter 2.3.

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Table 7: List of variants and baselines investigated for each kit, façade

Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
0-Timber-based facade	The timber-based prefabricated module is the base element in which the different multifunctionalities will be integrated. The module is composed of a wooden frame (beams and columns) with insulation panel within it, one inner and one outer layer of panel (OSB or similar), vapour barrier, waterproof and windproof layer and the external cladding with its wooden substructure. In the inner part, also a compensation layer made of soft insulation panels to "adapt" it to the existing façade will be included.	-improve the building thermal performances à reduction in the Heating and Cooling demand; -support the INFINITE integrations (KITS) in term of load and overall performances (water-air tightness).
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark
Typical passive façade	Timber-based (frame) ventilated façade with stone wool insulation and compensation layer and High-Pressure Laminates (HPL) panels as cladding.	Traditional ventilated façade with EPS insulation.
Options at the component level		
Component: Layers		
Alternative compensation layer	Alternative materials for compensation layer: 1. stone wool; 2. glass wool; 3. wood-fiber	Typical passive façade
Alternative cladding	Alternative material for cladding: 1. HPL panels; 2. Wood cladding	Typical passive façade
Alternative end of life scenarios	Alternative end of life options for façade layers: 1. Average market from LCA database ecoinvent 3.8; 2. Incineration-oriented scenario; 3. Recycling-oriented scenario; 4. Best case scenario: recycling and reuse	Typical passive façade
Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
1-Eco-compatible green envelope kit	The façade greening solution integrates a set of possible modular and non-modular green systems which match at best with the industrialisation principles with the RHB wood-based structure. The Green part of the KIT is considered as the external cladding anchored, with a metal substructure, to the prefab facade. The Green KIT could include several possible grey water treatment possibilities and a Bio Electrochemical System evaluation.	-improve the building thermal performances à lowering the summer overheating; -enhance the micro-climate, save and reuse water, preserve the wild-life (bees), etc.
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark

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Green Living Wall	The Green system is based on the Fytotextile system by Terapia Urbana mounted on a galvanized steel frame	-
Options at the component level		
Component: Green Living Wall		
Option name	Description	Baseline
Alternative end of life scenarios	Alternative end-of-life scenarios for Fytotextile component: 1. Incineration; 2. recycling	Incineration option
Alternative irrigation operation	Alternative irrigation of Green Living Wall: 1. Irrigation with tap water and no drain water recycling; 2. Irrigation with grey water and drain water recycling	Irrigation with tap water and no drain water recycling
Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
2-Energy and fresh air distribution kit	The kit is based on the integration of the following main active components in the envelope module: (1) Mechanical Ventilation Unit (MVU) with heat recovery and water coil for air heating and cooling. (2) Air ducts with connection points for fresh and exhaust air. (3) Water pipes from the centralised energy generation. (4) Electric wires. (5) Sensing and control unit.	Provide fresh air for hygienic purposes, as well as space heating and cooling energy to satisfy the thermal demand of the dwellings.
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark
Semi-decentralized ventilation and energy distribution	Semi-decentralized ventilation, heating and cooling per dwelling (1 mechanical ventilation unit covers 40 m ² of heated floor area)	Average ventilation system, decentralized with polyethylene ducts
Options at the component level		
Component: energy and fresh air distribution module		
Option name	Description	Baseline
Material alternatives for external case of MVU	Alternative MVU case: 1. Galvanized steel case; 2. Self-bearing case insulation material; Steel case with high recycled content	Galvanized steel case
Kit name	Description	Function/benefit

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3-Integrated smart window kit	The smart window kit is an easy-to-install smart and adaptive glazing solutions, integrated in an industrialised façade, to increase indoor comfort and reduce energy consumption. The main feature is to provide an autonomous, sensing and dynamic glazing unit, to improve the control of the solar radiation. The Smart window KIT will develop a set of different Smart Glazing units (see options).	Improve the control of the solar radiation with 3 different Smart Glazing units package solutions à lower the internal overheating risk, lowering the energy consumption, improve the visual comfort, provide privacy etc. At facade level, a proper integration of the new window will assure a reduction of cold bridges.
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark
Integrated shading system with solar control system	Triple glazing with solar control system and integrated blinds in IGU	Triple-glazing unit
Plasmochromic Glass	Double-glazing with plasmochromic device	Double-glazing unit
Options at the component level		
Component: Plasmochromic window		
Option name	Description	Baseline
Alternative energy source for operation	Alternative operation of control system: 1. With electricity from grid; 2. With self-powered module (electricity from photovoltaic cells)	Operation with electricity from grid
Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
4-Energy generation BIPV kit	The BIPV envelope kit is conceived as a glass-glass PV system integrated in the wooden-based prefab envelope systems (both roof and façade). This kit is looking specifically to 3 main aspects: (i) Technology interconnection (interfaces, overall construction optimisation and fire-safety); (ii) Aesthetic interconnection (color, finishing of the front glass); (iii) Energy interconnection (maximization of the energy match between the produced and consumed energy on-site and its relation with the building energy systems).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Produce renewable energy; -Decrease the electricity grid demand; -Integrate the PV panels "hidden" as external cladding (aesthetic aspects); -Maximize the energy "matching" between production and consumption.
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark

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Chemical anchoring	Tape to glue brackets to the back of the PV panel	Standard glass-foil PV integrated in façade
Hybrid anchoring	Aluminium profile integrated between the two glasses of PV panel during the production process	Chemical anchoring
Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
5-Energy generation BIST kit	The BIST kit (Building Integrated Solar Thermal) is the integration of a solar thermal collector as energy generating cladding system under a Plug&Build logic to assure easy installation, maintenance and clean end-of-life. Thanks to a plug and play connector, the panels - as cassettes - can easily be pre-installed on the desired façades on a timber frame structure. The integration of the BIST panels into the timber frame modules is mechanical, aesthetical and hydraulic. The manufacturing will be done using a "robotic manufacturing process".	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Produce Hot Water; -Coupling with the existing system; -Decrease the energy consumption; -Integrate the BIST as a cladding in the façade (aesthetic aspects).
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark
Copper manifold	Aluminium solar collector with XPS insulation. Hydraulic system based on copper manifolds connected to the panels through flexible steel pipes and brass connectors	Standard solar-thermal panels
Options at the component level		
Component: hydraulic system		
Option name	Description	Baseline
Plug & play	Hydraulic system based on plug and play system made of plastics	Hydraulic system with copper manifold
Component: solar thermal panel		
Option name	Description	Baseline
Alternative 3rd layer materials	Steel as alternative possible panel layer	Standard panel with Aluminium layer

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Table 8: List of variants and baselines investigated for each kit, roof

Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
0-Wood-based System for roof	The wood-based prefabricated module is the base element in which will be integrated the different multifunctionalities. The element is composed by a wooden frame (beams and columns) with insulation panel within it, one inner and one outer layer of panel (OSB or similar), vapour barrier, waterproof and windproof layer and the external cladding/tiles with its wooden substructure.	Improve the building thermal performances à reduction in the Heating and Cooling demand on the building
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark
Standard roof	Timber-based (frame) ventilated roof with stone wool insulation and compensation layer and steel cladding.	Traditional ventilated roof with stone wool insulation.
Kit name	Description	Function/benefit
2-Energy generation BIPV kit	The BIPV envelope kit is conceived as a glass-glass PV system integrated in the wooden-based prefab envelope systems (both roof and façade). This kit is looking specifically to 3 main aspects: (i) Technology interconnection (interfaces, overall construction optimisation and fire-safety); (ii) Energy interconnection (maximization of the energy match between the produced and consumed energy on-site and its relation with the building energy systems).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Produce renewable energy; -Decrease the electricity grid demand; -Maximize the energy "matching" between production and consumption.
Options at the kit level		
Option name	Description	Benchmark
Chemical anchoring	Tape to glue brackets to the back of the PV panel	Standard glass-foil PV mounted on roof

2.1.3 Scope of the LCC

The Life Cycle Cost analysis is well established in the common practice to evaluate all the costs for a certain product or element during its value chain to evaluate the costs impact of each activity/product in term of cost. The reference norm for the building sector is the ISO 15686-5:2017 Buildings and constructed assets — Service life planning — Part 5: Life-cycle costing. To better understand the content and the scope of the norm, here the abstract is reported:

The norm provides requirements and guidelines for performing life-cycle cost (LCC) analyses of buildings and constructed assets and their parts, whether new or existing. The Life-cycle costing takes into account cost or cash flows, i.e. relevant costs (and income and externalities if included in the agreed scope) arising from acquisition through operation to disposal. The Life-cycle costing typically includes a comparison between alternatives or an estimate of future costs at portfolio, project or component level. Life-cycle costing is performed over an agreed period of analysis, clearly identifying whether the analysis is for only part of or for the entire life cycle of the constructed asset.

The evaluation done within task 4.8 follows the principle of the previous norm but with a simplified approach in order to have as a final result the cost (€/sqm) of the different kits as for the “business as usual” without taking into account the end-of-life costs impacts. In this case the cost is comparable with most of the façade and roof “packages” ready on the market such as ETICS, Ventilated Façade, traditional roof, etc.. The analysis focused the attention on the following costs items (i) material and products, (ii) assembling effort (workforce) (iii) use of equipment and tools, (iv) electricity and other energy sources, (v) packaging, (vi) transportation and (vii) landyard materials and activities for the installation.

The data gathering process has been done with the following steps: (i) a preliminary step with a Cost breakdown and a excel file implementation, (ii) dedicated one-to-one meeting with each technology provider and the system integrator to explain the scope and the data needs, (iii) collecting data from technology providers, (iv) first data elaboration, (v) second one-to-one meeting with the technology providers explaining the data elaboration and asking the missing data, (vi) second data analysis and results elaboration.

The LCC kits results has been presented kit by kit with diagrams at 2 levels (i) at kit level, so prefabricated façade + add-on (the kit character) and (ii) at more detailed scale looking at the different costs categories.

The LCC analysis of the kit is linked to the task 6.4 where these data have been used for the LCC analysis of real buildings renovation (INFINITE DEMOS) comparing it with a traditional deep renovation. This specific analysis will be reported in a dedicated chapter of the deliverable 6.4.

It should be underlined that these data collection and activities were carried out during a particular unstable market period (end 2021-end 2022) due to war crisis, material scarcity and particular national subsidies (like 110 bonus in Italy). From the specific meeting with the partners has come out the large uncertainties in providing reliable costs-prices.

2.1.3.1 Functional unit

The definition of the functional unit (FU) of the study is crucial to **compare different options for the individual kits and to compare the kits against a baseline situation** (if applicable). The functional unit represents a quantification of the function and performance of the products under study.

Different functional units have been defined for each kit. It is important to define a FU also for components when meaningful for the technology providers and if different component alternatives need to be compared.

Functional unit is reported below for the different kits and for components that are individually assessed.

Components - facade

C 1 Green living wall FU: 1 m².

C 2 Energy and fresh air distribution system FU: 40 m² of net floor area covered by one mechanical ventilation unit for energy and fresh air distribution.

C 3.1 Plasmochromic module FU: 1 m² with thermal transmittance $U_g < 1.3 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$, durability >100000 cycles, air tightness Class A4 (EN12207), energy consumption <500W/m², T_{LUM} bleach/col 0.65-0.05 (dynamic range), T_{NIR} bleach/col 0.70-0.03 (dynamic range), Solar Heat Gain Coefficient 0.61-0.08 (dynamic range).

C 3.2 Sensor and solar technology FU: 1 item.

C 4 Photovoltaic panel: 1 m² of PV panel with nominal power of 140 Wp/m² for façade integration.

C 5 Solar thermal panel: 1 m² of solar thermal panel for façade integration.

Components – roof

C 4: FU Photovoltaic panel: 1 m² of PV panel with nominal power of 130 Wp/m² for roof integration.

Kits - facade

KIT 0 Timber-based façade FU: 1 m² of a timber-based façade with thermal transmittance (U) of 0.16 W/m²K.

KIT 1 Eco-compatible green envelope kit FU: 1 m² of green living wall installed on a timber-based façade (see KIT 0).

KIT 2: Energy and fresh air distribution envelope kit FU: 1 m² of a timber-based façade (see KIT 0), with energy and fresh air distribution.

KIT 3: Integrated smart window kit:

KIT 3.1 smart plasmochromic window FU: 1 m² of double-glazing window (including frame) with plasmochromic glass laminated in the IGU.

KIT 3.2 smart window with solar technology FU: 1 m² of triple glazing window (including frame) with sensor and solar technology and blinds integrated in the IGU.

KIT 4 Energy generation BIPV (Building Integrated Photovoltaic) kit FU: 1 m² of photovoltaic panel integrated in a timber-based façade (see KIT 0).

KIT 5 Energy generation BIST (Building Integrated Solar Thermal) kit: FU: 1 m² of solar panel integrated in a timber-based façade (see KIT 0).

Kits – roof

KIT 0 Timber-based roof FU: 1 m² of a timber-based roof with thermal transmittance (U) of 0.20 W/m²K.

KIT 4 Energy generation BIPV (Building Integrated Photovoltaic) kit FU: 1 m² of photovoltaic panel integrated in a timber-based roof (see KIT 0).

2.1.3.2 System boundary

The following life cycle phases are included to model the product systems listed in Section 2.1.2.1:

- Raw materials acquisition (feeding both components and kit manufacturing);
- Components manufacturing & packaging;
- Components transport;
- Kit manufacturing;
- Packaging of the kits;
- Kit transport;
- Kit installation;
- Use and maintenance of the kits;
- End of Life of the kits.

Infrastructure and equipment (e.g. machineries) for components and kit manufacturing are currently excluded from the boundaries of the environmental LCA study. Specific life cycle stages for kits and components may have been excluded depending on the purpose of the study. Detailed information about system boundaries for the LCA of components and kits is provided in chapter 2.3.

2.1.3.3 Allocation

Allocation is applied to partition the flows of a process when this produces two or more products as output. Allocation may be needed if by-products are generated during the manufacturing processes of the kits and components. In that case, economic or physical allocation will be applied.

2.1.3.4 Data requirements

The aim is to use **primary data** to a large extent. They are provided by technological developers with on-site measurements, simulations, and evaluations.

When primary data are not available, secondary data provided by Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) and well-established databases are used. Specifically, **ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off** is the database used for environmental LCA.

2.1.3.5 Impact assessment methodology and selected impact categories

The environmental LCA is performed in the openLCA software (version ≥ 1.11). openLCA is an open source and free software for Sustainability and Life Cycle Assessment developed by GreenDelta GmbH. To conduct the environmental LCA, the **Environmental Footprint v.3 impact assessment method** is applied. The analyzed impact categories for the different methods are reported below in Table 9.

Table 9: Impact categories considered in the LCA study

Name	Reference unit
Acidification	mol H+ eq
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq
Land use	Pt
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq
Particulate matter	disease inc.
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq
Resource use, fossils	MJ
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq
Water use	m ³ depriv.

2.1.3.6 Interpretation of results

This procedure starts with the performance of a **contribution analysis** to identify key hotspots and main drivers of impacts.

Furthermore, as recommended by ISO14044, a **completeness and consistency** check is performed. Besides, a **sensitivity analysis** is foreseen, for instance to evaluate how results change for different supplier locations and material type. An uncertainty analysis might be performed as well, depending on the availability of measurements' distributions.

2.1.3.7 Assumptions

Assumptions are linked to the system boundaries and data collection procedures. Detailed information about assumptions for the LCA of components and kits is provided in chapter 2.3.

2.1.3.8 Limitations

Limitations are linked to the assumptions of the study. Detailed information about limitations for the LCA of components and kits is provided in chapter 2.3.

Results are referred to kit development finalized to validate the INFINITE approach with demo buildings located in Italy, France and Slovenia. In the event of different application, data collection may need to be performed again together with the calculation and interpretation of results. However, the present study offers identification of hotspots and conclusions that can be considered as a starting point for assessing impacts in other retrofit interventions.

2.1.3.9 Data quality requirements

Primary data are preferred for the foreground system. Furthermore, **data quality** is tracked for all information used and received. Data quality is shown at least for the main processes of the foreground models for all kits in a specific chapter of the study.

2.1.3.10 Critical review

It is not foreseen. However, results are presented and evaluated by the project partners.

2.1.4 Link between LCA/LCC in Task 4.8 and 6.4

Task 6.4 aims at assessing the sustainability performance of industrialized retrofit solutions developed by INFINITE. These solutions are made of the different envelope kits assessed in Task 4.8. However, the difference is that the whole building level is considered in Task 6.4. Thus, different system boundaries and functional unit need to be considered. The goal of the study in Task 6.4 is to **compare impacts between the industrialized retrofit vs the traditional retrofit** of the demo buildings.

The FU to assess the industrialized retrofit at the building level in Task 6.4 is the following: providing a living environment to the inhabitants of a retrofitted building over a time period of 50 years under well-being conditions (to be specified). Impacts would be calculated per m²/year.

The system boundaries considered in the study are:

- Raw materials acquisition and manufacturing of the kits (from Task 4.8);
- Packaging of the kits (from Task 4.8);
- Transport of the kits on site (from Task 4.8);
- Installation of the kits (from Task 4.8);
- Operation of the building;
- Maintenance of the building (including maintenance of the kits from Task 4.8);
- End of Life of the building (including End of Life of the kits from Task 4.8).

2.2 Hotspots screening from literature, EPDs and LCA databases

In order to understand the **state of the art** for the LCA/LCC and already identified **environmental hotspots** of industrialized envelope kits, a literature review was conducted considering the different systems under development in INFINITE. The review was combined with hotspots screening through Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) and existing datasets from internationally recognized LCA databases.

2.2.1 Timber-based facade

RHB provided data regarding materials of a Typical passive façade (3,40m x 9,60m) without window. Data concerned typical layer thickness, size and availability of **Environmental Product Declarations** (EPDs). For most of the layers of the façade an EPD could be found and was, therefore, used as a basis for a preliminary LCA screening. No data concerning energy and consumables for the assembly of the façade were collected at this stage of the project. **The LCA screening focuses only on the life cycle stages A1 (raw material supply), A2 (transport) and A3 (manufacturing)** for each layer, given that these were the stages covered by all EPDs for the different materials. All EPDs were created following the EN 15804:2012+A1:2013 schema, which became outdated in summer 2022. After July 2020, EN 15804:2012+A2:2019 EPDs has therefore become the mandatory schema for.

The **environmental impact categories** considered in this preliminary screening are those considered in the EN 15804:2012+A1:2013 schema, as follows:

- Global warming potential (GWP) [kg CO₂-Eq.]
- Depletion potential of the stratospheric ozone layer (ODP) [kg CFC11-Eq.]
- Acidification potential of land and water (AP) [kg SO₂-Eq.]
- Eutrophication potential (EP) [kg (PO₄)₃--Eq.]
- Formation potential of tropospheric ozone photochemical oxidants (POCP) [kg ethene-Eq.]
- Abiotic depletion potential for non-fossil resources (ADPE, non-fossil) [kg Sb-Eq.]
- Abiotic depletion potential for fossil resources (ADPF, fossil) [MJ].

Results are calculated for **1 RHB façade module of 32.64 m²**.

2.2.1.1 Inventory analysis

The standard RHB façade is made of 9 layers with different functions, e.g. compensation, vapour barrier, etc. An overview of the different layers, related dimensions and materials is provided in Table 10. The only two layers for which an EPD was not available were the vapour barrier and the waterproofing and windproofing layer. In the first case, an air sealing tape by 3M instead of Siga Rissan was assumed (3M™ Flexible Air Sealing Tape Ultra-Conformable 8045). In the latter case, the BauBook calculator database¹ provides results for the layer under study for the stages A1-A3 and for all impact categories under study, except for ADPE fossil and non-fossil. Please consider the use of the proxy vapour barrier and incomplete results for the waterproofing and windproofing.

¹ Dörken Delta Foxx Plus. Available at: <https://www.baubook.at/m/PHP/Info.php?SI=2142711527&SW=2&win=y> Last accessed: 27.09.21. The study is supposed to be updated by the producer, according to the website.

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Table 10: List of layers of standard timber-based facade without window

STANDARD FACADE MODULE (3,40m x 9,60m) WITHOUT WINDOW								
Type of Layer	Typical components	thickness [mm]	Density	Product commercial name (if available)	Total surface for standard module (m ²)	TOTAL VOLUME, if applicable (m ³)	EPD available	Comment
Compensation Layer	Mineral wool	40	60 kg/m ³	Rockwool 226	32.64	1.3056	EPD-RW-11-2019-Adriatic-EN-0004	The EPD is referred to a standard Rockwool product. To obtain the impacts for the specific Rockwool product, one should multiply the impact value by the scaling factor provided in the EPD (1.9) and the Rd value for the specific thickness (for 40 mm, the Rd is 1.1)
Inner Planking	OSB-3	15	607 kg/m ³	Egger OSB-3	32.64	n/a	EPD-EGG-20180107-IBD1-EN	15 mm assumed according to documentation for presizing
Vapour barrier	Adhesive type	negligible		Siga Rissan	7.3	n/a	S-P-00988	Air sealing tape from 3M (3M™ Flexible Air Sealing Tape Ultra-Conformable 8045) assumed as proxy
Timber-based structure	Strength-sorted construction timber	160	465 kg/m ³	Rubner FST	n/a	0.942	EPD-RUB-20180059-IBB1-EN	
Insulation Layer	Mineral wool	160	60 kg/m ³	Rockwool 226	30.6	4.896	EPD-RW-11-2019-Adriatic-EN-0004	The EPD is referred to a standard Rockwool product. To obtain the impacts for the specific Rockwool product, one should multiply the impact value by the scaling factor provided in the EPD (1.9) and the Rd value for the specific thickness (for 160 mm, the Rd is 4.55)
Outer Planking	Vapour-permeable wood fiber boards	15	615 kg/m ³	Egger DHF	32.64	n/a	EPD-EGG-20140196-IBA1-DE	15 mm assumed according to documentation for predimension. A more updated EPD has been released (the one provided from RHB expired). However, values from the old EPD are used to be consistent with the A1 EPD schema

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Wood vertical mullion	Strength-sorted construction timber	60	465 kg/m ³	Rubner FST	n/a	0.261	EPD-RUB-20180059-IBB1-EN	
Waterproofing Windproofing	Membrane	negligible	0.27 kg/m ²	Dörken Delta Foxx Plus	32.64	n/a	no	In absence of EPD, results are available for A1-A3 phases from Baubook https://www.baubook.at/m/PHP/Info.php?SI=2142711527&SW=2&win=y . The study is supposed to be updated by the producer, according to the website
External Cladding	HPL panels	8.21	11.9 kg/m ²	HPL Exterior	32.64	0.09792	EPD-FMX-20190036-IBA2-DE	

2.2.1.2 Result analysis and interpretation

Table 11 reports the results for the environmental impacts of a standard RHB façade of 32.64 m².

Table 11: Environmental impacts for the standard RHB facade (32.64 m²)

Production stage A1-A3	GWP	ODP	AP	EP	POCP	ADPE (non fossil)	ADPF (fossil)
Standard facade module (32.64 m²)	kg CO2eq	kg CFC11eq	kgS O2	kgPO4 eq	kg Ethene eq.	kg Sbeq.	MJ
Compensation layer	83.20	0.00	0.58	0.05	0.03	0.00	928.00
Inner planking	- 369.00	0.00	0.45	0.11	0.26	0.00	2100.00
Vapor barrier (tape)	58.90	0.00	0.22	1.78	0.02	0.00	1140.00
Rubner FST	- 635.00	0.00	1.05	0.21	0.10	0.00	1060.00
Insulation layer	319.00	0.00	2.21	0.20	0.13	0.00	3560.00
Outer planking	- 367.00	0.00	1.68	0.47	1.32	0.00	1590.00
Waterproofing and windproofing	49.20	0.00	0.21	0.13	0.01	-	-
Wood vertical mullions	- 176.00	0.00	0.29	0.06	0.03	0.00	292.00
Cladding	682.00	0.00	1.43	0.32	0.17	0.00	17000.00
Total	- 354.00	0.00	8.11	3.34	2.07	0.00	27700.00
Total (without cladding)	- 1040.00	0.00	6.69	3.02	1.90	0.00	10700.00

Depending on the impact category considered, it is possible to highlight different materials as the main drivers to environmental impacts, see Figure 1. The analysis of results is based on what is available in the EPD description concerning the analysis of results and this is complemented with the analysis of generic processes with the EuGeos database in openLCA software. The main hotspots that can be detected are:

- **Cladding (High-Pressure laminates** made out of paper layers and resins) shows significant impacts on Global Warming Potential (due to CO₂ emissions during manufacturing), Acidification (due to emissions from raw materials, specifically kraft liner and phenol resin, and NO_x and SO₂ from energy supply) and fossil and non-fossil resource depletion (because of fossil fuels and non-fossil resources linked to phenol and kraft liner production).
- **Outer planking (moisture resistant wood-fiber board)** highly contributing to Acidification because of process emissions (Nitric oxide and Nitrogen oxide) in fiber preparation, Eutrophication due to Nitrogen monoxide emissions in fiber preparation and Nitrous oxide emitted during plate preparation, and Photochemical oxidation associated with formaldehyde emissions in fiber processing.
- **Insulation (stone wool)** which shows a contribution in all categories ranging between 6% and 27%, for instance regarding Global warming Potential (carbon-dioxide emitted during stone wool production), Acidification (due to sulphur dioxide emitted during stone wool production), and resource depletion (due to insulation raw materials and coke to melt raw materials in furnaces).

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Further contributions to Acidification are due to the Rubner Structural Finger jointed Timber (**FST**) because of emissions due to heat for drying the lamella and thermal treatment of wooden residues at the production site. The **vapour barrier** (adhesive tape) emerges as the main driver to Eutrophication because of the production of the acrylic binder and to non-fossil resource depletion (likely due to factory construction to produce the binder and tape). However, please note that the vapour barrier has been currently modelled with proxy data and the model of this layer have to be improved in the future, given its influence on some categories. The only category where the **waterproofing and windproofing layer** shows a relevant impact (85%) is the Ozone depletion one, likely due to adhesive zones production and emissions during manufacturing of polyethylene. More updated data would be needed to confirm waterproofing and windproofing layers as a hotspot.

Finally, negative impacts in Global Warming (hence credits for the system) are due to the high amount of wood used for the façade layers, namely the wood-based structure FST, the mullions, the inner (OSB) and outer (wood-fiber board) planking. The consideration of biogenic carbon in the life cycle of wood-based product is crucial for the new EPD schema EN 15804:2012+A2:2019 and may lead to changes in results calculated with the old schema EN 15804:2012+A1:2013.

Figure 1: Layer contribution to environmental impacts of standard RHB façade

If results are recalculated without the contribution of the cladding (which may consist of several options), the identification of the **outer planking and insulation layer** as hotspots is more evident, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Layer contribution to environmental impacts of standard RHB facade (without cladding)

2.2.2 Eco-compatible green envelope

Manso et al. (Manso, 2018) present the **LCA of a green wall and green roof system** that comprises industrial waste and sustainable materials. This modular greening system is called Geogreen, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Display of Geogreen modular system as described by Manso et al. (2018)

When compared with other living walls, Geogreen fared better on all three categories considered for the comparison, **global warming potential (GWP)**, **Human Toxicity Potential (HTP)** and **freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity potential (FAETP)**. Geogreen system was tested in Mediterranean climate conditions. Results show that thermal gains by conduction is reduced by 75% in warmer season, and thermal losses is reduced by 60% in colder season. **High GWP impact is due to alkali activated precast curing process.** Other **cladding system** using ceramic façade panels has 14% lower GWP, but 7 times higher Human Toxicity Potential. GWP impacts were found to be resulting from the **support**

system, which is the alkali activated precast slab. The study also made comparisons with other similar LCA studies and concludes that differences in results are mainly due to **supporting materials** and the **replacement both for plants and material**.

A cradle to grave LCA study (Vacek, 2017) of four semi intensive green roof systems considered **common assembly, assembly with added extruded polystyrene providing increased thermal resistance and two assemblies with hydrophilic mineral wool**. Semi intensive green roofs are an intermediate stage between extensive green roofs and intensive green roofs and include a multitude of built-in manmade materials such as waterproofing membranes or thermal insulation. The study has two objectives, first to evaluate and compare the environmental impacts of the green roof assemblies from using substrates or hydrophilic mineral wool, and second, to evaluate the environmental impacts related with reducing heat losses through the roof assemblies. For the first goal, functional unit is taken as 1 m² of the green roof assembly with a 200 mm thick layer of growing medium, when varying energy losses through the assessed roof assemblies is not considered. For the second goal, the functional unit includes the U-value (or thermal transmittance) set at 0.24 W·m⁻²·K⁻¹ (specified in Czech standards for a flat roof). The results show that **common assembly with no substrate or additional thermal insulation has the lowest impacts**. While hydrophilic mineral wool has other positives such as lower weight or increased water retention potential, it is not an ideal solution due to high **energy consumption** for producing the material.

A paper by Bozorg Chenani et al. (Bozorg Chenani, 2015) analyses the environmental impacts of different layers used in the build-up of **two lightweight green roof systems** (see Figure 4). The goal was to identify the layers that produce the greatest potential environmental impacts in green roof installation. The functional unit used was 1 m² of green roof during 40 years' service life. System boundary includes all the processes related to the production from the extraction and refining of raw materials to the final disposal, passing through the manufacturing of the components, and including transportation.

The two alternative green roof compositions used in this study.

Layer	Material	Weight (kg/m ²)	Thickness (mm)
Alternative 1			
Root barrier	Polyethylene (LDPE)	0.8	0.4
Protection layer	Nonwoven polypropylene (lighter)	0.3	1.8
Drainage layer	Polystyrene (recycled HIPS)	1.30	25
Water retention	Recycled textile fibers	1.2	10
Filter layer	Nonwoven polypropylene (lighter)	0.15	1.9
Substrate	Expanded clay	10	≈ 100 ^a
	Crushed brick	80	
	Compost	10	
Alternative 2			
Root barrier	PVC	1	0.8
Protection layer	Nonwoven polypropylene (heavier)	0.5	1.8
Drainage layer	Polystyrene (Virgin HIPS)	1.3	25
Water retention	Rockwool (Grodan)	4.8	40
Filter layer	Nonwoven polypropylene (heavier)	0.2	1.9
Substrate	Compost	15	≈ 100 ^b
	Sand	15	
	Pumice	70	

^a The overall thickness of the substrate is 100 mm, including expanded clay, crushed brick and compost.
^b The overall thickness of the substrate is 100 mm, including compost, sand and pumice.

Figure 4: Alternative green roof systems used in the study by Bozorg Chenani et al. (2015)

The results show that **green roofs can be environmentally positive, if several artificial layer materials are not considered**. These materials can be **rockwool, the egg carton-like plastic layers, or expanded clay**. Considering and developing alternative materials, that has the same green roof function, but minimum environmental impact is recommended. For example, in Switzerland, efficient green roof

systems without several plastic layers are used and being tested (these green roofs mainly consist of the root barrier, substrate and plants). The study also suggests that **using just a root barrier, substrate and plants leads to less environmental impact.**

An LCA study is described by Rasul and Arutla (Rasul, 2020) to evaluate the potential environmental impacts of roof greenery system of a building in Sydney, Australia. The environmental impacts of the operational energy for different types of roof systems were calculated based on the U-Value of the respective roofs. This was focused mainly on the **air conditioning system operation which is affected by the roofing system.** The cooling load due to the air conditioning system, the lighting load, operation of a normal fan and other electrical equipment were considered in calculating the environmental impacts. Results show **green roofs have 3 times lower environmental impacts compared to roof without greenery.** Study points out that the normal life cycle of the conventional roof is lower than for green roofs, which indicates that more frequent replacement or renovation requirements, thus, increasing the environmental burden of a conventional roof. Results indicate that while extensive and intensive green roofs are environmentally comparable, intensive green roof systems perform better in the urban context.

Table 4. Environmental impacts comparison of total operational energy for three types of roof systems.

Impact category	Units	Extensive green roof	Intensive green roof	Non-green roof
Abiotic depletion	kg Sb eq	4.03×10^3	3.89×10^3	4.08×10^3
Global warming (GWP100)	kg CO ₂ eq	5.09×10^5	4.90×10^5	5.14×10^5
Ozone layer depletion (ODP)	kg CFC-11 eq	0.01	0.01	0.01
Human toxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	1.43×10^5	1.38×10^5	1.45×10^5
Freshwater aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.06×10^4	1.99×10^4	2.09×10^4
Marine aquatic ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	6.56×10^8	6.32×10^8	6.63×10^8
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DB eq	2.37×10^3	2.28×10^3	2.39×10^3
Photochemical oxidation	kg C ₂ H ₄	104.63	100.75	105.69
Acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	2.87×10^3	2.77×10^3	2.90×10^3
Eutrophication	kg PO ₄ eq	184.47	177.65	186.35

Figure 5: Comparison of environmental impacts of different roof types (Rasul, 2020)

An LCA was carried out by Bianchini and Hewage (Bianchini, 2012) for green roof using **recycled and non-recycled materials.** Polyethylene low density (PE-LD) production mix at plant (RER) and polypropylene granulate (PP) production mix at plant (RER) were selected as the specific polymer materials for the root barrier and drainage, filter, and water retention layers. Results indicate **air pollution due to the polymer production process can be balanced by green roofs in 13-32 years.** However, the **manufacturing process of low density polyethylene and polypropylene has many other negative impacts** to the environment than air pollution.

Finally, this section reports on **an LCA study about a Green Living Wall by Terapia Urbana.** The LCA Study authored by Ghofran M.J.A. Salah & Dr. Anna Romanova, titled “Life Cycle Assessment of **Felt System Living Green Wall: Cradle to Grave Case Study**” (Sala, 2021) analyzed a selected Living Green Wall (LGW) designed by Scotscape Ltd. The study was conducted in United Kingdom (UK) and examined the Fytotextile® system used by Terapia Urbana company² with a focus on the Global

² Terapia Urbana, 2019. Technical description of fytotextile® system. Available at: <https://www.terapiaurbana.es/en/fytotextile-vertical-garden/jardin-vertical-fytotextile/>. Last accessed: 28.09.21

Warming Potential category (kg CO₂ eq.). The selected LGW has a size of 17m², as the model was built in Webber Street, near Waterloo station, London, 2015.

The module is 2.6 mm thick and consists of three synthetic layers, shown in Figure 6: **an outer hydrophobic layer made of polyamide, an inner layer of recycled hydrophobic fibers (geotextile) which are non-woven and micro-perforated to improve their permeability to water, and a waterproof back layer made of flexible PVC.**

Figure 6: Fytotextile® Living Wall System (Sala, 2021)

Each module has 49 pockets in which plants are placed with their root balls. **Irrigation is provided by horizontal pipe with drip emitters placed in the upper part of each module between the middle and outer layers.** Each irrigation line has 7 self-compensating emitters with a flow of 1.6 l/h. The irrigation lines are connected by vertical pipe that led to the entrance of the water supply network. In this irrigation system, the excess water is left for watering in a closed system connected to reservoirs where water is reused for LGW irrigation. **The water and electrical supply are located in the technical room.**

The exact amount of the materials used for the GLW is shown in Table 12. **The chosen functional unit in the study is 1 m². The water consumption is assumed to be 2 l/m² per day.** The life cycle stages considered in this analysis are: **raw material acquisition, production, transportation, installation, operation, maintenance and disposal for the facades area.**

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Table 12: Inventory data collection for Fytotextile® Living Wall System (Sala, 2021)

Components	Material	Weight (kg/m ²)	Distance (miles)	Distance (km)	Service Life (years)
Metal Structure	Aluminium Alloy (AA)	3.9	22	35	10
Outer Layer	Polyamide (PA)	0.6	1731	2786	10
Inner Layer	Polypropylene Fibre (PPF)	0.3	1731	2786	10
Waterproof Layer	PVC	1	1731	2786	10
Steel Strips	Galvanised Steel (GS)	0.2	1731	2786	10
Growing Medium	Black Compost Soil (BCS)	18	22	35	10
Vegetation Layer	Selected Plants	8	446	718	10
Irrigation	Polyethylene Pipe (PE)	0.09	12605	20286	10

The equivalent carbon emissions for each stage manufacturing, construction, maintenance, and end of use processes are listed in Table 13. The calculations are presented in kg CO₂eq. over 10-years of service life. Emissions from each component were quantified based on the required material per 1 m² of the selected LGW. One particular note is that **the manufacturing phase is responsible for 80.67% of the total CO₂e emissions, with Aluminium Alloy (AA) of the metal profiles (3,9 kg/m²) accounting for the largest share of released emissions at 31.886 kg CO₂eq compared to other processes.**

Table 13: The CO₂e Emissions Released from producing 1 m² of Living Green Wall in kg CO₂eq (Sala, 2021)

Process	AA	PA	PPF	PVC	GS	BSC	Plants	PE	Water	Total
Manufacturing	31.886	2.196	1.162	3.643	0.590	2.174	1.352	1.524	0	44.527
Construction	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.055	0.055	1.432	0.055	0	1.817
Maintenance	0	0	0	0	0	1.140	4.290	0	2.511	7.941
End of Use	0.082	0.013	0.006	0.021	0.004	0.540	0.240	0.002	0	0.908
Total Emission kgCO₂e /1m²										55.193

The study showed that 1 m² of the selected GLW system is responsible for 55.193 kg CO₂eq emission. **A comparison was made to compare 6 different walls in terms of GHG emissions** (kg CO₂eq), which is shown in Table 14 (Fytotextile LGW as “selected felt system”). The walls were compared based on 50 years useful life. Table 14 shows that **the Fytotextile GLW has the lowest GHG emissions, indicating a promising GLW which can help in reducing the GHG emissions and shorten the time of air balancing period** (Sala, 2021).

Table 14: Total Emission Comparison for 6 different walls (Sala, 2021)

Process	Types of Living Green Walls					
	Bare Wall	Planter Boxes	Mineral Wool	Foam	Felt Layer	Selected Felt System
Manufacturing	82.270	143.090	147.850	135.170	147.810	126.797
Construction	2.810	5.400	5.920	5.210	5.520	4.627
Maintenance	0	622.560	622.580	622.560	622.590	33.705
Total Emission Kg CO ₂ e/m ²	85.080	771.050	776.350	776.350	775.920	165.129

2.2.3 Energy and fresh air distribution kit

An environmental hotspot screening of **different ventilation systems available in EuGeos EN15804 database** was performed.

The house considered in the study includes 6 flats, each with 130 m² floor area and a ventilation rate of 120 m³/h. It is assumed that the lifetime of the system and ducts is 50 years, whereas the lifetime of ventilation unit is 20 years. The filter can last up to 1 year.

Some other assumption for all processes made for the calculation are provided in the database documentation: the influence of a smaller concrete demand due to embedment of ventilation tubes in the concrete of the floor is not included, **electricity for the operation of the system on 12 months per year** is included, transport of the components to the construction site, disposal of the components are included and influence of ventilation ducts on building construction is not included.

In the EuGeos database, there are 3 types of ventilation systems that differ by the material or the technologies itself, namely:

- Based on the **material** being used for the distribution of fresh- and exhaust- air within the flat: **galvanized (coated with a thin zinc layer) steel ducts / polyethylene ducts.**
- Based on the ventilation system after air intake on the facade: **centralized or decentralized ventilation units.**
- Centralized or decentralized ventilation system **with/without 4 parallel polyethylene ground heat exchanger tubes.**

The combination of these types leads to 6 different processes under investigation:

- ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h, polyethylene ducts | ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h | Cutoff, U
- ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h, steel ducts | ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h | Cutoff, U
- ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h, polyethylene ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger | ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h | Cutoff, U
- ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h, steel ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger | ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h | Cutoff, U

- ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m³/h, polyethylene ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger | ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m³/h | Cutoff, U
- ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m³/h, steel ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger | ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m³/h |Cutoff, U.

All processes investigated are referred to Switzerland. To avoid considering impacts of ventilation occurring in buildings outside Europe, Switzerland was the best available location for the purpose of the study. The comparison of the individual processes is based on 10 impact indicators, as can be seen in Table 15.

The results were calculated with the EN15804:2012+A2 method for **1 m² of dwelling ventilated per year**, considering a ventilation rate of 120 m³/h (6 flats with a floor area of 130 m²). Note that the lowest relative impacts are identified as green numbers and the highest relative impact are identified as red numbers. For a better understanding of the results, it is necessary to identify the processes that contribute the most to the results, also known as hotspots. To provide a good overview of the comparison, each ventilation model will hence be referred as Process 1 to 6 as in Table 15.

Overall, all these processes have similarities: the greatest environmental impact in all categories occurs mainly in the use phase. This can be seen in the hotspots of each product. Namely one that contributes the most to the acidification, GWP Total, Ozone Depletion, and the water consumption are all due to the same process “Market for electricity, high voltage”, which is necessary for low-voltage electricity production, as shown in Figure 7.

Table 15: Environmental impacts of 6 different types of ventilation system

Impact Indicator	Process						Unit
	1	2	3	4	5	6	
	Impact result						
El acidification	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	[molc H+ eq]
El climate change, GWP total	0.73	0.84	0.81	0.92	0.68	0.78	[kg CO ₂ eq]
El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPE elements	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	[kg Sb-Eq]
El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPF fossil fuels	10.00	11.50	11.20	12.70	9.36	10.90	[MJ]
El eutrophication, freshwater	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	[kg P eq]
El eutrophication, marine	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	[kg N eq]
El eutrophication, terrestrial	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	[molc N eq]
El ozone depletion	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	[kg CFC11 eq]
El photochemical ozone formation	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	[kg NMVOC eq]
El water use, AWARE	2410.00	2410.00	2220.00	2220.00	2210.00	2214.30748	[m ³]

Nr.:	Process:
1	ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U
2	ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, steel ducts ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U
3	ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U
4	ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, steel ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U
5	ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m ³ /h Cutoff, U
6	ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m ³ /h, steel ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m ³ /h Cutoff, U

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Figure 7: Impact analysis for Process 1

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Based on the summary in Table 15, there are also some information that can be used to compare the processes:

- **Centralized vs. decentralized ventilation unit:**

By comparing process 3 (decentralized ventilation) and 5 (centralized ventilation) as an example (see Figure 8), it appears that **centralized ventilation systems have a lower environmental impact than the decentralized ventilation units, due in part to the fact that more resources are required to manufacture a decentralized system.** Comparing the inputs and outputs between the two processes, the number of items that are required to produce the air filters, blowers and heat exchange units, silencers and control devices is about 6 times higher for process 3 (decentralized) than for process 5 (centralized), resulting in a higher environmental impact than process 5. However, please note that the electricity consumption for ventilation of operation is assumed to be the same between centralized and decentralized systems, therefore energy losses are not included in the analysis.

Figure 8: Impact analysis between process 3 (decentralized ventilation) and process 5 (centralized ventilation)

• **Steel ducts vs Polyethylene ducts:**

Comparing the process 1 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts) and 2 (decentralized ventilation, steel ducts) as presented in Figure 9, the **production of steel ducts contributes to greater relative environmental impacts than polyethylene ducts** in terms of the amount of CO₂ eq. released. Furthermore, by comparing the inputs and outputs of both processes, it appears that the number of inputs and the amount of wastes in the production of ventilation system with steel ducts is greater than the one with polyethylene ducts, which leads to a significant higher environmental impact for steel pipes than the polyethylene pipes.

Figure 9: Comparison of process 1 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts) and 2 (decentralized ventilation, steel ducts) with earth tube heat exchanger

• **Presence of heat exchanger:**

Considering and comparing process 1 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, without heat exchanger) and 3 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, with heat exchanger), it can be concluded that **earth tube heat exchanger contributes to a higher environmental impact than**

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without earth tube heat exchanger, see Figure 10. This is due to the fact that more resources and energy are needed to produce 6 earth tube heat exchangers.

ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U					ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U				
Name	Category	Inventory result	Impact factor	Impact result Unit	Name	Category	Inventory result	Impact factor	Impact result Unit
> El acidification				0.00555 molc...	> El acidification				0.00624 molc...
> El climate change, GWP biogenic				0.02203 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP biogenic				0.01906 kg CO ₂ e
> El climate change, GWP fossil				0.70675 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP fossil				0.78941 kg CO ₂ e
> El climate change, GWP land transformation				0.00137 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP land transformation				0.00142 kg CO ₂ e
> El climate change, GWP total				0.73039 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP total				0.81012 kg CO ₂ e
> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPE elements				0.00034 kg Sb _{eq}	> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPE elements				0.00049 kg Sb _{eq}
> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPF fossil fuels				10.03079 MJ	> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPF fossil fuels				11.18889 MJ
> El eutrophication, freshwater				0.00060 kg P eq	> El eutrophication, freshwater				0.00060 kg P eq
> El eutrophication, marine				0.00073 kg N _{eq}	> El eutrophication, marine				0.00080 kg N _{eq}
> El eutrophication, terrestrial				0.01232 molc...	> El eutrophication, terrestrial				0.01470 molc...
> El ozone depletion				9.35851E-8 kg CF ₄ e	> El ozone depletion				9.27181E-8 kg CF ₄ e
> El photochemical ozone formation				0.00195 kg NL _{eq}	> El photochemical ozone formation				0.00217 kg NL _{eq}
> El water use, AWARE				2410.99153 m ³	> El water use, AWARE				2216.40346 m ³

Figure 10: Comparison of process 1 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, without heat exchanger) and 3 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, with heat exchanger)

Comparing process 1 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, without heat exchanger) with the centralized model process 5 (centralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, with heat exchanger), it can be concluded that the **centralized ventilation system with the earth tube heat exchanger shows the smallest environmental impact because of the benefits due to a centralized system production**, which are not overtaken by the negative contribution of the additional production of heat exchanger in process 5 (see Figure 11).

ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m ³ /h Cutoff, U					ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m ³ /h, polyethylene ducts, with earth tube heat exchanger ventilation of dwellings, central, 1 x 720 m ³ /h Cutoff, U				
Name	Category	Inventory result	Impact factor	Impact result Unit	Name	Category	Inventory result	Impact factor	Impact result Unit
> El acidification				0.00555 molc...	> El acidification				0.00522 molc...
> El climate change, GWP biogenic				0.02203 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP biogenic				0.01973 kg CO ₂ e
> El climate change, GWP fossil				0.70675 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP fossil				0.65379 kg CO ₂ e
> El climate change, GWP land transformation				0.00137 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP land transformation				0.00123 kg CO ₂ e
> El climate change, GWP total				0.73039 kg CO ₂ e	> El climate change, GWP total				0.67497 kg CO ₂ e
> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPE elements				0.00034 kg Sb _{eq}	> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPE elements				0.00044 kg Sb _{eq}
> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPF fossil fuels				10.03079 MJ	> El depletion of abiotic resources - ADPF fossil fuels				9.55505 MJ
> El eutrophication, freshwater				0.00060 kg P eq	> El eutrophication, freshwater				0.00052 kg P eq
> El eutrophication, marine				0.00073 kg N _{eq}	> El eutrophication, marine				0.00067 kg N _{eq}
> El eutrophication, terrestrial				0.01232 molc...	> El eutrophication, terrestrial				0.01261 molc...
> El ozone depletion				9.35851E-8 kg CF ₄ e	> El ozone depletion				8.58833E-8 kg CF ₄ e
> El photochemical ozone formation				0.00195 kg NL _{eq}	> El photochemical ozone formation				0.00177 kg NL _{eq}
> El water use, AWARE				2410.99153 m ³	> El water use, AWARE				2211.20724 m ³

Figure 11: Comparison of process 1 (decentralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, without heat exchanger) and 5 (centralized ventilation, polyethylene ducts, with heat exchanger)

To conclude, all these processes have similarities, namely that their environmental impact is generated mainly from the use phase.

Table 15 shows that **a centralized ventilation system is a better option than a decentralized ventilation system. Polyethylene ducts**, as shown in Figure 9, **are better than steel ducts** in terms of the relative environmental impacts. **Efficient installation of ground pipe heat exchangers with a centralized ventilation system and polyethylene pipes appears to be the best option for the ventilation model.** On the other hand, **decentralized ventilation with steel pipes would be the worst-case scenario**, as the model requires the most energy, and resources to produce the materials, resulting in the largest environmental impacts in comparison to other processes.

2.2.4 Smart Window kit

LCA and total energy of two commercial buildings of same size and typology but differing in glazing technologies is performed by Pierucci et al (Pierucci, 2018). **Two glazing technologies are compared, one photovoltachromic windows (PVCCs) and second, commercial solar control glass panes integrated with photovoltaic (PV) panels.** The aim of the study is to evaluate the influence of PVCCs on the Life Cycle Impact and Life Cycle Total Energy of the commercial buildings. PVCCs offer a multifunctional smart glazing, enabling electric generation and smart modulation of transmittance, reducing undesired solar gains and maximising daylighting use indoor. The study also considers three different locations with different climatic conditions, Aswan (Egypt), Brindisi (Italy), and London (England). The whole building is considered as functional unit in the study. Results show that the **overall impact due to the production of a PVCC cell is considerably lower than the one of traditional technologies offering the same performances.** Adoption of **smart windows greatly reduced human toxicity potential.** For a **longer predicted life (15 years) the reduction of impact is due to operational energy consumptions,** while for **shorter time spans (5 years) the reduction of impact is due to savings on the production of the glass and the PV system.** In regions with **hot climate,** the expected benefit is largely due to the reduction of operational energy demand of buildings equipped with **smart windows,** while in **cold regions** the reduction of impact due to the adoption of a **green building-integrated technology** drives the overall benefits.

A paper by Ng and Mithraratne (Mithraratne, 2014) describes the life cycle environmental and economic performance of commercially available **semi-transparent BIPV modules for window application** under the tropical conditions of Singapore. For the study, the lifecycle stages considered are manufacturing of BIPV, transport to site, installation, operation and maintenance, decommissioning, disposal, and recycling of waste. Six modules are investigated, with different dimensions, and technical features. Results show that the **environmental burden associated with installing BIPV modules is significantly reduced if the avoided burden of double-glazed windows is deducted.** The energy and GHG emissions intensities of electricity generated by the facade systems is calculated, where module was found to have lowest impacts. Life cycle cost analysis (LCCA) is also performed for the six modules, energy payback time was less than two years while energy return on the investment could be as high as 35 times. The **viability of the semi-transparent PV systems could be improved if there is an increase in electricity prices.**

2.2.5 BIPV systems

An LCA was performed for a **building integrated concentrated photovoltaic (BICPV)** unit at the university of Lleida in Spain (Menoufi, 2013). This unit is compared with a hypothetical **conventional BIPV unit.** Results show that the **potential environmental impact can be significantly reduced by replacing the conventional unit with BIPV unit.**

Life cycle cost analysis (LCCA) was performed for a building integrated photovoltaics façade for a commercial building in Norway (Gholami, 2020). The aim of the study was to evaluate the savings in transmission line lost power, power delivery cost, societal cost of carbon (SCC) and building envelope material cost. The study also explored the impact of **different end-of-life material recovery approaches** on net present value, see Figure 12. The service life is expected to be 30 years. The calculations are based on the hourly incident radiation data between 2005 and 2006 from PVGIS. Results show that a 127.5 kWp of BIPV façade system with the estimated annual production of

55.5MWh/m² in the city Drammen, is economically feasible with a discounted payback period of 22 years, internal rate of return of 6%, cumulative net present value of 478,934 NOK³ and levelized cost of energy of 1.28 NOK/kWh.

Fig. 1. The proposed methodology for LCCA of BIPV systems.

Figure 12: Methodology for the LCCA of a BIPV system in a building (Gholami, 2020)

2.2.6 BIST systems

The LCA of a building integrated solar thermal collector (BIST) with different configurations (see Figure 13) is performed by Lamnatou et al. (Lamnatou, 2015) using different Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods, namely, Eco-Indicator 99 (EI99) and IMPACT 2002+ along with embodied energy and embodied carbon. Life cycle inventory is based on ecoinvent LCI database. The BIST unit is developed and tested at the University of Corsica. The functional unit for the study is defined as the whole unit, comprising 14 solar collectors and components such as storage tank, pump, external tubes with insulation, and glycol. The system boundaries include manufacturing, installation, operation and maintenance, transportation, and disposal. The results show that the **configuration with collectors in parallel connection has better environmental performance compared to the reference configuration with collectors in series. Using systems with double absorber surface/output and/or recycling can further reduce the impacts.**

Basic technical characteristics, annual thermal energy production and annual electricity consumption (for pumping and auxiliary heating) of the studied BI solar thermal systems (Systems 1–3).

System	Basic technical characteristics	Thermal energy production (kWh/year)	Electricity consumption for pumping (kWh/year)	Electricity consumption for auxiliary heating (kWh/year)
1 (Reference system)	Collectors of series connection; Tubes at different levels	549.16	63.03	972.10
2	Collectors of parallel connection; Tubes at different levels	811.21	61.54	815.93
3	Collectors of series connection; Tubes at the same level	884.75	63.21	770.42

Figure 13. Description for the system under comparison by Lamnatou et al. (2015)

³ Norwegian Krone

The LCA study by de Laborderie et al. (de Laborderie, 2012) aimed to evaluate the environmental performances of solar thermal installations for temperate-climate system, with solar thermal collectors and a backup energy as heat sources and tropical-climate system, with thermo-siphonic solar thermal system and no backup energy. For the temperate climate system, two options are studied for backup energy, one with gas backup energy and the second with electric backup energy. These systems are then compared with conventional scenarios, without solar thermal systems. The study also aims at identifying the most discriminating parameters to support implementation solutions. Results **for temperate-climate system show that the necessary water auxiliary heating is quite relevant for the environmental performance. Solar water heating with gas backup has higher GHG emissions compared to solar water heating with electric backup.** The **lower result for electric backup is mainly due to the French electricity mix that has particularly low carbon content: 103kg/kWh.** However, considering other impact categories, solar water heating system with gas backup has best environmental performance. For comparing energy pay-back time, only solar thermal system with gas backup is compared against conventional system, which was found to be lower than 1.5 years than conventional system. In case of tropical-climate system, water tank was found to be the most relevant to the impact results, between 31% to 60% of each impact.

2.2.7 Definition of sustainability parameters to support INFINITE kit development

In collaboration with Task 4.7, GREEND and EURAC defined a number of parameters that can drive the choice of layers and connectors in Task 4.7 considering sustainability aspects. Identified criteria are reported in Table 16 together with possible quantification units. These parameters are intended to be complementary to the deep investigations (LCA and LCC and DfA/D) reported in the next chapters. Furthermore, the proposed parameters can be used for a **first screening of alternatives** identified in Task 4.7. Finally, some of the parameters can be also directly obtained from LCA and LCC (such as Global Warming Potential).

Table 16: Proposed parameters for selection of connectors and layer alternatives in Task 4.7 (based on sustainability)

Sustainability (intended as environmental, economic, social)	UNIT 1	UNIT 2	UNIT 3
Global Warming Potential (GWP)	kg CO ₂ eq. (related to the class of materials)		
Recycled Material Content (in the components/kit analysed)	% on total or %/mc		
Waste generated during manufacturing	% on total or Kg/sqm or kg	Waste code (CER code)	
End of Life scenario	Reusability (% or 1 to 5 or table)	Recyclability (%)	Waste code (CER code)
Effort for recycling/reuse in the second life	Transformation effort (1 to 5)	Energy use (kWh/kg)	Existence of recycling/reusing pathways (1 to 5 or yes/no)

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Responsible sourcing of raw materials	Origin (natural, synthetic, etc.)	Existence of proof of sustainability (e.g. traceability of suppliers, deforestation) (yes/no)	Country of origin, from low to high risk of unsustainable business practices
Location of raw material suppliers	distance (km)	Provenance (distance in km from extraction to selling point) (Km)	
Health and safety for workers during manufacturing	Risk of accidents (1 to 5)	Handling of hazardous/toxic materials (1 to 5)	
Effect on Indoor Air Quality	VOC emissions (kg/kg)	Content of potentially harmful materials (%of total weight)	
Durability	Lifespan of product (years)		
Maintenance rate	From 1 to 5 (Easy – Hard)		

2.3 LCA results for INFINITE components

In view of supporting the design of the components, it appeared crucial to implement **a sustainability assessment approach that is customized to the different technology providers**, considering their needs, expectations and status of technology development. This section focuses on LCA of the components developed and used in the kits of the INFINITE project, according to the functional unit defined in chapter 2.1.3. The LCA for each kit is instead presented in chapter 2.4.

The objective of the LCA studies reported in the following sub-chapters are to:

- quantify the environmental impacts associated to the life cycle of INFINITE components;
- identify environmental hotspots in the life cycle of components and provide recommendations for their design and development.

2.3.1 Green Living Wall

2.3.1.1 Approach

The functional unit of the study is 1 m² of Green Living Wall (GLW). It is assumed that the GLW has characteristics similar to the Fytotextile system² proposed by the Spanish provider Terapia Urbana. The system is adapted to meet the needs of the project, for instance concerning the frame and irrigation system characteristics. The system consists of a galvanized steel frame, Fytotextile system of three layers (polyamide, geotextile and PVC) (Sala, 2021), plants and growing medium, and irrigation and control system. A schematic representation of the Fytotextile system as well as the INFINITE mock-up for GLW are shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Schematic design of GLW by Terapia Urbana² (left) and photo of INFINITE mock-up (right)

Primary data are obtained from Terapia Urbana (irrigation system, water and fertilizer during operation, end of life of Fytotextile material) and combined with secondary data from literature (production, maintenance, and end of life stages) and background data from ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off database (control system and operation of water pump). Data collection has been complemented with discussions with LEITAT, GSG and EURAC concerning maintenance and soil composition.

It is assumed that the service life of a retrofitted façade is 50 years; as the service life of a Fytotextile system is reported by Terapia Urbana to be 10 years, this study considers a reference time frame of

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10 years. Results are calculated for 1 m² of GLW operating for 10 years with the EF v.3 method and the GLW is assumed to be installed on a façade with a service life of 50 years.

The system boundaries of the study are reported in Figure 15 and include: **production, transport of the steel frame to RHB for integration in the façade and transport to the building for installation, transport of all the other components to the building site for installation, installation at the building site, use and maintenance, and End of life (EoL)**. Due to lack of data, assembly of the steel frame in the RHB façade is excluded from the boundaries, however, minimum energy use is expected for this step.

Figure 15: System boundaries of the LCA study of a GLW

2.3.1.2 Inventory analysis

An overview of the inventory for the investigated GLW is provided in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Inventory analysis for the investigated GLW

The life cycle model of the GLW is created in openLCA, see Figure 17.

Figure 17: Life cycle model of the investigated GLW in openLCA

The following **assumptions** were considered for the life cycle model:

- **Production:** the growing medium is assumed to have the following composition: 30% soil, 65% perlite, 5% compost; as the plants commonly used for GLWs were not available in the ecoinvent database, grass production was taken as a proxy (ecoinvent dataset: grass production, Swiss integrated production, intensive | grass, Swiss integrated production | Cutoff, U – CH).
- **Installation** at the building: the control system is generically modelled as electronics for control units (weight: 600g). Installation of the green system is performed by two technicians with a lifting platform for an average time of 0.43 h/m².
- **Operation:** 4.5 l/m² is considered for water use (calculated as average for summer and winter provided by Terapia Urbana); pump electricity use is obtained from the ecoinvent database (1.4 MJ/m²/year); wastewater from irrigation is assumed to be 44% of total water needed for irrigation (Van Herreweghe, 2019).
- **Maintenance:** a service life of 10 years is assumed for the following components: Fytotextile system, pump, control system; the irrigation system is assumed to be replaced 2 times in 50 years (service life of building demo cases in INFINITE); the gutter service life is 25 years; the steel frame is assumed to need no replacement in 50 years. Plants are assumed to last for 10 years. As for plant replacement in 10 years, 7% replacement rate is considered for the first year, 4.5% to 3% for the second to fourth year, and 2% from the fifth to the tenth year. It is also assumed that all the soil will be replaced once in 10 years, considering the risk of pest issues.
- **EoL:** Terapia Urbana reports that “Regarding the final disposal of the product at the end of its useful life, it has been considered that the main components of the system are not easily separable and, therefore, in an average European waste management system, these elements, despite being

mostly recyclable the Fytotextile system is assumed to be incinerated as a default scenario⁴. The option of Fytotextile recycling is investigated in the sensitivity analysis in chapter 2.3.1.5. Plants and soil are composted at the end of life, pipes for irrigation and the steel frame are recycled, while average treatment for Europe is assumed for the water pump and control system.

2.3.1.3 Result analysis and interpretation

Green Living Wall production, operation and maintenance are the most contributing life cycle stages to environmental impacts, see Figure 18 for selected impact categories. Installation, transport and end of life show much lower impacts.

Figure 18: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of life cycle stages to overall results for the GLW in INFINITE

The **production** of the **galvanized steel frame** and **Fytotextile system** are mostly responsible for overall GLW production impacts, followed by the gutter. The polyamide layer in the Fytotextile system often shows larger impacts than PVC and geotextile, depending on the impact category analyzed. Plants have significant impact on acidification due to fertilizer and pesticide used during harvesting, according to the data provided by the proxy process of grass harvesting in the ecoinvent database.

⁴ Fundación vida sostenible (2022) Life Cycle Assessment for the study of the environmental performance of the passive living wall system Fytotextile® manufactured by Terapia Urbana.

Figure 19: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of elements to GLW production stage

Operation impacts highlight **tap water for irrigation and drain water (treated as average wastewater from residence)** as the main environmental hotspots, see Figure 20. It is important to mention that average volumes for water irrigation and drain water have been used for the study; however, operation impacts are highly influenced by the location of the GLW and type of soil used, which affect the amount of water needed for irrigation and the capacity of soil to retain water. The “water use” impact category shows negative impacts due to the wastewater treatment process, as it is assumed that cleaned water after treatment is released back to the natural environment, thus contributing to replenish water resources.

Figure 20: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution analysis of GLW operation stage

As for the **maintenance** stage, provided that the galvanized steel frame does not have to be replaced, **substitution** (production, transport and installation) **of the Fytotextile system** emerges as a hotspot in different impact categories, see Figure 21. Replacement of other elements like irrigation system

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and gutter, water pump, and control system, shows significant contribution to specific impact categories, such as “resource use, mineral and metals”, due to the metals contained in the control unit and pump. Incineration of waste Fytotextile contributes to climate change impact, therefore, it appears important to seek for Fytotextile recycling. The “human toxicity, non-cancer” category displays a negative value regarding plant replacement because of heavy metal uptake (lead, nickel, cadmium and mercury) by plants while growing, which is considered in the input-output balance of heavy metals from fertilizers and pesticides.

Life cycle impact contributions for the climate change category are summarized in Figure 22, with main hotspots being the steel frame, the Fytotextile system and plants irrigation (including wastewater treatment).

Figure 21: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of elements to GLW maintenance stage

Climate change life cycle impacts of 1 m² of GLW – contribution analysis

Figure 22: Summary of contribution of GLW life cycle to climate change impacts

2.3.1.4 Comparison with benchmark

In the case of the GLW, a benchmark is not represented by a competing system, due to lack of data. However, a comparison can be made with literature results for the Fytotextile system by Terapia Urbana (see hotspots screening in Chapter 2.2.2). The comparison considers only the climate change category for 1 m² of GLW and 10 years of operation, and the following features:

- **Literature case study** (Sala, 2021): aluminium frame to support the Fytotextile system, water recycling system after irrigation, and Fytotextile recycled at the end of life. Location: UK.
- **INFINITE GLW**: galvanized steel frame to support the Fytotextile system, waste water treatment after irrigation, and Fytotextile incinerated at the end of life. Location: Europe.

The GLW in INFINITE shows lower climate change impacts than the one from the selected literature case study. This is mainly due to the **use of a steel frame instead of aluminium**; for instance, 1 kg of low-alloyed, hot rolled steel shows up to 90% less climate change impacts than 1 kg of primary aluminium ingot production (calculated with EF v.3 and ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off). On the other hand, the GLW operation and maintenance in INFINITE displays higher impacts because of a higher water volume considered for irrigation (INFINITE: 4.5 l/m²; literature case study: 2l/m²) and the lack of a system to recycle drain water. Finally, the literature case study performs better for the EoL than the INFINITE GLW as the Fytotextile system is assumed to be entirely recycled and not incinerated; this also affects the maintenance stage for the treatment of replaced Fytotextile.

Figure 23: Comparison of climate change impacts of 1 m² of GLW with Fytotextile system in the INFINITE project and from the selected literature case study

2.3.1.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the LCA study, it is possible to identify the top contributors to the whole life cycle and life cycle stage impacts. For specific hotspots identified only in some impact categories, please refer to the complete discussion of results in chapter 2.3.1.3.

- Top contributors to **life cycle impacts**:
 - Production
 - Operation
 - Maintenance.

- Top contributors to **production impacts**:
 1. Galvanized steel frame
 2. Fytotextile system (PA layer mainly).

- Top contributors to **operation**:
 1. Irrigation (water and wastewater treatment).

- Top contributors to **maintenance**:
 1. Fytotextile system replacement – every 10 years (including transport, installation and waste treatment)
 2. Irrigation system and gutter replacement (every 16 and 25 years respectively).

Based on these outcomes, the following recommendations apply:

- Explore the possibility of **recycling drain water after irrigation**; together with less tap water intake and wastewater sent to treatment, this option should consider additional energy use for a recirculation pump and any chemicals for water treatment on site.
- Investigate the **use of rain water instead of tap water** for plants irrigation; this option is under study in INFINITE by LEITAT through the development of a bio-electrochemical system. Trade-offs of energy and consumables for collecting rain water should be considered together with the benefits of saving tap water use.
- Consider the possibility to **recycle the Fytotextile system at the end of life** by separating the three polymer layers, instead of disposing it through incineration or landfilling.
- Explore **alternatives to steel frames**, such as a wood frame, to fix the Fytotextile system to the timber-based facade.
- **Extend the service life of the Fytotextile system** beyond 10 years, which would reduce maintenance and end of life impacts.

2.3.1.5.1 Frame material: galvanized steel vs wood frame

The frame for the GLW in INFINITE is made of galvanized steel. This is the main hotspot in the production stage of the GLW. Also, in the case of the literature case study by Terapia Urbana (Sala, 2021), the aluminium frame contributes by far to production impacts. Therefore, alternative materials may be considered for the frame, such as wood.

Two options for a GLW frame are compared for 1 m² of GLW in INFINITE:

- **Galvanized steel frame:** 0.0019 m³ for 1 m² of façade. Selected dataset from ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off: steel production, low-alloyed, hot rolled – RER, section bar rolling, steel – RER and zinc coating, pieces – RER.
- **Wood frame:** 0.0085 m³ for 1 m² of façade. Selected dataset from ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off: sawnwood production, softwood, dried (u=10%), planed – Europe without Switzerland.

Results show that for all impact categories from the EF v.3 method, the wood frame has a better environmental performance than the galvanized steel option, except for land use (due to land needed to harvest the trees from which sawn wood is obtained), see Figure 24.

Figure 24: Comparison of environmental impacts of different frame options for GLW for 1 m² of facade

2.3.1.5.2 End of life of Fytotextile system: incineration vs recycling

The LCA of the GLW in INFINITE has highlighted that incineration of the Fytotextile system is a hotspot for the waste treatment of GLW elements. According to Terapia Urbana, recycling would be theoretically possible but currently not feasible due to the difficulty of separating the PA, PVC and geotextile layers. As an ambitious scenario, it is possible to investigate climate change impacts if 100% of Fytotextile is recycled. It can be also considered that the **recycling of Fytotextile would avoid the production of virgin materials** like polyamide, polypropylene granulates and PVC. Therefore, net benefits of recycling Fytotextile can be estimated as the difference between the efforts for the recycling process and the avoided production of virgin plastic materials.

The comparison between different scenarios for the end of life of Fytotextile can be set as follows:

- **Baseline:** 1 m² of GLW, Fytotextile 100% to incineration;
- **Recycling scenario:** 1 m² of GLW, Fytotextile 100% to recycling + credits (i.e. net benefits = difference between the recycling process and avoided virgin materials). As for recycling process efforts, recycling of polyethylene is taken as proxy from ecoinvent database. As for avoided virgin materials, it is considered that recycled materials from Fytotextile will replace nylon 6-6, polypropylene granulate and polyvinylchloride, emulsion polymerised.

As shown in Figure 25, climate change impact can be reduced if the Fytotextile system is recycled instead of being incinerated (baseline); both **maintenance and end of life stages are affected by the recycling scenario**. Furthermore, credits obtained in the maintenance and end of life result in a negative climate change impact, which means that potential impacts of virgin plastics are higher than impacts linked to Fytotextile recycling effort.

Figure 25: Comparison of climate change impacts of different EoL options for Fytotextile system for 1 m² of GLW

2.3.2 Energy and fresh air distribution system

2.3.2.1 Approach

The Functional Unit of the study is 40 m² of net living area served with ventilation and energy distribution through decentralized Mechanical Ventilation Unit (MVU) and centralized heat pump for energy generation.

As for data collection, primary data are obtained from VORTICE and EURAC (manufacturing of components, packaging, maintenance, operation) and combined with background data from ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off database (end of life). Results are calculated for **40 m² of net living area for a reference service life of 15 years** with the **impact assessment methods** Environmental Footprint v.3 and Cumulative Energy Demand.

The system boundaries of the study are reported in Figure 26 and include: production of energy and ventilation components, transport to RHB for integration in the building envelope and transport to the building for installation, transport of remaining components to the building site for installation, operation and maintenance, and End of life (EoL). Due to lack of data, integration of MVU in the building envelope and installation of components on site are excluded from the boundaries, however, minimum energy use is expected for this step.

Figure 26: System boundaries of the LCA study of the ventilation and energy distribution system in INFINITE

2.3.2.2 Inventory analysis

The MVU considered for the INFINITE ventilation and distribution system covers 40 m² of living area. The inventory for the MVU includes electronics inside the machine, printed wiring board, fans, enthalpic air-to-air heat exchanger unit, sensible air-to-air heat exchanger unit, water-to-air heat exchanger unit, air damper, internal insulation in expanded polypropylene (EPP), a galvanized steel case and filters inside the machine. As the ecoinvent database does not include EPP, the dataset for this material is imported from the Evah OzLCI2019 database. Ventilation control and wiring for decentralized ventilation with similar characteristics is taken from the ecoinvent database. The distribution system includes polyethylene (PE) pipes, flexible aluminium/PET ducts, plenums, insulated spiral-seam ducts, connecting accessories in PE, air inlet and outlet grids, and filters. Packaging with cardboards and wood pallet is included according to the characteristics of the different components.

Based on the energy simulations for the Italian demo building, the electricity associated to the MVU operation is 10.4 kWh/m²*year. In the Italian demo case, considering a self-sufficiency of 48% (electricity covered with a PV system), 5.4 kWh/m²*year is the electricity taken from national grid. This amount of electricity from grid (Italian electricity mix, low voltage) is considered for the operation stage of the analysed system. PV infrastructure to cover the remaining electricity need for the MVU is excluded from this analysis, not to overshadow results for the ventilation and energy system, and is instead considered for the LCA at the whole building level in Task 6.4.

It is assumed that the **service life of the system is 15 years**. In 15 years, MVU components like the printing wiring board, the fans, the enthalpic air-to-air heat exchanger unit, sensible air-to-air heat exchanger unit, the air damper and the water-to-air heat exchanger unit are assumed to be replaced once. Filters inside the machine are substituted 23 times in 15 years. Filters in exhaust air outlet are replaced 30 times. Cleaning of the different heat exchangers in the MVU is included in the maintenance stage. The distribution system is expected to have a service life higher than 15 years, therefore in a building life cycle perspective, impacts of distribution pipes can be distributed over a higher time frame (see Task 6.4 Deliverable).

The end of life stage for the different ventilation components considers an average waste treatment scenario for Europe available in the ecoinvent v3.8 database.

2.3.2.3 Result analysis and interpretation

Production of ventilation components and operation (due to national grid electricity consumption) are the main hotspots in the life cycle of the INFINITE ventilation and energy distribution system, see selected categories in Figure 27. **Maintenance of ventilation components, especially regarding replacement of filters and MVU printed wiring board**, shows a significant contribution to some impact categories, such resource use, minerals and metals and freshwater ecotoxicity.

Figure 27: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of life cycle stages to overall results for the ventilation and energy distribution system in INFINITE

Impacts in the production stage are driven by the MVU to a large extent, followed by PE corrugated pipes and electronics for ventilation control and wiring, see Figure 28.

Figure 28: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of elements to production impacts for the ventilation and energy distribution system in INFINITE

If production impacts are specifically analyzed for the MVU, it is not straightforward to identify one element that stands out from the rest. However, the **galvanized steel case and the printed circuit board (PCB)** can be highlighted as recurring hotspots, see Figure 29. EPP insulation and electronics can contribute to certain categories, like water and resource use.

Figure 29: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of elements to production impacts for the MVU in the ventilation and energy distribution system in INFINITE

Based on the chosen waste treatment average European scenarios from the ecoinvent database, **end of life impacts** are mainly related to incineration of PE pipes and connecting accessories, incineration

of plastic components in the MVU and treatment of waste electronics, for instance affecting water use and freshwater ecotoxicity. See selected impact categories in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Environmental impacts for selected impact categories – contribution of elements to end of life impacts of the ventilation and energy distribution system in INFINITE

2.3.2.4 Comparison with benchmark

The INFINITE ventilation and energy distribution system can be compared against an **average ventilation system available in the LCA database ecoinvent**. The benchmark is obtained by adapting the dataset “ventilation of dwellings, decentralized, 6 x 120 m³/h, polyethylene ducts - Switzerland” to ensure a symmetric comparison with the INFINITE case. However, the average system from ecoinvent only fulfills the function of ventilation and not energy distribution; this limitation should be taken into account in the comparison of results. The average ventilation system for benchmark has the following characteristics:

- **Ventilation unit for decentral ventilation systems with 120 m³/h average air flow** and covering 40 m² of living area; housing case is made of galvanised steel, insulation materials in the MVU are stone wool and EPS.
- Weight of **ventilation unit**: 43.1 kg (INFINITE: 35 kg).
- Weight of **electronics for control units**: 0.23 kg (INFINITE: 0.36 kg).
- **Distribution is made with PE ducts** and adapted for 40 m² of dwelling area (from an original dwelling area of 6*130 m² in the database).
- **Maintenance**: service life of ducts is 50 years and of mechanical ventilation unit is 20 years. Service life of filters is 1 year. **As for INFINITE, the considered time frame is 15 years of operation.**
- **Electricity for operation**: 3.65 kWh/m²a (Italian demo: 5.4 kWh/m²a from electricity grid).
- Description of **operation from the ecoinvent dataset**: “electricity demand of ventilator (0.4 Wh/m³) representative for DC- or EC-motors and a system design with low pressure drops.

Electricity demand of control unit 10 W. Additional 0.3 kWh/(m² a) electricity demand for defrosting of heat exchanger. Decentral ventilation system without ground heat exchanger. Air intake on the facade and direct to the decentral ventilation units with a short galvanised steel tube (125 mm diameter). Distribution of fresh- and exhaust-air within the flat with polyethylene tubes (75 mm diameter). Exhaust air from the decentral ventilation units with a short galvanised steel tube (400 mm diameter) direct to the exhaust on the facade.”

Results are calculated for 40 m² of living area covered by ventilation for 15 years of operation. Depending on the impact category, the INFINITE system performs better in 4 impact categories and worse in the remaining 12 categories in the EF v.3 method.

The **higher electricity demand for INFINITE ventilation operation** affects the overall life cycle performance in comparison to average ventilation, see selected categories in Figure 31. The INFINITE ventilation kit performs better than the average for the **Human Toxicity category**, due to lower amounts of metals in the ventilation unit. However, the **higher weight of electronics** for the VORTICE machine affects human toxicity impacts and makes them in line with the average machine for the production phase (electronics affect resource use as well).

Figure 31: Comparison average vs INFINITE ventilation, whole life cycle, selected impact categories

If “climate change” impact category is analyzed, it can be clearly seen that higher electricity use in operation causes INFINITE ventilation to perform worse than average ventilation, see Figure 32. Maintenance of average ventilation shows generally lower impacts than the INFINITE case because of **higher life time of the MVU (20 years)**. As for end of life, treatment (incineration) of **more complex distribution system** for the INFINITE system causes higher impacts than the disposal of the average system.

Figure 32: Climate change comparison average vs INFINITE ventilation, whole life cycle

The INFINITE ventilation kit shows for some categories a better performance in the production phase than the average, see **climate change and water use** in Figure 33: this is due to lower impacts of steel, aluminum and insulation in comparison to the average (due to lower amounts in the INFINITE MVU). Higher **energy demand** (fossil) is associated to the production of INFINITE ventilation **components for distribution** rather than the average distribution (distribution in INFINITE is more complex and requires more materials).

Figure 33: Comparison average vs INFINITE ventilation, production and end of life stage, selected impact categories

As a last step, INFINITE ventilation and energy distribution system can be compared to a centralized ventilation system, adapted from the ecoinvent dataset “ventilation system production, central, 1 x 720 m³/h, polyethylene ducts - Switzerland”. A centralized ventilation may be more comparable than a decentralized system, if the aim is to compare industrialized and traditional retrofitting. A centralized ventilation system performs overall better than INFINITE and decentralized ventilation, because of more efficient use of materials (e.g. distribution) and less electricity use in operation, see Figure 34.

Figure 34: Comparison of environmental impacts INFINITE vs decentralized average ventilation vs centralized average ventilation

Finally, based on the benchmark comparison, it is possible to summarize the **main drivers to life cycle impacts of ventilation systems:**

- Amount of electricity needed in the use phase and share of renewable energy;
- Metals in MVU parts (aluminum and steel);
- Electronics weight in the ventilation machine;
- Complexity of distribution system (ducts and pipes);
- Service life of parts and replacement rate.

2.3.2.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the LCA study, it is possible to identify the top contributors to the whole life cycle and life cycle stage impacts. For specific hotspots identified only in some impact categories, please refer to the complete discussion of results in chapter 2.3.2.3.

- Top **contributors to life cycle impacts:**

- Production
- Operation.

- Top contributors to **production impacts:**

1. Mechanical ventilation unit -> galvanized steel case, PCB, electronics
2. PE corrugated pipes
3. Ventilation control and wiring.

- Top contributors to **operation impacts:**

1. Electricity from grid (excluding 48% from PVs).

Based on these outcomes, the following recommendations apply:

1. Explore the possibility of **using a MVU without metal case**, i.e. using only **a self-supporting insulation material**. Technical requirements, such as noise reduction and fire protection, need to be considered in the event of testing the option of MVU without case.
2. Select a MVU where the **case is made of steel with high recycled content**. Default recycled content from the ecoinvent dataset used in the LCA study is 23%.
3. Investigate whether it is possible to **increase the PV coverage for electricity production** to be used by the MVU.
4. Make assumptions about **technology improvements that can affect the MVU**, for instance increased service life beyond 15 years, more efficient performance or reduced size of some MVU components (or even for the whole MVU) in the future.

2.3.2.6 Comparison of insulation materials for MVU integration in façade and balcony

The MVU in the INFINITE project could be integrated in the facade under the window or in the balcony parapet. In both cases, **insulation** will need to be added as panel in front of the machine (integration under window) and all around the machine (integration in the balcony). As a standard solution, **stone wool** can be used as insulation material. However, alternative materials can be evaluated to achieve the same thermal performance.

As for the integration of the MVU under the window, it is possible to compare **stone wool (baseline) with expanded PUR (e.g. Stiferite), phenolic foam (e.g. Supercel Vitrum) and Aerogel**. The materials have the characteristics reported in Table 17 and are compared using the method EN15804+A1. The choice of the method is related to the approach followed by the EPDs identified for the selected materials.

Results only consider the production stage and show that **stone wool has the best environmental performance, followed by expanded PUR** (e.g. Stiferite), see Figure 35.

Table 17: Characteristics of insulation material analyzed for insulation panel of MVU under window

Stone wool	Thickness 3 cm Density $\rho = 40 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.035 W/mK	Data source: Ecoinvent database (stone wool)
Stiferite (expanded PUR) or Supercel Vitrum (phenolic foam)	Thickness 2 cm Density $\rho = 35\text{-}36 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.019-0.022 W/mK	Data source Stiferite: Ecoinvent database (polyurethane foam, rigid) Data source Supercel Vitrum: Company EPD, Kooltherm K5 Kingspan Insulation B.V., Declaration number EPD-KSI-20190072-IBC1-EN
Aerogel	Thickness 1 cm Density $\rho = 200 \text{ kg/m}^3$	Data source: Company EPD, SPACELOFT® AEROGEL INSULATION, Declaration number S-P-00725

	Thermal conductivity 0.015 W/mK	
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Figure 35: Comparison of environmental impacts of different insulation materials for MVU for under window integration

As for the case of MVU integration in balcony parapet, it is possible to **compare stone wool insulation with hemp, Aerogel, expanded PUR (e.g. Stiferite) and phenolic foam (e.g. Supercel Vitrum)**. The materials have the characteristics reported in Table 18 and are compared using the method EN15804+A1. Results are calculated only for the production stage and show **stone wool and hemp as best performing materials**, depending on the impact category, see Figure 36.

Table 18: Characteristics of insulation material analyzed for insulation all around MVU for integration in balcony parapet

Stone wool	Thickness 12 cm Density $\rho= 40 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.035 W/mK	Data source: Ecoinvent database (stone wool)
Hemp	Thickness 10 cm. Density $\rho=35 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.04 W/mK	Data source: Company EPD, EKOLUTION® HEMP FIBRE INSULATION, EPD registration number: S-P-01961
Aerogel	Thickness 5 cm Density $\rho= 200 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.015 W/mK	Data source: Company EPD, SPACELOFT® AEROGEL INSULATION, Declaration number S-P-00725

Stiferite (expanded PUR)	Thickness 7 cm Density $\rho = 36 \pm 1,5 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.022 W/mK	Data source: Ecoinvent database (polyurethane foam, rigid)
Supercel Vitrum (phenolic foam)	Thickness 7 cm Density $\rho = 35 \pm 1,5 \text{ kg/m}^3$ Thermal conductivity 0.019-0.021 W/mK	Data source: Company EPD, Kooltherm K5 Kingspan Insulation B.V., Declaration number EPD-KSI-20190072-IBC1-EN

Comparison all around insulation – option MVU integrated in balcony parapet

Figure 36: Comparison of environmental impacts of different insulation materials for integration in balcony parapet

Based on the results of the comparison, it is possible to conclude that stone wool is currently a good solution for the insulation of MVUs, both integrated in the façade and in balcony parapet.

2.3.3 Plasmochromic module

2.3.3.1 Approach

It is important to note that the **object of the study is the Plasmochromic (PLSMC) module** (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) and not the whole Insulated Glazing Unit (IGU) where the module is inserted.

The functional unit is defined as **1 m² of PLSMC module** with the characteristics reported in **Error! Reference source not found.** The life span of the module is **20 years**. Results are presented for **1 m² of PLSMC module for 20 years of operation**.

As for **data collection**, primary data are obtained from the technology provider (production, packaging, transport, use stages) and combined with secondary data from literature (maintenance and end of Life) and background data from ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off database. The impact assessment method used is EF v.3.

The system boundaries of the study are reported in Figure 37 and include: **production** (divided into 8 processes), **packaging, transport to RHB for integration in the façade, installation, transport to the building, operation and maintenance, and End of life (EoL).**

Figure 37: System boundaries of the PLSMC LCA study

2.3.3.2 Inventory analysis

Different inputs and outputs are modelled for each process in the different life cycle stages, including energy, chemicals, waste, transport and other products. An overview of the **inventory** for the PLSMC module is provided in Figure 38.

Figure 38: Inventory analysis for the PLSMC module

Some **assumptions** had to be made in absence of specific data in the ecoinvent database or when detailed information could not be provided by the technology provider.

Specifically:

- **Production:** in absence of specific data for chemicals, proxy data were assumed after discussion with the technology provider.
- **Transport to installation site:** an average distance between RHB in Bressanone (Italy) and the 3 demo cases in Italy, Slovenia and France is assumed.
- **Installation at the building** includes wiring, electricity for testing, sensors and control units. The last two items are modelled as “electronics, for control units” with an average weight of 387 g/m².
- **Maintenance:** no specific maintenance is required for the PLSMC module; no replacement of cables and electronics is assumed to occur in 20 years.
- **EoL:** according to Saint Gobain⁵, there are currently no known reuse, recycling or energy recovery programs for electrochromic IGUs. However, recycling of glass could be feasible if this is removed from sealants. Two scenarios are currently possible: landfill or incineration. Incineration is considered as a default option, with N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP) and PGE handled as hazardous waste, given the toxicity level. Electrical cables and electronics are assumed to be incinerated at the end of their service life.

⁵ Saint-Gobain Sage Glass. EPD Electchromic Insulated Glass Unit. Last accessed: 24.09.2021. Available at: https://www.sageglass.com/sites/default/files/saint_gobain_sageglass_environmental_product_declaration_double_glass_unit.pdf

The life cycle model created in openLCA software for the product under study is reported in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Life cycle model of the PLSMC module in openLCA

2.3.3.3 Result analysis and interpretation

2.3.3.3.1 Environmental impacts

If the impact contribution of the different life cycle stages is analyzed, it clearly emerges that the **production stage is a hotspot in the PLSMC module life cycle**, see Figure 40. **Electricity use during operation** has a contribution of up to 15% of total impacts, depending on the impact category (e.g. freshwater eutrophication, climate change and ionising radiation). So far, an average low-voltage European electricity mix has been considered, hence assuming that the module can be installed in any place in Europe. Impacts from operation can change depending on the specific electricity mix of the country or region where the smart window kit is installed. **Transport** appears to have larger impact on few categories (marine eutrophication, ozone depletion and particulate matter) to which tyre and brake emissions, diesel consumption and road construction are highly contributing. **End of life impacts** show low contribution to total results, except for human toxicity (cancer) and particulate matter, due to emissions generated from incineration of glass and electrical cables. The **installation stage** is a hotspot for specific categories, such as minerals and metal resource use, freshwater ecotoxicity and non-cancer human toxicity, because of the impacts linked to **window auxiliaries**, i.e. the installation of cables, control units, da and sensors. Finally, **packaging** (wooden crates and pallets) is the main contributor to land use, due to land occupation and transformation for tree harvesting.

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Figure 40: Life cycle stage contribution to environmental impacts of 1 m² of PLSMC module for 20 years of operation

If the detailed contribution of the 8 processes part of the production stage of the module is analyzed in Figure 41, it is clear that the **use of electricity for thermal treatment, lamination of the PLSMC module and IGU is the main driver to impacts. Processes concerning deposition of the inks on ITO** (Indium tin oxide) **glasses** show an individual impact contribution of up to 10%, mainly due to production of glass. Counter electrode (CE) synthesis and ink formulation impacts are related to electricity needed in the process, rather than to chemicals. The first process of PLSMC synthesis and ink formulation displays a contribution of 20% to minerals and metals resource use due to molybdenum trioxide use (proxy for Tungsten hexachloride).

Figure 41: Environmental impacts of 1 m² of PLSMC module for 20 years- production stage

Land use and human toxicity (cancer) are largely impacted by the packaging option chosen in the analysis. If **packaging with easels instead of crates and pallets** is investigated, life cycle impacts can be reduced for both impact categories, see Figure 42. This is because less wood is used in total for packaging, and sawn wood can be used for easel instead of plywood for crates, therefore avoiding the use of resins and glues. Furthermore, 20 PLSMC modules can be packed in easel, while only 5 modules can be packed in a crate and pallet.

Figure 42: Comparison of life cycle impacts of 1 m² of PLSMC module with different packaging options

2.3.3.4 Comparison with benchmark

The PLSMC IGU developed in INFINITE can be compared with some existing commercial alternatives, the Electrochromic (EC) IGU SageGlass by Saint Gobain and the View Dynamic Glass, see Table 19. For a fair comparison, a double glazing from ecoinvent database is added to the PLSMC module, as also the other alternatives considered a double glazing IGU. Based on the EPDs from the commercial alternatives, the environmental performance calculated with the CML-baseline could be compared to the PLSMC IGU for the production stage.

Table 19: Compared commercial alternatives to PLSMC IGU

Name	Total thickness (4 glasses), mm	Area	Source
EC IGU SageGlass Double Pane	16.47	1 m ²	https://www.sageglass.com/sites/default/files/saint_gobain_sageglass_environmental_product_declaration_double_glass_unit.pdf
INFINITE PLSMC IGU double glazing	15.0	1 m ²	LEITAT data for PLSMC + double glazing added from ecoinvent cut-off v.3.8 database
View Dynamic glass	12.5	1 m ²	https://view.com/sites/default/files/documents/View-Dynamic-Glass_EPD.pdf

Results of the comparison are reported in Figure 43. If results are not displayed in the figure for a commercial alternative for selected categories, it means that no value for that category was provided in the respective EPD. The **PLSMC IGU performs better than the commercial alternatives in all considered categories**. However, please note that this is a preliminary comparison and further efforts should be made to ensure the comparability among the different alternatives.

Figure 43: Comparison PLSMC IGU vs commercial alternatives. Results for 1 m² of IGU, production stage, CML-baseline method

2.3.3.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the LCA study, it is possible to identify the top contributors to the whole life cycle and life cycle stage impacts. For specific hotspots identified only in some impact categories, please refer to the complete discussion of results in chapter 2.3.3.3.

- Top **contributors to life cycle impacts:**

- Production
- Installation (for resource use, minerals and metals, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater ecotoxicity)
- Operation (lower contribution).

- Top contributors to **production impacts:**

1. Thermal treatment of PLSMC and Counter electrodes due to electricity use
2. Lamination of PLSMC module and IGU due to electricity use.

- Top contributors to **installation impacts:**

1. Control unit and electronics
2. Wiring.

- Top contributors to **operation impacts:**

1. Electricity from grid.

Based on these outcomes, the following recommendations apply:

1. **Explore pathways to reduce electricity use during production** (lamination and thermal treatment). One possibility could be to **move from glass to plastic substrate for the PLSMC module**, as lower temperature (and therefore less electricity) would be needed for thermal treatment and lamination. Another option could be to **switch to greener electricity mixes**, e.g. install PV panels or purchase green electricity for the manufacturing plant.
2. **Work on packaging optimization** by packing in easel instead of crate and pallet.
3. **Reduce electricity from grid for module operation** through a **self-powered module**, for instance through a solar technology like the one described in chapter 2.3.4.
4. **Investigate recycling** of PLSMC IGU at the EoL, also considering treatment of any hazardous waste due to chemicals in the PLSMC.
5. **Include considerations about improved process efficiency if the PLSMC is produced at a larger commercial scale**, with implications on energy and chemical usage and raw material supply.

2.3.3.6 Cost calculation for the production stage

Based on data provided by the technology developer for the production stage, material costs (excluding transport and labor) for the eight manufacturing processes were investigated. Please note that all costs were provided in Autumn 2021 and do not reflect the increase of electricity prices experienced in 2022. In the production stage, electricity is a minor driver to costs, thus differing from the case of environmental categories, see Figure 44.

Figure 44: Production cost distribution of 1 m² of PLSMC module

In the case of costs, **outsourcing of the ITO glasses (glass production and transport of the glass from Asia) is the main driver to costs, followed by cost of chemicals for ink and polymer gel electrolyte (PGE) formulation**, especially lithium perchlorate.

If ITO glass is supplied from Europe (for instance, assuming a distance of 500 km between supplier and manufacturing plant) rather than Asia in the future, this can contribute to reduce overall

production costs, see **Error! Reference source not found.** Please note that a change in glass price between Europe and Asia has not been considered. Only the change in transport price from Europe (by lorry) rather than Asia (by ship) has been evaluated.

Furthermore, **optimizing chemical usage** can have a positive impact on the economic dimension. Finally, additional cost improvements are expected when the PLSMC is deployed at a larger commercial scale.

2.3.4 Sensor and solar technology

2.3.4.1 LCA hotspots screening

A sensor and solar technology is developed in INFINITE as a **power bar** providing energy to sensors that are going to measure a number of parameters (e.g. light and cavity conditions). **Sensors** are powered by PV modules. The main components of a power bar to be integrated in IGU are:

- **Assembled printed circuit board (PCB);**
- **PV modules** (attached to PCB);
- Injection molded **thermoplastic** part (polycarbonate);
- Steel sheet antenna (attached to PCB);
- **Double-sided acrylic foam tape** for mounting the plastic housing to the IGU spacer.

Packaging of power bar consists of cardboard and plastics. Average distances are assumed for transport of raw materials and transport of power bar to IGU manufacturer.

An LCA hotspots screening has been performed for one power bar, considering the stages of raw material supply, transport during product manufacturing, manufacturing and transport to IGU manufacturer. Primary data are provided for the investigated stages and linked to background data fromecoinvent 3.8 cut-off database.

Figure 45 shows that the PCB is contributing the most to production impacts, followed by PV modules. To have a better understanding of benefits and impacts in the life cycle, it is recommended to evaluate **energy savings occurring in the operation phase and maintenance** of the power bar. In case of malfunctioning, placing the power bar outside of the IGU could make replacement or repairing easier.

Figure 45: Contribution analysis of INFINITE sensor and solar technology components to production stage impacts

An important topic for smart windows is **recycling potential of IGUs** and especially **recycling potential of glass**, as main component of an IGU. Challenges and potential of glass recycling are reported in the Annex 1 (section 6.1).

2.3.5 Building integrated photovoltaic panel

2.3.5.1 Approach

A colored glass-glass PV module is developed in the INFINITE project, see **Error! Reference source not found..** The PV module for façade integration has 48 cells (type M6, monocrystalline half-cut cells 166 x 83 mm). The PV module for roof integration has 32 cells (type G1, 158.75mm*158.75mm) and a nominal power of 130 Wp/m² (100-150 Wp/m²).

The functional unit of the study is defined as **1 PV Module, dimension 730 x 1100 mm (0.803 sqm)**. The life span of the module is **25 years**.

As for data collection, primary data are obtained from the technology provider (production, packaging, transport stages) and combined with secondary data from literature (maintenance, end of life stages) and background data from ecoinvent cut-off v.3.8 database (installation). The impact assessment method used is EF v.3. **Results are presented for 1 PV module for 25 years of operation.**

The system boundaries of the study are reported in Figure 46 and include **production (divided into three processes), packaging, transport of the aluminum substructure to Rubner for integration in the façade or roof, transport of the module to the building for installation, installation of the panel on site, use and maintenance, and end of life**. Please note that PV auxiliaries, such as inverter, batteries and cables are excluded from the scope of the study, as the technology provider does not have an influence on the production of these components. PV auxiliaries are instead considered for the LCA of the whole building level in task 6.4.

Figure 46: System boundaries of the PV study

2.3.5.2 Inventory analysis

Different inputs and outputs are modelled for each process in the different life cycle stages, including energy, consumables, waste, transport and other products. An overview of the **inventory** for the PV module is provided in Figure 47.

The PV panel is integrated in the timber-based façade through a hybrid connection. As for the roof installation, brackets are attached to the back of the panel with tape and then hooked onto other brackets screwed to the roof wood substructure.

Colored panels in INFINITE are produced through mineral coating, a coating process using very high temperature so that the coating is stabilized on the glass surface. The coloring process is modelled in INFINITE with data from literature (Gasonoo , 2021) concerning molybdenum oxide (MoO_3) and aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) layers. The required chemical amount per m^2 of colored glass is assumed to be 0.47 g of molybdenum oxide and 0.40 g of aluminum oxide. Finally, as no electricity consumption during the coloring process could be found in literature, it was assumed that mineral coating is comparable to spray pyrolysis technology, which requires 0.00344 MJ/m^2 of electricity (Gong, 2015). However, data for the coloring process included in INFINITE are likely to be incomplete and further efforts should be made to improve modelling of chemicals and, especially, electricity use.

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Figure 47: Inventory analysis for the PV module

The life cycle model created in openLCA software for the product under study is reported in Figure 48.

Figure 48: Life cycle model of the PV module in openLCA

Some assumptions were made in absence of specific data in the ecoinvent database or when detailed information could not be provided by the technology provider.

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Specifically:

- **Production:** in absence of data concerning weight of Junction box (Jbox), data from literature and ecoinvent database were assumed.
- **Packaging:** materials (pallet, PVC strips, kraft paper and cardboard boxes) are provided by SUNAGE, but amounts were assumed based on web search.
- **Installation at the building** only considers electricity for installation (assumed from ecoinvent processes “photovoltaic facade installation, 3kWp, single-Si, laminated, integrated, at building - CH” and “photovoltaic slanted-roof installation, 3kWp, single-Si, laminated, integrated, on roof - CH”).
- **Transport to installation site:** an average distance between RHB in Bressanone (Italy) and the three demo cases in Italy, Slovenia and France is assumed.
- **Use:** no direct consumables associated to PV panel.
- **Maintenance** includes PV cleaning with deionized water, based on web search and validated by the technology provider.
- **End of Life:** data are obtained from literature and cross-checked with NOBATEK/INEF4 (NBK) for Design for assembly and disassembly. A comparison of End-of-Life pathways selected by GREEND and NBK is provided in Table 20. Hypotheses from GREEND appear to be slightly more conservative, although similar to NBK. The main difference is related to **disposal of Silicon cells**, assumed to be incinerated by GREEND, while recycled according to NBK. The hypotheses from GreenDelta are considered for the model as representing the worst-case scenario. Transport distances to collection and dismantling sites as well as electricity from dismantling are obtained from literature (Markert, 2020)(Wambach, 2020)(Latusna, 2016).

Table 20: End of life pathways for PV module after research from GREEND and NBK

Components	Materials	End of life Pathway	% (GREEND)	% (NBK)
Glass of the laminate	Glass	Recycling	89%	100%
		Landfill	11%	0
Brackets, back profiles	Aluminum (Al)	Recycling	100%	100%
		Landfill	0	0
Encapsulant and plastic from connectors and JBOX	EVA & Polymers	Incineration	100%	100%
Connectors	Copper (Cu)	Recycling	100%	100%
		Landfill	0%	0%
Cells	Si chips/cells	Recycling	0%	100%
		Incineration	100%	0%
Ribbon	Non-ferrous Metal	Recycling	93%	100%
		incineration	7%	0%
Diodes		municipal solid waste mix	100%	-

2.3.5.3 Result analysis and interpretation

2.3.5.3.1 Environmental impacts of PV module for façade integration

If the contribution of the different life cycle stages to impacts is analyzed, it clearly emerges that the **production stage is the main hotspot in all impact categories**, see Figure 49. Packaging (cardboard and pallets) appears to have larger impact on land use due to wood supply for pallet and paper products. End of life impacts have a low contribution to total results and are mainly due to transport to PV collection point and dismantling site and incineration of plastic components (e.g. EVA, JBox and connector cases). Ozone depletion is affected by the production of plastic packaging of PV cleaning solution during maintenance.

Figure 49: Life cycle stage contribution to environmental impacts of 1 m² of PV module [25 years]

If the detailed contribution of the three production processes to the manufacturing phase of the module is analyzed, it is clear that the **laminare production is the main driver to impacts**, while finishing the panel with the production of brackets, horizontal profiles and Junction box does not show more than 30% contribution to impacts for the different categories, see Figure 50. Glass coloring does not show any significant contribution to impacts; however, as pointed out in the inventory section, further efforts are needed to make sure the impacts for this process are not underestimated.

Figure 50: Environmental impact contribution of 1 m² of PV module - production stage

Top contributors to module assembling and lamination are photovoltaic cells and solar glass production, while aluminum for brackets and horizontal profiles is the main impact driver for the end of module production process. The case of Climate Change is shown in Figure 51.

Figure 51: Climate change impacts contribution of 1 m² of PV module - module assembling and lamination process (left) and end of module production process (right)

Finally, if the Climate Change category is analyzed for the end of life stage, it is clear that **incineration processes (plastics and cells)**, together with **transport and electricity for disassembly are the main drivers to impacts**, see Figure 52. Application of DfA/D principles can reduce EoL impacts, although this may not have significant consequences on the overall life cycle, which is dominated by the production stage.

Figure 52: Climate change impacts of 1 m² of PV module - End of Life

2.3.5.4 Comparison with benchmark

The modelled PV module for INFINITE can be compared with an average PV module from ecoinvent v.3.8 cut-off database (dataset: “photovoltaic laminate production, single-Si wafer | photovoltaic laminate, single-Si wafer | Cutoff, U – RER” and “photovoltaic module production, building-integrated, for facade installation | photovoltaic module, building-integrated, for facade installation | Cutoff, U – RER”). In order to compare 0.803 m² of colored panel by SUNAGE of a generic traditional glass-foil monocrystalline panel with a comparable performance of 140 Wp needs to be considered. The traditional glass-foil panel is adapted from a 60 cells panel in the database, with a performance of 224 Wp. The dimension of the traditional panel is therefore scaled proportionally to obtain the area needed to achieve the same performance (nominal power) as a colored INFINITE panel.

Based on the current data collection, **the production of a colored INFINITE panel (1 m², 140 Wp) shows a better environmental performance than an average monocrystalline panel (1.34 m², 140 Wp)** in all impact categories, see Figure 53. This is due to the **lower number of cells** needed to achieve the defined performance of 140 m² for the INFINITE panel (INFINITE panel: 28 cells/1 m²; average panel: 38 cells/1.34 m²), considering that silicon cells are highly contributing to impacts. The use of the additional back glass for the INFINITE panel does not appear a crucial factor for a worse environmental performance in comparison to a traditional panel, although this reduces the impact difference between the two panels for the resource use aspect. As for the interpretation of results, it should be noted that the performance (nominal power) of the average of PV panel is rather low, and not necessarily representing all market alternatives.

Figure 53: Comparison of production of a colored INFINITE PV laminate (1 m², 140 Wp) vs a generic traditional monocrystalline PV laminate (1.34 m², 140 Wp)

2.3.5.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the LCA study, it is possible to identify the top contributors to the whole life cycle and life cycle stage impacts. For specific hotspots identified only in some impact categories, please refer to the complete discussion of results in chapter 2.3.5.3.

- Top **contributors to life cycle impacts:**

- Production

- Top contributors to **production impacts:**

1. Module assembling and lamination due to PV cells and solar glass;
2. End of module production due to aluminum production (brackets and profiles).

Based on these considerations, the following recommendations apply:

1. **Investigate alternatives to the current anchoring system and connection with timber-based structure**, for instance by reducing aluminum use for finishing the laminate (for brackets and horizontal profiles).
2. **Investigate alternatives to back glass for the PV module, such as a foil made of a polymer material.** It is important to notice that replacing the back glass with another material will also require a new design of the anchoring system.

Unfortunately, optimizing the two main drivers to impacts (silicon cells and glass production) is not an alternative in the project.

2.3.5.5.1 Comparison of anchoring systems for PV module integrated in façade

The LCA results for the INFINITE PV panel integrated in the roof are lower than the case of the PV panel integrated in the façade. As there are no major material differences between the panels except for the anchoring system (brackets for the roof panel vs brackets + aluminum profiles for the façade panel), it is clear that impacts can be reduced if a lower amount of aluminum is used for fixing the panels to the back structure.

Results are calculated and compared for the production stage of 1 m² of PV panel with 140 Wp/m² with chemical and hybrid connection, using the EF v.3 method. **A hybrid connection appears to reduce environmental impacts in comparison to a chemical connection which requires more aluminum**, see Figure 54. The categories affected the most by aluminum production are human toxicity (cancer), particulate matter and freshwater ecotoxicity.

Figure 54: Comparison of environmental impacts to produce PV modules with different anchoring system for facade integration (chemical vs hybrid connection)

2.3.5.6 Cost calculation for the production stage

Based on data provided by the technology developer for the production stage (excluding the coloring process), material costs (excluding transport and labor) for this stage could be calculated. Figure 55 reports costs for 1 m² of PV module. Please note that all costs were provided in Autumn 2021 and do not reflect the increase of electricity prices experienced in 2022. As already emerged for the environmental impacts, **laminare production is the most contributing stage to costs**. Specifically, **solar glass and silicon cells are the main drivers to production costs**, see Figure 56. **Around 10% of costs are due to the junction box and 20% to the anchoring system.**

Figure 55: Cost distribution of the production of 1 m² of PV module (per process)

Figure 56: Cost distribution of the production of 1 m² of PV module (per material)

Production costs can be also compared between the PV for façade and roof integration with chemical connection and with PV for façade integration with hybrid connection.

2.3.6 Building integrated solar thermal panel

2.3.6.1 Approach

A full LCA study for the so-called “Batisol” solar thermal panel (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) was performed by NBK before the start of the INFINITE project. This study is the starting point for the LCA of the Building Integrated Solar Thermal Panel (BIST) in INFINITE.

NBK has assessed the environmental impacts of **1 m² of Batisol panel, considering a life span of 50 years and the whole life cycle from cradle to grave** (production, packaging, transport, installation, operation and maintenance and end of life). The study only focuses on the panel; anchoring to the façade and auxiliaries (water tank, expansion vessel, pump and pipes) are excluded from the analysis. Results for the Batisol can be summarized as follows:

- **Manufacturing and installation of the panel** are the most contributing life cycle stages to impacts;
- **Raw material production** is the main driver to Climate Change impacts in the manufacturing and installation stages;
- **Aluminum layers are the most contributing materials to Climate Change impacts in the manufacturing stage.**
- **The Batisol panel shows higher Climate Change impacts than other generic aluminum panels, due to the thickness of the aluminum sheets, which is higher than other generic aluminum panels.**

The following improvement possibilities are suggested by NBK and are all related to the aluminum parts of the panel:

- Use **aluminum produced in France**;
- Use of **recycled aluminum**;
- Reuse of Aluminum dismantled from other buildings for the inner layer of the panel;
- **Use steel instead of aluminum**;
- Improve the panel and anchoring design to decrease the mass of aluminum;
- Avoid the treatment of the external aluminum layer.

The solar thermal panel designed for INFINITE does not show significant differences from Batisol in terms of materials and quantities. Therefore, data from the previous LCA study are transferred to the INFINITE case. The main differences between Batisol and INFINITE solar thermal panel concern the inclusion of the anchoring system designed in INFINITE and the replacement of the Plug & Play hydraulic system of Batisol with a copper manifold system, see Figure 57.

Figure 57: Hydraulic system with copper manifolds for the solar thermal panel developed in INFINITE

The functional unit of the BIST LCA study in INFINITE is **1 m² of solar thermal panel for façade integration. The service life of the panel is 10 years.** As for data collection, primary data are obtained

from the technology provider for all life cycle stages (except for installation) and linked to background data from ecoinvent cut-off v.3.8 database. Results are calculated with the EF v.3 method. The system boundaries of the study are reported in Figure 58 and include **production, packaging, transport to Rubner for integration in the façade, installation, transport of the module to the building for installation, use and maintenance, and end of life**. Please note that auxiliaries, such as water tank, expansion vessel, pump and pipes are excluded from the scope of the study, as the technology provider does not have an influence on the production of these components. These auxiliaries are instead considered for the LCA of the whole building level in task 6.4.

Figure 58: System boundaries of the BIST study

2.3.6.2 Inventory

The main panel components are aluminum plate (powder coated), XPS insulation, glue and aluminum foil. Installation of the panel on the façade considers the use of a lifting platform and related diesel consumption. At the end of life, 95% of the metals are assumed to be recycled, while 5% are assumed to be landfilled. 100% of the glue and XPS are assumed to go to landfill. No consumables are considered for the use and maintenance in 10 years of service life of the panel.

The life cycle model created in openLCA software for the product under study is reported in Figure 59.

Figure 59: Life cycle model of the ST module in openLCA

2.3.6.3 Result analysis and interpretation

If the contribution of the different life cycle stages to impacts is analyzed, it clearly emerges that the **production stage is the main driver**, see Figure 60. As for land use, wood for pallet (packaging) and road construction (transport) are the most contributing processes to impacts.

Figure 60: Life cycle stage contribution to environmental impacts of 1 m² of solar thermal (ST) module

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In the production stage, **the main drivers to impacts are the aluminum cladding and aluminum film of the panel, and the hydraulic system** (due to copper manifold and chromium steel for flexible piping), see Figure 61. The **XPS insulation** shows a large contribution to ozone depletion, while electricity use shows a significant contribution only to ionizing radiation because of nuclear power in the French electricity mix.

Figure 61: Contribution to environmental impacts of production of 1 m² of solar thermal (ST) module

Land use displays a negative contribution (i.e. positive effect) from the hydraulic system production: this is linked to positive impacts assumed for the occupation and transformation of land for storing tailings from copper mining (i.e. prevention of land contamination through mine waste) (Huijbregts , 2017). Copper mining is a process in the upstream chain of the production of copper for the manifold and brass connectors, see Figure 62.

Category	Sub-category	Impact Type	Value	Unit	Point Value
Land use	treatment of non-sulfidic tailing, off-site non-sulfidic tailing, off-site Cutoff, U - GLO	382:Waste treatment and disposal / 3822:Treatment and dis...			26.30107 Pt
	Occupation, dump site	Resource / land	-105.24000	Pt/m ² a	-130.52724 Pt
	Transformation, to dump site	Resource / land	-4472.60000	Pt/m ²	-84.64405 Pt
	Transformation, from unspecified	Resource / land	-2943.60000	Pt/m ²	-27.67147 Pt
	hard coal mine operation and hard coal preparation hard coal Cutoff, U - CN	051:Mining of hard coal / 0510:Mining of hard coal			-18.21172 Pt
	Occupation, dump site	Resource / land	-105.24000	Pt/m ² a	-54.79111 Pt
	Transformation, to dump site	Resource / land	-4472.60000	Pt/m ²	-36.50390 Pt
	Transformation, from unspecified	Resource / land	-2943.60000	Pt/m ²	-12.92817 Pt
	Transformation, to mineral extraction site	Resource / land	4708.40000	Pt/m ²	-9.13252 Pt
	Occupation, mineral extraction site	Resource / land	110.79000	Pt/m ² a	0.99805 Pt
	recultivation, bauxite mine recultivation, bauxite mine Cutoff, U - GLO	390:Remediation activities and other waste management se...			2.77543 Pt
	treatment of non-sulfidic overburden, off-site non-sulfidic overburden, off-site Cutoff, U - C	382:Waste treatment and disposal / 3822:Treatment and dis...			-16.07180 Pt
	electricity production, hydro, reservoir, non-alpine region electricity, high voltage Cutoff, U	351:Electric power generation, transmission and distribution...			-13.36091 Pt
	treatment of sulfidic tailings, from copper mine operation, tailings impoundment sulfidic tai	382:Waste treatment and disposal / 3822:Treatment and dis...			-12.01358 Pt
					-6.94943 Pt

Figure 62: Land use impact analysis for the production of 1 m² of solar thermal (ST) module

2.3.6.4 Comparison with benchmark

The BIST system developed in INFINITE can be compared with an average solar thermal collector system available in ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off database. Therefore, to consider an average panel, the dataset “market for flat plate solar collector, Cu absorber | flat plate solar collector, Cu absorber | Cutoff, U – GLO” is selected and complemented with a process representing the manufacturing of the hydraulic system (copper pipes), which is adapted from “solar collector system installation, Cu flat plate collector, multiple dwelling, hot water | solar collector system, Cu flat plate collector, multiple dwelling, hot water | Cutoff, U - CH”. Based on the datasets, for 1 m² of panel, 1.6 kg of

copper is needed for the pipes of the system. Results are only referred to the production stage and are calculated for 1 m² of panel.

The BIST system developed in INFINITE shows a better performance than the average case in almost all impact categories for the functional unit of 1m², see Figure 63. The INFINITE BIST performs worse than the average for ionizing radiation (due to nuclear power in the French electricity mix), **ozone depletion** (due to **XPS insulation**, while stone wool is used for the average solar thermal panel) and particulate matter (because of high amount of aluminium used for the INFINITE panel). Land use is not displayed in the figure because of visualization reasons. Indeed, land use impacts for the average BIST are negative (i.e. positive impact): a high copper amount is used for the average collector, this results in positive land use occupation and transformation effects, as waste from copper mining is prevented from polluting the land.

Figure 63: Comparison of environmental impacts between INFINITE BIST and average BIST from ecoinvent database

2.3.6.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the LCA study, it is possible to identify the top contributors to the whole life cycle and life cycle stage impacts. For specific hotspots identified only in some impact categories, please refer to the complete discussion of results in chapter 2.3.6.3.

- Top **contributors to life cycle impacts:**

- Production

- Top contributors to **production impacts:**

1. Aluminum cladding
2. Aluminum film
3. Hydraulic system, consisting of copper manifold, brass connectors, flexible piping,

Given the “short” service life of the panel (10 years guaranteed by the producer), replacement of the panel in the building lifetime (e.g. 50 years) is expected to have a contribution to **maintenance** impacts. This aspect is further investigated at the building level in Task 6.4.

Based on these considerations, the following recommendations apply:

1. Investigate the possibility to **replace copper manifold with plug&play connection**, for the hydraulic system.
2. **Use aluminum with high recycled content** for the cladding and foil of the panel; or apply the other recommendations previously identified by NBK for Batisol (see chapter 2.3.6.1).
3. **Investigate alternative insulation to XPS material**, which highly affects ozone depletion, and resource use and water use to a lower extent.
4. **Consider extending the service life of the panel**, which will improve the environmental performance in the maintenance stage of the building where the panel is installed.

2.3.6.6 Cost calculation for the production stage

Based on data provided by the technology developer for the production stage of the panel, material costs (excluding transport and labor) for this stage could be calculated. Please note that all costs were provided in Autumn 2021 and do not reflect the increase of electricity prices experienced in 2022. As already emerged for the environmental impacts, **the hydraulic system (copper manifold, flexible piping and brass connector) and aluminum parts are the most contributing components to costs**. Furthermore, it is important to highlight that the **glue is also a main driver to costs**, while environmental impacts for this element did not appear to be significant.

2.4 LCA and LCC results for INFINITE kits

In this section the LCA and LCC results for INFINITE kits are summarized. The section does not include absolute costs for confidentiality reasons. These values have however been calculated for the analyses.

2.4.1 LCA of the base KIT 0 Timber-based envelope

2.4.1.1 Timber-based façade

2.4.1.1.1 Approach

The goal of the study is to quantify and identify **environmental hotspots** in the life cycle of a timber prefabricated façade (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) and provide recommendations for the design and development in INFINITE. Furthermore, **different cladding and end of life options** are compared in the study. The functional unit of the study is **1 m² of standard RHB façade** (without windows). Please note that the analyzed façade has a timber frame with a width of 160 mm; this dimension may change when the façade is applied to different buildings (for instance, the width of the frame is increased to 200 mm for the Italian demo). Primary data are obtained for all life cycle stages from the technology providers and complemented with background data from ecoinvent 3.8 cut-off.

It is assumed that the **service life of the façade is 50 years**. Results are calculated with the EF v. 3 method and are presented for 1 m² of façade per year (i.e. impacts are simply divided by 50).

The boundaries of the study include manufacturing (production of material layers and connectors, transport of materials to the façade developer, assembly of the façade), packaging, transport to the installation site, installation at building, use and maintenance, and end of life, see Figure 64.

Figure 64: System boundaries of the LCA of the timber façade

2.4.1.1.2 Inventory

The inventory analysis of the RHB façade is reported in Figure 65. A detailed list of the materials and their characteristics considered in the inventory is reported in Table 10. Quantities in the table are referred to 15 m² and are, therefore, scaled to 1 m² of functional unit.

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Figure 65: Inventory analysis for the timber-based façade

The façade is modelled considering three different cladding scenarios: without cladding, with HPL panels and with wood cladding.

The following assumptions were made for the study:

- **Assembly:** tape was modelled based on technical sheets of similar products; water proofing membrane was modelled with PES fleece; HPL panels were modelled based on the material shares reported in the EPD. Wood cladding is instead model with the ecoinvent dataset “wood cladding production, softwood – RoW”. Heating and electricity for lighting are excluded as not specific to the product under study.
- **Installation** at the building: equipment (crane) is currently excluded, but its energy consumption is included in the model.
- **Use:** this phase has no environmental impacts.
- **Maintenance:** it is assumed that all façade components (excluding cladding) last until the end of the façade service life (50 years). If cladding is considered in the model, HPL panels have a service life of 50 years. As for wood cladding, two scenarios are considered: scenario 1: cladding painted 7 times and not replaced in 50 years; scenario 2: cladding painted 4 times and replaced 1 time.

Furthermore, four different end of life scenarios are considered:

- Base scenario 0, considering end of life average processes from the ecoinvent database;
- Scenario 1 incineration focused, where incineration is the prioritized scenario, based on assumptions from the technology provider;

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- Scenario 2 recycling focused, where recycling is the prioritized scenario, based on assumptions from the technology provider;
- Scenario 3 best case recycling, where recycling is prioritized.

The end of life scenarios are summarized in Table 21. Please note that reuse is currently not considered and will be added as a scenario after the mock-up tests in March 2023 and the advancements of design for assembly and disassembly work. A combination of different scenarios can be also added. Effort for disassembly is currently excluded.

As for those elements that can be recycled or incinerated at the end of life, benefits (i.e. credits) could be considered to take into account that incinerated materials will avoid the production of heat and electricity from other sources and recycled materials will prevent the extraction and production of virgin materials. For the calculation of energy credits from incineration, the net energy production reported inecoinvent for the respective incineration processes is considered. As a correction factor, it is assumed that recycled materials will replace 80% of virgin materials; a list of replacing materials per element that can be recycled is available in Table 22.

Table 21: End of life scenarios for the timber-based facade in INFINITE

EoL scenarios	based on what is provided in ecoinvent as average EoL scenario			based on data collection (incineration chosen when both recycling and incineration were given as options by tech provider)			based on data collection (recycling chosen when both recycling and incineration were given as options by tech provider)			based on recycling possibilities of the material (from tech provider data and/or EPD)		
	Base scenario 0 (ecoinvent database)			Scenario 1 (incineration-based)			Scenario 2 (recycling-based)			Scenario 3 (best case: recycling)		
	Recycling	Landfill	Incineration	Recycling	Landfill	Incineration	Recycling	Landfill	Incineration	Recycling	Landfill	Incineration
Stone wool	40%	60%			100%			100%		100%		
OSB-4 (inner planking) - Egger			100%			100%	100%			100%		
Vapour-permeable wood fiber boards (outer planking) - Egger DHF			100%			100%			100%			100%
Wood-based structure – RHB		56%	44%			100%	100%			100%		
Wood vertical mullion (60 x 60mm) – RHB		56%	44%			100%	100%			100%		
Membrane (Water proofing/windproofing) - Dörken Delta Foxx Plus	100%			100%			100%			100%		
External cladding (HPL panels) - Exterior			100%			100%			100%			100%
Tape (incl that added for installation)		56%	44%		56%	44%		56%	44%		56%	44%
Steel screws		99%	1%			100%	100%			100%		
Plastic screws		56%	44%		100%			100%		100%		
Wood cladding		wood 56%	wood 44%; paint 46% (16% hazardous, 30% non-hazardous)		100%		100%			100%		

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Table 22: Recyclability of timber facade and overview of credits achievable if recycled material replaces a virgin material

	Comment/ credit for...	Source
Stone wool	Rockwool is recyclable	EPD
Replacing:	virgin rockwool insulation	virgin rockwool can be given back to the factory https://www.rockwool.com/de/downloads-und-services/steinwolle-entsorgen/
OSB-4 (inner planking) - Egger	Processing rate after removal from the building is 100%.	EPD
Replacing:	wood chips	To be checked if panel can be reused after 50 years
Vapour-permeable wood fiber boards (outer planking) - Egger DHF	DHF boards fastened with screw connections can be easily collected separately when a building is converted or ends its use phase in the case of selective dismantling and reused for the same application or for applications other than the original one.	EPD
Replacing:	If cannot be reused, only incineration is possible	To be checked if panel can be reused after 50 years
Wood-based structure - RHB	In the event of selective de-construction, Rubner structural finger jointed solid timber can easily be reused after the end of the structures service life.	EPD
Replacing:	structural use as mullions	The mullions can be used again for other projects
Wood vertical mullion (60 x 60mm) - RHB	same as above	EPD
Replacing:	structural use as mullions	The mullions can be used again for other projects
Membrane (Water proofing/windproofing) - Dörken Delta Foxx Plus	recycled	assumption
Replacing:	polyester material	
External cladding (HPL panels)	The material cannot generally be re-used.	EPD
Replacing:	-	
Tape	reusing is not possible	
Replacing:	-	
Steel screws	recycled as steel	assumption
Replacing:	virgin steel	
Plastic screws	recycled as plastic	assumption
Replacing:	virgin plastics	

Alternative wood cladding	4 possible EOL scenarios, incl. Recycling, reuse, landfill, incineration	EPD
Replacing:	wood chips	

2.4.1.1.3 Result analysis and interpretation

Results are first analyzed for a timber façade without cladding, given the many options that could be available for the last cladding layer. In a second step, results are analyzed with different cladding options.

LCA RESULTS FOR THE TIMBER FAÇADE WITHOUT CLADDING

The **production of the timber façade** (including manufacturing of the façade components, excluding cladding) is the most contributing life cycle stage to impacts, see Figure 66. Depending on the impact category, **transport of the façade to the installation site and end of life** contribute together up to 20%.

Figure 66: Life cycle stage contribution to environmental impacts of the timber facade in INFINITE (excluding cladding)

In the production stage, the main hotspots are **stone wool insulation, MDF and OSB panels**, see Figure 67, excluding cladding that is not considered in this first analysis. **Timber frame and mullions** also show an average impact of 10% or higher, depending on the impact category. It is also important to consider that **ozone depletion** is highly affected by the polyester material used for the **waterproof membrane**.

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Figure 67: Production stage contribution analysis for the timber facade in INFINITE (excluding cladding)

Environmental impacts of the timber façade can be compared considering four different end of life scenarios. The two scenarios where **recycling of façade components at the end of life is prioritized** show lower impacts than the base (average ecoinvent waste treatment) and incineration-based scenarios, see Figure 68. However, the difference between the best and worst performing scenarios is not higher than 10% in any impact categories.

Figure 68: Comparison of environmental impacts of a timber facade with different end of life options, without credits

The end of life scenarios make a difference when benefits (credits) of recycling and incineration are considered. Credits include production of energy by incinerating waste which avoids heat and electricity from other sources and the provision of recyclable materials which avoid the production of virgin ones. If benefits of recycling are included, the fourth scenario “best case recycling” shows

lower impacts than the other scenarios. The third scenario “recycling (RHB)” does not show the same benefits as the fourth one because stone wool is assumed to be landfilled and not recycled. There are some impact categories, such as ozone depletion, ionizing radiation, and climate change, where the second incineration scenario performs better than the recycling (RHB-based) scenario; this shows that benefits achievable by replacing energy with heat and electricity resulting from waste treatment are higher than avoided impacts of virgin materials.

Communication and estimate of benefits are sensitive topics in LCA and it should be clear that credits do not cancel negative impacts linked to a product life cycle. Indeed, inclusion of credits in LCA results risks overshadowing the actual impacts of the system under study. For instance, Figure 70 reports a comparison of contribution to end of life impacts with and without the consideration of credits. If credits are included, end of life impacts are negative due to saved virgin materials; however, actual end of life impacts are mainly due to incineration of MDF-DHF and OSB panels, which is clearly visible if the system is analyzed without considering any credits.

Furthermore, for a comprehensive understanding of benefits of recycling, **efforts due to waste pre-processing and preparation of recyclable materials to be usable in secondary life cycles should be subtracted from these benefits.** These efforts are currently excluded from the model, due to a lack of data. Finally, it is crucial to define the replacement rate between secondary and virgin materials for recycling and reuse (1 kg of recycled stone wool replaces 1 kg of virgin stone wool?; 1 dismantled MDF panel (e.g. 15 m²) replaces 15 m² of virgin MDF panel?). Effort for disassembly in the different end of life scenarios should be considered as well. a comparison of environmental impacts of a timber facade with different end of life options can be seen in Figure 69.

Figure 69: Comparison of environmental impacts of a timber facade with different end of life options, with credits

Figure 70: Comparison of climate change impacts of end of life of a timber facade with and without credits

LCA RESULTS FOR THE TIMBER FAÇADE WITH CLADDING

As expected, the option without cladding shows the lowest environmental impacts, due to less materials considered in the product system, see Figure 71. When cladding is included, **the option with HPL panels shows higher impacts than wood cladding** in most of the environmental categories. Wood cladding shows the highest impacts only for land use, due to land occupation for wood harvesting, and photochemical ozone formation, because of the emissions related to the production and application of paint in the maintenance stage of the cladding. Overall, **not replacing the wood cladding and painting it for seven times shows lower impacts than the scenario where wood cladding is replaced and painted less often.**

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Figure 71: Comparison of LCA results for 1 m² of timber façade with and without cladding options

If the climate change category is analyzed in detail, the **production stage** is confirmed as the most contributing life cycle stage also for the options with HPL and wood cladding, see Figure 72. **Production impacts are notably higher for HPL cladding than for wood cladding**; however, **HPL cladding does not require maintenance**, while this stage accounts for approximately 10% of impacts for the wood cladding option (case where wood cladding is replaced once in 50 years and painted four times).

Figure 72: Life cycle stage contribution to climate change impacts with and without cladding options

If climate change impacts are analyzed specifically for the production stage of the façade with the two cladding options, it is interesting to note that **HPL cladding is the main driver to the façade**

manufacturing impacts, see Figure 73. In the event of wood cladding, the main hotspots are stone wool insulation and MDF panels, like in the option without cladding.

Figure 73: Production stage contribution to climate change impacts with and without cladding options

The analysis of the maintenance stage of the timber façade confirms that no impacts are expected for the options without cladding and with HPL panels. As for wood cladding, painting the wood seven times in the service life of the façade appears to be more sustainable than replacing the cladding (and painting it four times in 50 years). However, it should be noted that **Non-methane volatile organic compounds (NMVOC) emissions occurring during paint application heavily affect photochemical ozone formation**, see Figure 74.

Figure 74: Comparison of maintenance stage impacts with and without cladding options

2.4.1.1.4 Comparison with benchmark

The timber façade developed in INFINITE can be compared against a traditional façade for renovation. The comparison is based on the INFINITE solution developed for the Italian demonstration building and on making sure that both façade options achieve the same thermal performance of 0.16 W/m²K.

The traditional façade for renovation is characterized by a base layer and masonry support, EPS insulation (220 mm, density 35kg/m³) with a PE fixing system, a bituminous layer, an aluminum substructure for a ventilated system with cladding of HPL panels. For a fair comparison, the INFINITE industrialized façade is modified by increasing the timber frame width (from 160 mm to 200 mm) and the insulation within the frame (from 160 mm to 200 mm); HPL panels are also considered for the INFINITE cladding.

Transport of components to installation site is considered for the traditional façade; components are then assembled directly on site. This implies that no intermediate transport is needed to bring components to off-site assembly. On the other hand, on-site assembly requires façade preparation and cleaning with pressurized water, scaffolding as well as a longer occupation of the construction site (use of electrical equipment and fences). Finally, it is assumed that around 10% of materials transported to the site end up being construction waste.

Results for 1 m² of façade renovated in a traditional and industrialized way are compared in **Error! Reference source not found..**

INFINITE timber façade performs better than the traditional façade for climate change, water use and fossil resource use, see Figure 75. For all the other impact categories, the INFINITE façade solution shows a worse performance than the traditional case.

Land use is heavily affected by the large use of wood in the industrialized solution. As for the other categories where the industrialized renovation option performs worse than the traditional case, this is due to the **higher complexity of the industrialized façade** in terms of number and quantity of components which affects the production and end of life stages. Furthermore, additional transport required to bring components to off-site assembly increases impacts for the industrialized option. Larger efforts at construction site for the traditional façade installation appear not to balance impacts related to the production and end of life of a much more complex façade.

Figure 75: Comparison results of 1 m² of traditional vs INFINITE timber façade

One of the main drivers to the difference of impacts between the traditional and industrialized façade is the **choice of the insulation material**. The stone wool material chosen in INFINITE has a higher density than the EPS material used for the traditional façade. 8 kg of EPS (35 kg/m³) in the traditional scenario are needed to achieve the same thermal performance of 12.6 kg of stone wool (60 kg/m³) in the industrialized case. Based on these quantities, **stone wool shows a worse performance than EPS in most of the impact categories**, see Figure 76. This impact difference has a large influence on the overall LCA results for the whole façade with the traditional and industrialized scenarios.

It is important to note that **the comparison in this section does not provide a comprehensive understanding of advantages and disadvantages of industrialized renovation in comparison to traditional approaches**. For this purpose, **it is recommended referring to LCA at the whole building level where different kits are integrated** rather than to the analysis of 1 m² of façade.

Figure 76: Comparison of LCA results of EPS (8 kg/m²) vs stone wool (12.6 kg/m²)

2.4.1.1.5 Conclusions and recommendations

Based on the LCA study, it is possible to identify the top contributors to the whole life cycle and life cycle stage impacts. For specific hotspots identified only in some impact categories, please refer to the complete discussion of results in chapter 2.4.1.1.3.

- Top **contributors to life cycle impacts:**

- Production
- Transport (minor driver)
- End of life (minor driver)

- Top contributors to **production impacts:**

1. Cladding (HPL panels)
2. Stone wool insulation
3. MDF (DHF) and OSB panels

If **wood cladding** is considered instead of HPL panels, replacement and/or painting of wood are important drivers to maintenance impacts.

Based on these considerations, the following recommendations apply:

1. Investigate the possibility to **replace stone wool for the compensation layer with an alternative material.**
2. Test **alternative cladding materials**, such as bio-based panels.
3. Explore whether there are alternatives to polyester for the **waterproof membrane** which highly affects ozone depletion impacts.
4. Test **alternatives to MDF and OSB panels**, such as gypsum fiberboards.

5. **Include design for disassembly principles**, which are expected to reduce end of life impacts and increase recyclability and reusability of materials.

All the recommended actions above should be evaluated considering the **fulfillment of technical requirements**, such as fire resistance. This implies that when alternative materials are explored, it should be investigated whether they require additional layer or paints or other materials to fulfill the same performance as the default Typical passive façade.

2.4.1.1.5.1 Alternative materials for compensation layer

Environmental impacts of the timber façade in INFINITE can be investigated if the compensation layer is changed from stone wool to alternative materials. Specifically, **glass mineral wool with plant-based and conventional binders and wood fibre with and without PMDI** (Polymeric 4,4'-diphenylmethane diisocyanate) and **formaldehyde** are evaluated as alternatives. The density and thickness of the alternative materials are selected based on discussion with EURAC. Currently, no production waste and the same fixing systems as for stone wool are assumed for glass wool and wood fiber insulations.

The following datasets are selected in ecoinvent for the different materials:

- Stone wool: stone wool production, packed | stone wool, packed | Cutoff, U - RoW
- Glass wool with plant-based binder: glass wool mat production, with plant-based binder, uncoated, Saint-Gobain ISOVER SA | glass wool mat, uncoated, Saint-Gobain ISOVER SA | Cutoff, U - CH
- Glass wool with conventional phenolic binder: glass wool mat production, with phenolic binder, uncoated, Saint-Gobain ISOVER SA | glass wool mat, uncoated, Saint-Gobain ISOVER SA | Cutoff, U - CH
- Wood fiber with PMDI and formaldehyde: fibreboard production, soft, from wet & dry processes | fibreboard, soft | Cutoff, U - Europe without Switzerland
- Wood fiber without PMDI and formaldehyde: fibreboard production, soft, from wet processes | fibreboard, soft | Cutoff, U - CH

If life cycle impacts of 15 m² of timber façade with different compensation layers are compared, **glass wool and wood fiber insulations perform environmentally better than stone wool insulation** in most of the impact categories, see Figure 77. However, **it is crucial to choose wood fiber that does not use PMDI and formaldehyde as binders**, which especially affect eutrophication, human toxicity (non-cancer) and particulate matter. On the other hand, there is no significant difference between impacts of glass wool with phenolic and plant-based binder. **Glass wool shows a good performance if a light material (low density) is chosen**. In this case, glass wool can perform better than wood fiber. Please consider that, in the current model, glass wool is partly recycled (40%) at the end of life, while wood fiber is assumed to be incinerated.

As expected, the production stage is affected the most by the change of insulation, followed by the end of life. The production location of the insulation and the energy mix can affect some impact categories, e.g. ionizing radiation.

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Figure 77: LCA results for the timber-based facade in INFINITE with different compensation layer materials

The Life Cycle Cost analysis on the INFINITE Kits has been carried out starting from the so called “kit 0”, that is the timber-based envelope without multifunctionalities, and then add the activities, materials and expenses to transform it into the other Kits (kit 4.1-4.2-4.4 and 4.5). The “smart window kit” (kit 4.3) has been evaluated separately focusing on the windows level evaluating just the few interactions with the overall façade element. The data collection has been done thanks to a series of one-to-one meeting with the technology providers and via data costs file exchange (primary data collection). In addition to that, internal evaluation and costs data from previous projects, interview-quotation from external companies and public list of costs for tenders, has been collected to have a fair comparison and a good level of reliability (secondary data collection). The costs collected should take as a first costs based on mock-up realization and without high industrialization processes and optimization. The expectation is to reduce, depending of the technologies and complexity, from 10% (RHB façade) to 50% (BIST). In this report all the specific costs will be reported in percentage or in a range value due to confidentiality and sensitivity of the data managed.

2.4.2 LCC of KIT 0 Timber-based envelope

Main kit characteristics:

- Timber-based prefab modules – overall thickness 4+1,5+16+1,5+6+1,5 -> around 30cm **including the passive cladding**
- Ventilated façade with 6cm of ventilation gap
- Thermal properties: 4+16cm Rockwool insulation (60 kg/m³)
- Possibility to integrate different cladding components and technologies

Boundary conditions, constraints and assumptions:

The costs of the base Rubner module are not comprehensive of VAT, general expenses, and profit. For confidentiality reasons, this report does not include absolute costs.

Cost analysis results:

Kit 0 main costs breakdown -> looking at the main elements of the prefab module, we can see that 78% of the total cost is related to the components purchasing, 17% for the manufacturing and assembling phases, 3% for the packaging and only 2% for the lanyard activities. Regarding the roof element has been evaluated in the first instance the same costs as for the façade since the variability for the external finishing could be very different (from tiles to metallic cladding, etc.) and the thickness for the insulation layer and the main structure can vary much more than a façade element (from 12 to 30cm). These variations are affecting a lot the costs impact, so in general the cost of a traditional roof (16-20cm of insulation) for sqm can be evaluated as for the façade reported here.

Figure 78 -Kit 0 macro percentage cost breakdown

Looking in depth to the costs categories, the two most impacting ones have been reported in the following figures. In the first graph, the materials and products purchasing costs breakdown is reported. In this graph we can see that almost half of the cost is for the external cladding while only 10% is related with the cost for the insulation layer.

Figure 79 – kit 0 Main components costs breakdown

The second graphs show the assembly costs category where the main effort is for the assembling of the cladding.

Figure 80-Kit 0 assembly process cost breakdown

Pro and cons including general **co-benefits**:

Guaranteed - Co-Benefits	Pros and Cons vs Traditional
Wood-based envelope modules deigned to be ventilated and completely assembled off-site	Due to the ventilated technology, the insulation layer is well protected à guaranteeing an extended life to the product in comparison with a traditional ETICS
Manufacturing in protected environment - > less defects risks on the modules	The on-site works are heavily reduced in comparison to the installation of a traditional ETICS
High insulation and air tightness are guaranteed	Higher precision in the finished product is guaranteed thanks to the off-site assembling process, all the steps occur in a closed and controlled environment as Rubner factory (highly automated robotic process)

The prefabrication of the façade lowers the installation time allow the inhabitants to stay in the house

System that can reach an important weight (kg), that might not be sustained by the existing building structure

Results, feedbacks, and next steps:

The costs breakdown underlines that the costs of the prefabricated façade without cladding are not so high. The main impacts in term of costs are the purchasing and the installation process for the external cladding. Working on different external cladding options could reduce the overall costs of the kit. Looking at the prefabricated modules without cladding, it has been highlighted, together with the manufacturer, that there is a good level of improvement on primary wood structure dimensioning and materials costs. This analysis has been carried out in task 4.7.

2.4.3 LCC of KIT 1 eco-compatible green envelope kit

Within INFINITE project, the Green kit has been developed and defined without a specific technology providers as for the other kits. This choice was made due the fact that for these types of “cladding – roof” the possibilities could be very different and the idea was to evaluate the most promising technologies on the market. The results of the analysis carried out in the task 4.1 was a set of possible solutions based on the constrains-limits for the building renovations. In the following the system chosen for the INFINITE green kit mock-up has been analyzed from the costing point of view. The green roof solutions have been selected for the “catalogue” but not included in the mock-up realization and demonstrator implementation and either for the LCC analysis (lack of information from companies).

Main kit characteristics:

- Timber-based prefab modules – Overall thickness of the envelope Kit: about 32-35 cm (hp: 16 cm of the insulating layer) **including the green cladding**
- Overall weight of the envelope Kit: < 90 kg/m²
- Ventilated façade behind the green kit with 4-5cm of ventilation gap
- Thermal properties: 4+16cm Rockwool insulation (60 kg/m³)
- Possibility to prefabricate different greening systems (*from climbing plants to living walls*)
- Rainwater irrigation system to be integrated in a technical room (D:1x1x1m)

Boundary conditions, constraints and assumptions:

The costs of the base Rubner module are not comprehensive of VAT, general expenses, and profit. The costs of the green system have been defined thanks to the close cooperation with the manufacturing company. All the costs related to the green system should be considered as final cost for the kit integrator without the only profit for the installer. The cost analysis model has been built on a calculation unit of 15sqm of façade and them parametrized to a single sqm.

Cost analysis results:

Green kit (Kit 1) main costs breakdown -> looking at the general overall cost distribution of the kit, we can see that almost 87% of the total cost is related to the green envelope purchasing and installation, and only 13% for the manufacturing and assembling of the prefabricated wooden based panel. This big differences can be referred to (i) evaluation of prices instead costs for the green part (expected a reduction of 25% at least), (ii) these kinds of green application on façade are expensive in general because of the market dimension, (iii) the costs of the components for the irrigation have been included for a small portion of façade, bigger dimensions will decrease these costs per sqm, (iv) the installation of the green elements has been evaluated as it is in business as usual (the installation on the factory is expected to reduce these costs of at least 10%), (v) the installation includes also the first year of maintenance and all the equipment.

Figure 81-Kit 1 macro percentage cost breakdown

Focusing the attention on the green system, the costs share for the Manufacturing and Assembling (M&A) and the installation differ of about 10%, the first is 37% and the second 49%.

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Figure 82– GREEN Envelope à M&A vs installation

Deepening the analysis to the two main costs categories (M&A and Installation on site), the following two graphs show the costs sharing.

Figure 83 - On-Site installation costs breakdown (materials + labor)

Figure 84- Green M&A costs breakdown

Pro and cons including general **co-benefits**:

Guaranteed - Co-Benefits	Pros and Cons vs Traditional
Plants transpiration cools down the surrounding environment and prevents internal overheating in summer	With Kit 4.1 technology, only the water connection and plants plantation must be done on site, while traditional all other activities must be done on site baskets, work at height, etc. (several problems)
Combining the PV modules with a green roof can increase the output of the modules avoiding over heating	The Green substructure can be installed in the factory (off-site) and only the plants are installed on site
A green envelope can provide a home for wild bees, birds, and other animals to increase biodiversity	
This Kit allows the additional installation of grey water / rainwater treatment system reduces the need for potable water for irrigation.	

Results, feedbacks, and next steps:

The costs breakdown underlines the high-cost impact of the green solution that is mostly related to the installation and first maintenance phases. These modular green solutions are quite complex and need several components to work properly (pumps, filters, fertilization, pipes, etc.). This preliminary analysis should be carefully deepened to (i) compare costs with costs, (ii) define possible costs reduction % for the off-site manufacturing, (iii) define the minimum surface dimension to amortize the water components costs, (iv) separate the operational costs from the investment costs.

2.4.4 LCC of KIT 2: Energy and fresh air distribution envelope kit

Main kit characteristics:

- Timber-based prefab modules – Overall thickness of the envelope Kit: about 30-33 cm (**hp: 20 cm of the insulating layer for the passage of ventilation ducts**) including the passive cladding
- Overall weight of the envelope Kit: ab. 60-65 kg/m² (Ventilation unit is concentrated on a single point and its weight is ab. 25 kg)
- Ventilated façade as external cladding with 5-6 cm of ventilation gap
- Thermal properties: 4+20cm Rockwool insulation (60 kg/m³)
- Possibility to integrate the Ventilation unit under the window or on the prefab balconies. The air ducts are running into the façade (insulation layer).
- Innovative machine: fresh air & heating & cooling supply. Ventilation unit dimensions ab. 1.3x1x0.25m to be connected with an Heat Pump via hydraulic connections

Boundary conditions, constraints and assumptions:

The costs of the Rubner module modified for ducts and machine integration and the Ventilation unit with all components from Vortice are both not comprehensive of VAT, general expenses, and profit. The costs of the Ventilation unit and all the connection elements like ducts, plenum, inlets and outlets elements, etc. have been defined thanks to the close cooperation with Vortice. The cost analysis model has been built using the Italian demo façade dimensions as calculation unit and then parametrized to a single sqm.

The on-site installation costs consider the ventilation machine integration under the window and not the case where the machines are installed in the prefabricated balconies. The on-site operations need to be better defined to have reliable costs.

Cost analysis results:

The E&FA kit has been carefully evaluated due the activities and interactions with the Rubner based façade that is much more invasive than the other kits. The overall kit costs share shows almost a balance (53-47%) between: the cost of Rubner based façade with all the modification to allow the

ducts routing, the Ventilation machine and the inlet-outlet elements integration; and the Ventilation unit production, assembling and installation into the façade.

Figure 85– Energy and Fresh Air kit costs share with the façade

The cost impact of the Rubner façade modified for hosting all the Vortice components, compared to the passive façade (kit 0) with the same external cladding is about +10-15%.

Looking at the Energy and Fresh Air elements, as shown in the following graph, the main costs share is the Manufacturing and Assembling (M&A) that is about 65% (30% of total) while the installation 25% (11% of the total) and timing to install the ducts, machine and other components off-site (in Rubner factory) is around 12 % (5,6% of the total)

Figure 86– Energy and Fresh Air components costs breakdown

Looking in details to the two main cost impact “slices” reported in the following two graphs, we can see:

- a) the on-site activities costs are distributed quite homogeneously with the biggest share for the “preparation activities”. These activities are foreseen to be done on the existing building before installing the kit. The most impacting ones, both in terms of costs and impact in general, are (i) the Intake/Discharge holes (to be made in the existing walls to connect and position the inlet-outlet elements) with about 30% (7% of the total) and (ii) existing wall cutting below the windows with about 25% (6% of the total).

Figure 87– Energy and Fresh Air kit - on-site costs breakdown

b) the Manufacturing and Assembling (M&A) cost breakdown with the largest “slice” of costs on the Ventilation Machine Unit that is the core of the system and takes almost 75% of the overall M&A cost (45% of the total), the rest is shared between the components for the distribution system (plenum, air ducts, fixing system, etc.) with a 12% of the total and the costs for the inlets terminal (connection elements with the internal part of the flat) with a 7% of the total.

Figure 88– Energy and Fresh Air kit – Manufacturing and Assembling costs breakdown

Pro and cons including general **co-benefits**:

Guaranteed - Co-Benefits	Pros and Cons vs Traditional
This Kit guarantees an increased comfort of the occupants and optimization of the energy consumption.	Less invasive solution that traditional HVAC deep renovation system
This system allows to provide HVAC services to all internal spaces without intrusive interventions and in a cost-effective way	Two machines for each apartment needs to be maintain (change filters, general maintenance, etc.)
Compared to bulky fully centralised solutions, this kit is more suitable to buildings with small indoor spaces	Flexibility on the MVU installation, both under the windows, in terraces, balconies, parapets.
	User acceptance barrier due to the change of the Heating and Cooling emission, from radiators to air

Results, feedbacks, and next steps:

The analysis shows that adding the energy system to the prefabricated façade double the cost per sqm. At a first glance, this seems to be a high impact but if compared with a traditional deep renovation, the results are quite comparable and cost-effective (see kit comparison chapter). Moreover, the analysis shows that the main cost impact is coming from the Ventilation Unit, so a further optimization of it will impact positively on the overall kit costs. Regarding the prefabricated façade, an optimization could still be evaluated looking at the façade with few ducts lowering the overall façade thickness from 25cm to 20cm with a cost impact that could be important.

2.4.5 LCC of KIT 3: Integrated smart window kit

The integrated smart window kit developed within INFINITE project is focalized on sun shading via the glazing part of the window. In fact, all the development analysis and costs analysis are referred to the entire window with a specific focus on the glazing part. “Smart Glazing kit” will be more appropriate as name of this kit.

Main kit characteristics:

The smart “glazing” kit is composed mainly by two parts:

- Smart measure and control system:
 - SENSE bar from PHYSEE (multi sensor bar to be included in the IGU)
 - Remote server for real-time optimisation (control hub)
- Sun shading techs:
 - Traditional curtains (internal or external), lamellas (like Pellini) + SENSE bar (SW1)

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- Commercial **electrochromic** glazing (SW2)
- **Plasmochromic** glazing (SW3)

Boundary conditions, constraints and assumptions:

The costs reported are comprehensive of the window frame and the IGU integration in the window frame based on estimation from a window manufacturer. All the costs are not comprehensive of VAT, general expenses, and profit. The costs of the Plasmochromic glass are an estimation from the tech provider at this level of development (still not on the market and high level of optimization). The cabling and the internal works costs to connect the control hub in the flat are not included. The cost analysis model has been built on a calculation unit of 1sqm of window.

Cost analysis results:

The costs analysis has been carried out on a complete window ready to be installed in the prefabricated façade. The costs of glass integration, window frame and window installation has been defined thanks to the window manufacturer that produce the mock-up and to a further quotation based on demo buildings. Looking at the results, the glazing part is the most expensive part on the total of the window, the Pellini solution is around 50%, the electrochromic glass 60% and finally the plasmochromic 75%. The second bigger voice is the window frame and the rest is limited to a few percentage points.

Figure 89– Smart Window kit – Window costs breakdown

Pro and cons including general **co-benefits**:

Guaranteed - Co-Benefits	Pros and Cons vs Traditional
This system allows to set the amount of heat entering the building according to the external weather conditions, reducing the energy request of the building	Differently from classic shutters, the shading systems are integrated in the glass à Larger windowed area
Smart windows (SW) are fully automated, but it is possible for users to control them manually at any time.	With this curtain integrated in the window the user might have a perception of lesser safety
The prefabrication of the window into the wooden façade reduces the risks of errors during the installation phase on site.	Kit 4.3 smart windows present higher costs than traditional. On the other hand, with Kit 4.3 you have much less on-site activities therefore reduced on-site work operations

Results, feedbacks, and next steps:

Looking at the results, it is clear that the electrochromic and plasmochromic are solutions much more expensive than a traditional shading system (see comparison chapter). The high cost for sqm is also linked to the fact that these technologies are on a different market share (commercial and tertiary building) where the glazing dimensions and the components are optimized in numbers (bigger façade, only one sensor every large module, etc..). The application in the residential sector is a challenge in term of investment costs compared to traditional shading system.

2.4.6 LCC of KIT 4 Energy generation BIPV kit

Main kit characteristics:

- Timber-based prefab modules – Overall thickness of the envelope Kit: about 28-32 cm (hp: 16 cm of the insulating layer) **including the BIPV cladding**
- Overall weight of the envelope Kit: ab 75 kg/m² (BIPV cladding corresponds to 15-20 kg/m²)
- Ventilated façade behind the BIPV kit with 6cm of ventilation gap
- Thermal properties: 4+16cm Rockwool insulation (60 kg/m³)
- Coloured glass-glass PV modules (with dynamic colour selection tool)
- Possibility of different glass finishing (Satin, 3d-shaped, smooth, texture)
- Optimised module sizes (standard modules) and Tailor-made (custom if needed)

- Glued or Hybrid or Mechanical anchoring system

Boundary conditions, constraints and assumptions:

The costs of the base Rubner module like the BIPV panel from SUNAGE are not comprehensive of VAT, general expenses, and profit. The costs of the BIPV panels have been defined thanks to the close cooperation with the manufacturing company. The costs of the BIPV panels are referred to the normal satin glass finishing and with the hybrid connection system. The Electric system and components (on-site installation costs) still to be defined for each demo site à impossible to define correct costs now. Source: “*National Survey Report of PV Power Applications in Italy*” (2019). The On-site operation costs comprehend inverters, cabling, connection to the grid, etc. à these costs will have to be adjourned (2023). The cost analysis model has been built based on quantities of Italian Demo building, both façade and roof, and them parametrized to a single sqm.

Cost analysis results:

The cost breakdown has been evaluated both for the roof and façade elements in details. The results of these two solutions are similar (almost the same structure and finishing has been evaluated) and for this reason only the façade kit is presented in detail. The cost range includes the PV panels, the insulated prefab façade and all the elements needed for the installation (inverter, cabling, optimizers, installation).

The BIPV kit is mainly composed by the base prefab wooden-based façade plus a metallic substructure and the PV colored glass-glass panels. In this analysis also all the equipment needed to be connected to the grid (inverters, optimizers, cabling) and installed properly has been included.

In the following graph, it is clear that the biggest part of the costs is referred to the BIPV elements (87%). To this big part, around 80% (69% of the total) is referred to the PV colored glass-glass panel (glass, glue, cells, brackets, manufacturing, etc..) including also the Junction box on the back. The second biggest part is the on-site installation that takes around 20% (16% of the total). In the on-site costs are included all the electronics (inverters, optimizers and cablings) and the effort to install and connect the panels once the base structure is mounted on the building. The last cost share is referred to the activities needed to allow the installation of the PV module on the Rubner façade (horizontal mullion added to the based structure).

Figure 90– BIPV kit – Façade module costs breakdown

The Manufacturing and Assembling of the PV colored glass-glass panels are not deepening from the cost point of view due to the confidentiality since these are sensible data. Looking instead in depth to the on-site installation phase shown in the graph below, we can see that:

- Most of the costs are referred to the optimizers (6%) and inverter (6%) that both cover around 70% of the installation costs
- Permits and commissioning (2%), cablings (3%) and the transportation (0,5%) covers around 25% of the installation costs
- Only 1,3% of the total costs (5% of the installation costs) are referred to the installation phase (fix the panels on the prefab façade) due to its fast and easy-to-install technologies (like a ventilated façade).

Figure 91– BIPV kit – on-site installation costs breakdown

Pro and cons including general **co-benefits**:

Guaranteed - Co-Benefits	Pros and Cons vs Traditional
Architects no longer need to choose between sustainability and aesthetic appearance. INFINITE BIPV modules look exactly like other standard cladding materials	BIPV modules present a very high aesthetic value
The installed power (kW) can be increased, by exploiting the possibility to install BIPV modules also on the building façades	The Kit 4.4 allows integration into (almost) any façade compared to the traditional PV modules which are difficult to integrate
The system it's easy to install. The PV supporting structure is already integrated in the wooden frame.	The BIPV modules present a half efficiency compared to a traditional (not integrated/building applied) PV system
nZEB standards can be achieved easier	Advantage for Kit 4.4: replaces the passive cladding of an opaque façade with an active façade

Results, feedbacks, and next steps:

The BIPV kit presents an important overall cost that if analyzed in depth could be evaluated not so high looking at the advantages such as: (i) energy production on the façade, (ii) avoid the cost of passive cladding, (iii) good aesthetical aspect, (iv) ventilated façade with improved thermo-hygrometric performances, etc... Nowadays, the integration of the BIPV colored glass-glass panels is increasing the market share year by year and this will allow the manufacturer to decrease costs (an optimization around 20% is foreseen in the next years).

2.4.7 LCC of KIT 5 Energy generation BIST (Building Integrated Solar Thermal) kit

Boundary conditions, constraints and assumptions:

The costs of the base Rubner module and the BIST panels produced by SERNEO are not comprehensive of VAT, general expenses, and profit. The costs of the BIST cladding have been defined thanks to the close cooperation with the manufacturing company. The hydraulic connection develop by NBK are not included in the cost analysis due to missing data. The cost analysis model has been built thanks to the quotation done on the Italian Demo (ab. 60 sqm of façade) and then parametrized to a single sqm.

Cost analysis results:

The costs of the BIST solution include all the activities and processes done by SERNEO to produce the BIST panels and its components. In this “prototyping” phase some activities and processes are made from other companies and paid by Serneo (gluing of insulation layer and second panels on the back of the modules).

As for the other Kits, the BIST “cladding” is the post impacting voice in the overall cost of façade module with around 88% of the total.

Looking at the second highest cost, the on-site activities took just around 5% of the total cost due to the prefabrication on the factory and the limited activities done on site (just the Plug and Play connections between panels). In general, the activities to carried out in the factories and in the demonstration cases have been monitored. In the graph below the costs from the Serneo ONLY support is reported

Pro and cons including general **co-benefits**:

Guaranteed - Co-Benefits	Pros and Cons vs Traditional
As for Kit 4.4, with BIST the designers can achieve the desired effect by choosing among all types of metallic finishing (cladding, cassette, etc.), shapes and sizes.	BIST modules present a very high aesthetic value

The system can be easily coupled to the building's main energy system to reduce the overall building's energy consumption	Kit 4.5 can replace passive cladding with solar thermal which would otherwise never be integrated into the facade
Dedicated control algorithms to BIST system ensure a high level of energy efficiency	BIST disadvantage for BIST panels: Low efficiency and above all at present still R&D (unglazed)

Results, feedbacks, and next steps:

As for the BIPV kit, this kit has a high cost in term of €/sqm at first. Further analysis comparing the benefits of this active technologies should be investigated.

2.5 Kit costs comparisons

To have a better understanding of the overall costs of the industrialized kit solutions compared to the traditional ones, a set of different preliminary comparisons has been set. Even if some data should be updated (wood and electronics increased a lot in the last year) and verified with the technology providers, the comparisons show the magnitude of differences between kits and the costs share.

In the following the main comparisons are reported with a short comment. In the next months, deepening the comparisons is one of the main activities planned due to the high interest shown by the kits providers and to have a “fair” comparison with the “business as usual” deep retrofit solutions.

Task 4.1 Green kit comparison:

Here the industrialized kit has been compared with the same technology (Terapia Urbana panels) fixed on-site on a traditional ETICS adding some technology implementation activities (substructure installation, etc.). The improvement of the industrialized kit could be more effective due to the pre-installation of the substructure off-site and mover other activities off-site (not evaluated in details so far).

Figure 92–Kit 4.1 costs comparison with traditional solution

Kit 4.2 E&FA kit comparison:

This kit is one of the most complicated one from a technological point of view. The comparison of the kit has been done evaluating all the traditional activities needed to have the same results (ducts on façade, ETICS, inlets, counter ceiling, etc..). The results show that the difference between the two approaches is around only 5%.

Figure 93–Kit 4.2 costs comparison with traditional solution

Kit 4.3 Smart Window kit comparison:

The Smart window kit solutions has been compared with a window with a traditional shading (roller shutter). Since the high level of technologies used for the SW solutions, the comparisons show high differences. These differences are related to the new technologies, low level of industrialization and cost scale-up, high quality integration, etc...

Figure 94–Kit 4.3 costs comparison with traditional solution

Kit 4.4 BIPV kit comparison:

The BIPV kit has been compared in a simple way with a traditional ETICS plus the installation of traditional PV panel on it (Building Applied PV instead of Building Integrated PV. Of course, this first comparison is not so “fair” and conceptually correct because normally the traditional PV panels are not accepted to be installed as it is on a façade (aesthetically not accepted). So, a further investigation on a “fair” comparison will be done in the following months.

Figure 95–Kit 4.4 costs comparison with “traditional” solution

Kit 4.5 BIST kit comparison:

Since the BIST solution is an innovation with not so high potential replication and high market share like for the BIPV, as a first comparison a traditional thermal panel has been “installed” vertically on a façade. This is a “strong” assumption due the fact that these kinds of Solar thermal panels are not normally used vertically on façade for aesthetical reasons. Moreover, the efficiency and the cost benefits will show a huge difference (a traditional Thermal panel produce 10 time more that the integrated BIST). In the next months, a more realistic comparison will be set up together with NBK. These results show that the traditional solution has a higher cost mainly because of the presence of a cladding behind the ST traditional panels.

Figure 96–Kit 4.5 costs comparison with “traditional” solution

2.6 LCC/LCA Conclusions and next steps

The following conclusions were drawn from the LCA:

- Kit 0, RHB façade: based on preliminary analysis with EPDs for the production phase of a standard Rubner façade, materials that emerged as environmental hotspots include **insulation (stone wool), cladding (high-pressure laminates), outer planking (moisture resistant wood-fiber board)**.
- Kit 1, green envelope: **metal profiles** to fix the greening systems and **maintenance** needs are the two aspects that contribute the most to environmental impacts, based on literature review.
- Kit 2, energy and fresh air distribution: based on a screening with generic data, **centralized** systems appear to perform environmentally better than decentralized ventilation units; further, steel ducts cause higher impacts than **polyethylene pipes**.
- Kit 3, smart window: environmental impacts of PLSMC modules are mainly due to **electricity** needed during module manufacturing (glass lamination and thermal treatment) **and transport by plane** from Asia **of ITO glass** for ink deposition. From an economic point of view, production and transport of ITO glass and **inks** are the main hotspots. As for **the end of life**, recycling and reuse possibilities of IGUs and PHYSEE's smart window power bars are crucial aspects to be investigated and supported with DfA/D.
- Kit 4, BIPV: environmental and economic hotspots are related to **photovoltaic cells and solar glass**; in addition, **aluminium brackets and back rails** also show a contribution to environmental impacts overall.
- Kit 5, BIST: based on the LCA study of Batisol performed by NBK, **manufacturing and installation of the panel** is the most contributing life cycle stage to impacts, due to raw material production; specifically, **aluminium** layers are the most contributing materials to Climate Change impacts in the manufacturing stage.

Regarding the LCC analysis:

The preliminary Cost analysis of the INFINITE Kits shows a general high cost of the solutions due to the new technologies and the poor optimization processes on the technology development (see for instance BIST and BIPV panels) and in the installation phases (see green kit as example). The first round of data gathering help us to identify the main costs share and to set-up the costs analysis methodology. The data gathering took more than one year starting from beginning of 2021 and since that several unforeseen events (Ukraine war and material scarcity) affect the costs with a unstable market. Some of the costs reporters should be updated accordingly to the new prices on the market and these will affect the overall cost analysis with a probable increase of wood, electronics and manufacturing costs.

3. Design for Disassembly and Assembly

3.1 Literature review

3.1.1 What is DfD/A?

Design for *disassembling and for assembling* (DfD and DfA, named *DfD/A* in the report) could be defined as “a systematic method for separating a product into its constituent parts, components and subassemblies” (Gungor and Gupta, 1999 quoted by Kara, Pornprasitpol and Kaebernick). In some cases, actors also talk about *Reversibility* and *Design for Reversibility (DfR)*.

In other words, it is the design effort to enable a product, a system and a building (or part of it) to be easily assembled and disassembled.

The objectives of DfD/A are multiple, mainly: to reduce Construction and Demolition Wastes, to facilitate maintenance, reuse and recycling, to reduce costs and environmental impacts during the life cycle.

3.1.2 Methodologies of DfD/A

Disassembly or Reversibility support methods and tools have already been developed, either for mechanical systems in general or buildings specifically.

First, some methods exist to qualitatively assess systems or buildings on component composition, connections, functionalities, etc., using diagrams. The aim is to **analyse systems/buildings to support the DfD/A and introduce DfD/A principles/concepts**.

For buildings, the functional layers theory (Brand, 1995) is a key principle of an evolutive, dismantlable building. Later, DfD/A principles and qualitative assessment methods were globally made explicit with the research conducted at TUDelft (Durmisevic, 2006). They are still relevant and were used as basis on many recent guidelines, for example in the French guideline for Design for Disassembly (Fondation Bâtiment Energie, 2020)).

In the mechanical engineering sector, Kara, Pornprasitpol and Kaebernick developed in *A selective disassembly methodology for end-of-life products* (Kara, Pornprasitpol, & Kaebernick, 2005) a method to find the best sequence of assembling for the disassembling.

In the following section, those two methods, on which the DfD/A support process in INFINITE is based, are presented. The support is focalized on design for disassembly. The design for “Assembly” is considered as a positive consequence of DfD (not in the absolute).

Second, some methods and tools are more recent or still under development and allow to **rate quantitatively the disassembly/reversibility performance of component**, system, buildings. These methods and tools are mainly developed and communicated by Dutch actors like TUDelft (Heesbeen,

Zabek, & Hildebrand, 2021), GTBLab, Dutch building Council, Alba concepts (Alba Concepts, 2021) and we can mention for example the DRIVE 0 project (Zuyd University of Applied Sciences, SURD research team. Dario Cottafava, Michiel Ritzen, John van Oorscho, 2020).

3.1.2.1 A method to analyse the design for disassembling

The first document analysed is a document from Elma Durmisevic called *Transformable building structures - Design for disassembly as a way to introduce sustainable engineering to building design & construction* (Durmisevic, 2006). The fifth chapter is the most interesting one for our study and is about the *Design aspect of transformation*. The author defines two major criteria for the transformation: independence and exchangeability. These two criteria are defined with a lot of disassembly concepts such as systematisation, life cycle coordination, type of connection and the assembly sequences. Independence affects the functional breakdown (which is relative to the materials) and the technical breakdown (which is relative to the hierarchy between components). The exchangeability affects the technical breakdown too, and the physical breakdown (which is relative to the interfaces).

To explain the method, Elma Durmisevic draws many diagrams that help to understand how the systems works. The first aspect to analyse is the functional independence between components. Three levels of functional separation are described: the integration, the incorporation and the separation. They indicate if a function is linked to one or more components. The aim is to achieve the simplicity of one function assigned to one component.

If the analysis is done at a building scale, the main functions are: supporting, enclosing, servicing and partitioning. In the INFINITE project, the DfD/A approach is applied on envelop kits. We can define subfunctions such as water carry, data transmission, ventilation or energy capture. The functional independence indicates the spatial zoning of the functions, from a total integration to a total separation. When there are many components, clustering the components allows analysis at different levels of detail. A cluster is a set of materials or components with the least connections on site.

Figure 98: The four levels of functional incorporation which define the level of functional autonomy, according to Elma Durmisevic

The technical breakdown consists in the design of a relational model with base elements and hierarchical position. For example, in a relational diagram all the links between components are drawn. The aim is to have the fewest components with the fewest links to reduce the number of relations. The position of the relation may impact the facility of dismounting. In the nomenclature

below, a vertical link is within a functional group and a horizontal one is between functional groups. Having less column is better for the maintenance and the change of a component. Each cluster (aka functional group) should define its base element, the element to connect to the entire product. Sometimes, an element is added just for the connection. This intermediary makes the disassembly easier.

Figure 99: The types of relational pattern, according to Elma Durmisevic

The last breakdown is the physical one. The geometry of product defines the facility of disassembling. The design of the boundaries and the connection types enable the non-interpenetration of the components. If there is interpenetration, disassembling generally requires demolition, thus it should be avoided.

In the figure below, there are the six geometry levels. The assembly sequences must minimize the destruction. If the disassembly is designed at the same time as the assembly, the components can be easily dismantled. However, the disassembling is never the reverse of the assembling because of links which are not removable. The connections are defined relatively to the degree of freedom: integral (overlapped and interlocked), indirect (with additional accessories) or filled (chemical material or welded). In the INFINITE project, there are other specific connections between components such as contact and electrical connection.

Figure 100: The geometry of product edges, according to Elma Durmisevic

In a first approach of this method, we tried to adapt the diagrams to the kits of INFINITE project. However, these diagrams are often too complex in comparison with the information available at that time for each kit. This method is probably better for the evaluation of products which are already designed. However, the schematic representation developed in this document helped us in the definition of our nomenclature and type of representation. We tried to do a clustering of the kits' components too.

3.1.2.2 A method to choose the best steps sequences of disassembling

The second document we studied is a method to choose the **best sequence of assembling for the disassembling**. Kara, Pornprasitpol and Kaebernick developed this method in *A selective disassembly methodology for end-of-life products* (Kara, Pornprasitpol, & Kaebernick, 2005).

The aim of this document is to help finding an optimum disassembly process. With the number of liaisons and their complexity, we can have many possibilities of disassembly. However not all of these sequences are efficient. The authors highlight that the disassembly is not the reverse of the assembly because of the different operations (difficult, unprofitable, destructive), targets (maximize the profit and minimize environmental damages) and product conditions (damaged, corroded, ...).

The method consists in identifying each component with a code in a directory with the material type and the end use. Next, a diagram with liaisons is created. Each liaison is identified with a code number too. Accessibility, requirement of a prerequisite action and step for disassembly are indicated with a code. For example, if we must dismount L1 and L2 to dismount L3: {L1, L2 → L3}. With additional information, it is possible to generate a sequences diagram which consider all the possibilities. It is the base diagram and the next steps will simplify this first diagram. To do so, we must consider the selected components, disassembly constraints, disassembly states, transitions, and quantitative data. With all these considerations only a couple of diagrams are relevant and it is easier to choose the best sequence.

In the diagram below, we can see the steps to disassembly a product. After the third level, there are two alternatives. The white cases are relative to the code number of the component which is dismantled at each level. Beside are indications of the time required and the tools needed for the disassembling.

Figure 101: Time mapping of two sequences for the same product, from Kara, Pornprasitpol and Kaeberrick

3.1.3 Benchmark of reuse and recycling practices for each kit typology

3.1.3.1 Green roof and green facade

Green roof and green facade projects may have different purposes and different life expectancies (Greenscreen, 2013). Some projects will be legacy projects beneficial for decades: for those, facilitating the maintenance and improving durability is expected. Other projects may be in place for a shorter period to keep in line with current design trends. If a project is expected to be replaced or renovated within a shorter time frame, designing them conducive to DfD/A principles is even more important and the end-of-life valorisation should be considered.

3.1.3.1.1 Reuse

The winning team of the Solar Decathlon 2018 designed a green roof which was installed on the temporary installation in Denver. Due to the short lifespan of the installation, the green roof had not reached its end of life. A new place was found to extend the use of the green roof. The green roof was disassembled and transported with a crane to another building (Tolderlund). This green roof is made of modular boxes that were just put on the roof. This feedback is the only one found for reuse of a green roof that actually took place.

Figure 102: Disassembling operation at Solar Decathlon with crane (image credit Leila Tolderlund)

Another easy disassembling-ready green roof was designed for a building in Hong Kong with a limited life cycle of three or four years. The designed adopted is a modular system. The transport to another location is possible without too much trouble (Hui, 2006).

3.1.3.1.2 Recycling

The recycling of parts of a green roof or green facade is also possible, but with difficulties. All the components are not recyclable, for instance plants are usually composted. Earth substrate is difficult to recycle too. Recyclable components like metallic cables or grids must be separated from plant waste for valorisation. No recycling chain seems to be available currently for green facades and roofs.

3.1.3.2 Air distribution

3.1.3.2.1 Reuse

Ducts are variable in size and geometry because of the specificity of each building. They are assembled, cut and shape to measure: the possibility of reuse is reduced, despite the standardization of the initial material. As the pipes have standard fittings, it is easier to disconnect and reconnect, but waste often is created. Moreover, the disassembling could cause damages on the components (Steps to maximise value at deconstruction, 2021).

Concerning equipment, when removed, some equipment may be in a good enough shape to be reused or reconditioned. However, as the performance and/or communication standards may have evolved in the meantime, old equipment is often obsolete, despite being functional.

3.1.3.2.2 Recycling

HVAC equipment are complex to recycle due to the variety of materials and components. Fittings are chosen for their ease and speed of making and installing. The ability to remove is not the main parameter. If smaller items can be easily removed, it is not the same for the larger ones, usually built up in situ. If there is a lot of various polymers, the effective recycling of each type is reduced (Steps to maximise value at deconstruction, 2021).

3.1.3.3 Windows

3.1.3.3.1 Reuse

The recycling of windows is not usual due to the specific geometry of the products. Windows are often custom-made and it is more difficult to adapt the windows to another building. Moreover, the performances of old windows are too low, and this is usually one of the main reasons for their removal. That is why there are so few examples of windows being reused nowadays for the same function (building thermal envelope).

However, there are some artistic projects that reuse windows or windows frame. For instance, the facade of the European Union Council is made of windows frame from all over Europe. Often, the whole window is not reused but only some parts of it.

Figure 103: European Union Council Headquarters, Philippe Samynn & Associés

3.1.3.3.2 Recycling

Windows, and smart windows too, are made of a lot of different materials. The recycling depends on the frame material. In general, sorting centres separate the different parts and materials. PVC frames are crushed and made into flakes. These flakes then are de-polluted and used by the industry. Wooden frames are not recycled, but some methods exist to sort the elements to recover energy from the wood. They also could enter the wood agglomerates production, although no example has been found. The aluminium frames are recovered and integrated into the classic aluminium recycling chain. Steel frames are also recycled but are not used to make new windows. Flat glass is complex to recycle and the layers, such as sound insulation, complexify the process. Electrochemical layers would certainly be even more difficult to separate (Le recyclage des fenêtres : un enjeu environnemental, s.d.).

A patent application publication from a US manufacturer describes an innovative process for recycling smart windows. The method for recycling glass is as follows: break into coarse elements, heat at low temperature until before the transition temperature of the glass (between 250 and 500°C) to incinerate the organic elements (if the electrochromic layer is made of organic material). If the layers are made of metallic material, they are treated in an acidic solution to dissolve lithium, rhodium, silver, tungsten, tin, ... (Agrawal, 2020).

3.1.3.4 Photovoltaic Panels

3.1.3.4.1 Reuse

Photovoltaic panels are not very repairable and re-usable. According to PV Cycle, replacing a part seems to reduce performance and reuse presents warranty issues: *"Replacing parts of or repairing PV modules might result in a performance shortage. In fact, as PV modules are nearly to 100% installed in (several) dozens, it may become difficult to track PV modules that were treated for reuse, resulting in a guarantee/warranty issue. Furthermore, panels need to be safe for use and go through a strong lamination process to be able to stand extreme weather conditions"* (PV Cycle, s.d.).

Therefore, it seems complicated to reuse photovoltaic panels, considering moreover the speed of new technologies that allow to obtain better performances. Today, dismantled panels have an average efficiency of 80-90% and can be reused if higher performances are not desired. Individual components (junction box, frame) are not necessarily compatible between panels. The reuse of silicon plates, if recovered in their integrity, has been studied by the company SolarWorld. The silicon cells could be reused up to four times.

3.1.3.4.2 Recycling

Different recycling processes exist depending on the panel composition. Most components are recyclable. More than 94% of a panel can be recycled and the material can be used to make new panels. The separation process is described below:

- Manual dismantling of the aluminium frame, cables, and junction boxes.
- Cutting the module into strips and crushing it
- Separation of some components (about 7 different ones)

The separated components are glass of various granularities, ferrous and non-ferrous metals, polymers (10%). The aluminium and copper from the cables are integrated into industrial processes. Polymers are transformed into solid fuels for energy recovery. Silicon is melted into bars and sold to industry (NégaWatt, 2021).

3.1.3.5 Solar thermal panels

3.1.3.6 Conventional solar thermal panels - Reuse and recycling

The components of a conventional solar thermal panel are glass, steel, insulation, and copper. If the panel is dismantled, the reuse of parts of the panels seems possible based on the components and materials. However, no feedback or dismantling methods are available.

3.1.3.7 Cladding panels - Reuse and Recycling

The BIST proposed in INFINITE is different in its conception from conventional solar thermal panels, as it is based on a standard cladding panel and glue. For cladding panels, reuse is difficult as the panels must be in good shape (no bump or scratches), and the products are very customized. However, some initiatives try to develop the reuse of metallic building components, like the platform MétalRéemploi (Centre Technique Industriel de la Construction Métallique (CTICM)) in France. For recycling, cladding panels usually enter existing recycling chains for metal.

3.2 DfD/A support approach and working principles

3.2.1 Objectives

DfD/A facilitates assembling and disassembling processes, allowing direct reduction of wastes (during fabrication, maintenance, and end of life), facilitating maintenance, permitting conditions for recycling and reuse of kits or components. Considering these aspects, DfA/D reduces life cycle costs and life cycle environmental impacts.

The goal of the DfD/A approach in this project is to introduce assembling and disassembling principles in the design of technical solutions and kits (disassembling of kits themselves but also disassembling of kits that are interconnected) developed in INFINITE.

3.2.2 Scope

DfA/D approach possibly concerns all kits in development and kits grouped in global solutions. DfD/A can concern A/D of components of the kits, connections of the kits with their build environment (with support and with other connected kits). Possibilities of support are different for each kit, depending on maturity of the design, the typology of the product, relevance of DfD/A.

Despite its advantages for the final solutions, disassembling performance was not compulsorily for the kits in this project, as it can compete with other essential performances (economic or technical for instance). Preliminary works were done with kit developers to evaluate interest and possibilities.

Global guidelines were communicated to developers to improve the DfD/A of their respective solutions.

3.2.3 Approach for DfD/A

The approach carried out to support the kit developers in the implementation of DfD/A principles was based on successive stages that are described hereafter:

The first stage was **to communicate global objectives** of the INFINITE project and expectation related with DfD/A. This work was carried out through on-line bilateral meetings with the kit developers.

The second stage was to **gather detailed technical documentation** on the kits and their components. All data-gathering methods and documents were defined and shared (see section 2.3.1). Most of the information was collected from the kit developers.

The third stage was to **represent the kits into technical diagrams** to target kits functions and components where DfA/D is relevant and is of interest. This stage is based on engineering methods for DfD/A allowing the evaluation of the kits.

The fourth stage was to **iterate questions and answers on the design of the kits** using previous analysis, so that they improve their kit design for more DfD/A. Kit developers oversee the design and its improvement. NBK is challenging them, targeting design issues, and occasionally bringing design support (solutions).

The fifth stage was the **evaluation of the kits** and the improvements proposed, using DfD/A related evaluation criteria.

Figure 104: General process for DfD/A approach

Whereas in this project, the DfD/A assessment has concluded the work focused on DfD/A aspects, the three last steps can be seen as an iterative method of improvement that could be implemented until achievement of a satisfactory DfD/A score.

3.2.3.1 Collecting information

The methodology for supporting disassembly requires a large amount of information before being implemented. Indeed, the recommended solutions should be adapted to the initial system. The specifications of the solution should be respected and the economic and technical stakes included. First, it is necessary to collect as much information as possible, then the system can be described precisely. Most of the information was available online and provided by the partners. To summarize this dispersed information, information sheets by kit were produced, with all the data and illustrative graphics. The information, provided by the technology providers, included in the information sheet are:

- Contact information of the technology provider,
- General information and description of the functional system,
- A first list of components,
- A potential description of the anchoring,
- Suggestion for the maintenance,
- Ideas of disassembling if applicable.

Information from a kit has been made available from several stakeholders: the kit developers (sometimes composed of several companies) and task supports. The information is dispersed and must be first collected and then aggregated. When prefabricated elements are used, the data can be even more complicated to find.

Intervening on disassembling during the design is an opportunity to modify components and improve systems. In INFINITE project, some kits were designed and developed and some others were adaptations from an existing product. If the design process is at a very early stage, it is also difficult to obtain information. For instance, the Smart Window from LEITAT and PHYSEE was complex to study because all the information needed cannot be provided.

Several documents to be completed have been sent to technology providers to collect data. In INFINITE project, as all the partners were not trained in the challenges of disassembling, it was also relevant to offer interactive tools. Two documents were proposed to the kit developers:

- A database to list the components and their characteristics,

- An on-line questionnaire on the current state of development of each kit on DfD/A, market needs & opportunities for DfD/A.

The second document aggregated more information from partners. Even if the documents were pre-filled, it was sometimes difficult to have access to all the information because of the current development of the products. However, the questions allowed the partners to begin a more in-depth reflection on the dismantling of their products.

All the information was shared online with the kit developers. This allowed everyone to change the data as the design progressed. To track the progress and modification of the documents and data from the technology providers, we set up a Trackbook online.

3.2.3.2 Terminology

First, we tried to develop an adapted terminology, applicable to each kit. This terminology was inspired by the literature review. To prioritize the constituent elements and to establish a specific methodology to various scale, a precise terminology was required. We then broke down the elements into different levels:

- **Material (M)** is a shapeless raw material.
- **Subcomponent (S)** is a simple piece made of a single shaped material.
- **Component (C)** is a more complex item than the subcomponent and it can be composed of several materials shaped to meet a specific sub-function. For example, a cable is composed of a metal conductive material and a plastic insulating envelope and responds to a data transfer sub-function.

During manufacturing and assembly, material transformation processes happen, so that no raw material is usually found during the use phase (with rare exceptions, such as water):

Figure 105: Material, Sub-component, component schematic definitions

- **The family of components (F)** refers to the group of components that together form a technical whole. For example, the "Frame components" is a family of components of different types and functions, which together form a technical whole.

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- **The kit (K)** refers to the set of component families that are assembled to fulfil a function. Each kit was given a number and was developed by a group of companies. A kit usually consists of one functional solution, but may combine several ones. For example, the R2.4 kit meets both a need for aesthetic facade cladding and power generation. The Rubner facade is a specific kit – called Kit 0 – and its code is KB, for Kit Basis.
- **The group of kits (G)** is the set of kits put together in the same wall. At least one group of kits is composed of the structural timber frame solution. To this solution, other kits can be assembled depending on the requirements of the building at a specific position (e.g. a need of ventilation) and the location in relation to the environment (e.g. the possibility to produce energy on a southern facade).
- **The existing facade (E)** is the wall to which the group of kits is fixed.
- **The new facade (N)** is composed of the two walls (the added one and the existing one).

This breakdown can be summarised schematically as follows:

Figure 106: Schematic representation of a new facade with the Rubner timber base and the kits 1, 2 and 3

3.2.3.3 Technical description of components

The technical description of each kit was carried out in close collaboration with the technology providers. Indeed, it is crucial to have a good knowledge of the functions associated with each component and the specificities required to avoid inconsistent solutions.

The technology provider has a global knowledge of the technical functions to be fulfilled and seeks to supply components that meet the technical requirements as closely as possible. The complexity of the selection criteria does not always take into consideration the energy required to manufacture the pieces, the maintenance needs, the ease of disassembly and the end of life. A more detailed study of each component is therefore necessary to manage material resources as far as possible and to encourage reuse. The way the components are assembled is studied in a second phase and influences the potential for reuse according to several parameters.

The first stage in identifying the components was to list them. The easiest way to do this was to find a list of all the components provided by the technology provider. Partners had not always this list available, mainly because they were in a development process that entailed to choose/develop components, make changes in function of tests. At this stage, the main components could be determined from the graphical elements. This list has then been checked and completed by the technology provider.

A database was created for each kit. This document must be exhaustive to maximise the information available on the components and to establish the most relevant assembly/disassembly procedure in view of the components, their specific properties, and the assemblies to be implemented. These are working databases that were continually updated, therefore not all the information is fully completed.

Each component was described with as much information as possible. The components were classified into component families according to their function. Each component were given an identifier, preceded by the associated component family.

Figure 107: Family components and components per kit

For example, in kit 3, components such as "Smart window assembly", "Frame" and "Sensor module" were grouped in the "Frame components" family and cannot be separated.

The components may have changed during the project, some solutions were not yet definitive and variants may have been possible. Final choice of a variant may have been made rather late in the

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project and the study must have therefore covered all the variants. In addition, the results of the disassembling study could be used to select a variant. Each component was then annotated in relation to its status of use in the project.

Below is the legend of a part of the list of components:

- **Definitively chosen:** the component is essential and will be included in the kit;
- **Chosen potentially:** the component is likely to be chosen, however parameters remain to be determined, like geometry, connections, or technical specifications;
- **Not selected:** choice to be made between several variants;
- **Non-existent/indefinite:** component to be found to meet a function of the kit.

The more orange-red a component is, the more possible and simpler the modifications are to implement. If a component is permanently selected, only modifications to the assembly are possible, which reduces the possibilities of end-of-life optimisation for reuse and recyclability.

Five main steps required information for each component. The implementation and dismantling steps indicated the necessary steps, the ease of assembly and the information given by the manufacturer in the product manual. Before assembly, data on the manufacture and type of the component were listed:

- **The type of product:** prefabricated, partially prefabricated, adjustable product, manufactured by the tech provider from raw materials;
- **The materials of the component:** plastic (HDPE, PP, ...), metal, wood, small electronic elements, etc;
- **The technical properties associated with the material:** antistatic, antibacterial, ... and the additives and treatment agents.

The use stage of the component forms the major part of its life. This is when the part will potentially degrade, which can impact on its life and end-of-life management. During this phase, information was gathered on:

- **The associated function:** this enables an estimate of the potential damage that the component may suffer;
- **The life cycle:** evaluation of the number of years of operation;
- **Maintenance requirements:** complexity of maintenance, necessary checks, regularity of maintenance, change of parts, etc.

All components, sub-components and materials have been hierarchically structured as follows according to their assigned function:

Figure 108: Functional breakdown of a kit

This method of structuring information makes it possible to consider each element in relation to its function. The links between elements do not represent a physical link but a functional one. A function-subfunction relationship is created between the elements.

Once all the components have been described in detail, it has been possible to create links between them in a schematic way and to model the assemblies according to technical and functional criteria.

3.2.3.4 Technical description of connection

Assembly provides a connection between several elements, for technical reasons (fixing to a wall) or functional reasons (continuity in the flow of a substance). Assembly can be carried out at several levels:

- Between sub-components;
- Between components;
- Between families of components;
- Between kits;
- Between the grouping of kits and the existing facade.

In each case, assemblies can be made at several points, with different materials and types of assembly. The assembly elements are to be distinguished from the components. In general, they only serve to connect two components, but they can also have other secondary functions, such as providing a seal between two components. Wherever possible, the assemblies should be uniform, thus reducing the number of tools and skills required.

For technical reasons, a distinction was made between assemblies between elements recommended by a technology provider and those involving several partners.

The assembly within a kit was designed by a partner according to the required technical and physical specificities. An assembly is defined by its geometry and its type. The geometry of the components indicates the degree of closure of the assembly. An open-linear geometry between two components refers to elements that can be separated by bilateral linear movement. On the contrary, a closed-integral on two sides geometry is characteristic of a component inserted in two others. No movement is possible, it is then necessary to dismantle each of the side components to access the main component. Disassembly is therefore constrained. The table below shows four main types of assembly geometry, with an associated type of schematic:

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- **Open:** consists of a juxtaposition of components, allows bilateral movement;
- **Covered** (on one or two sides by the central component): allows unilateral movement;
- **Overlapped** (on two sides, one of which by the central component): no movement possible;
- **Closed** (on one or two sides with embedding): no movement possible.

Interface geometry	Engineering drawing	Level of fitting - number of interfaces	Symetry
open - linear geometry		1	o
symetric overlapping		2	o
overlapping on one side		2	x
unsymmetric overlapping		2	o
closed - integral on one side		3	x
closed - integral on two side		3	o

Figure 109: Interface geometry of components. Source: Transformable building structures. Elma Durmisevic

The nature of the connection is related to the energy or material input that modifies the integrity of the interface. Four main types of connection were defined at the interface between components, each of which has a type of schematic associated with it:

- **Integrated or embedded:** assembly without the use of another element but may require a modification of the initial interface (drilling, boring, ...);
- **Mechanical:** a force connection, a system or element is added (riveting, screwing, nailing, ...) and the interface can be modified;
- **Material (chemical or welded):** with the use of an adhesive (adhesion), or welded with or without the addition of material.

Table 23: Schema of types of connections (legend created for the DfD support approach in INFINITE)

Family of connection	Type of connection	Schematisation
Integrated	Integrated interlock	
	Integrated screw	
	Integrated interlock + screw	

Mechanical	Screws + bolts / stud	
	Nail	
	Magnetic	
	Other	
Material	Chemical	
	Welded	
Electrical	Electric	
Other	Contact	

The assembly between kits and between the group of kits and the existing facade was designed by several partners. This added complexity to the analysis. The connection to the environment can be established in several ways:

- By adding assembly elements;
- By modifying the components of the kit grouping;
- By a modification of the assembly elements between kits (shared assembly).

The same interface assembly features as above can be used. However, the assembly must be facilitated and carried out in a minimum of points for greater efficiency. In addition, a kit or group of kits must be able to be dismantled without altering the wall.

3.2.3.5 Implementation description

Some manufacturers provided assembly instructions with their products, and less frequently disassembly instructions. Depending on the assembly method, disassembly can be carried out by reversing the assembly process. Mechanical assemblies and embedded assemblies are more easily dismantled in this way. Glued joints are more difficult to dismantle, and a different method must be used than in assembly.

The implementation steps were sometimes well described with explanatory diagrams. To design the disassembling of a system, these diagrams were very useful since they allow to understand the type of links between the elements and to estimate the possibility of disassembling.

3.2.4 Schematic design per kit

The schematic design is an interesting tool at many levels. It can be used to have a simplified representation of the links between components or to describe a process, for instance the steps of the disassembling and of the assembling.

3.2.4.1 First diagramming method

In the section relative to the literature review of this deliverable, the attempt to adapt the schematic diagrams from Elma Durmisevic to represent the kits of INFINITE project is explained. The method is exhaustive but complex for a first study of the functioning and the components of the kits. Here are some initial diagrams of the kit 1 inspired by this method. First, a code was assigned to each element in relation to its function kit in the system. This allowed an initial clustering by family of component.

Figure 110: Legend of the components, kit 1 Green roof modular plastic

This legend was produced at the same time as the functional diagram for the specification of sub-assemblies. Clustering by function made it possible to quickly understand the purpose of a component. This diagram does not show physical links between components but only functional links.

Working diagrams with all the component names can be dense and not very readable. Components are reminded through the numbers presented for example in the previous legend.

Figure 111: Clustering at the system level, kit 1 Green roof modular plastic. Extract of the working document as illustration

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After this first analysis of the system, it was possible to draw up a technical breakdown with a relational diagram. Each component is physically connected to at least one other component. The aim was to simplify the system and to ensure that a component is only linked to one other component. Depending on the number of links, it can be determined if the assembly is open or closed. This has an impact on the complexity of disassembly. The type of link is not explicit, but this type of diagram makes it possible to create the link with the next step: the physical breakdown of the system.

Figure 112: Relational pattern, kit 1 Green roof modular plastic. Extract of the working document as illustration

Once the links between components were known, it was possible to qualify them. For this purpose, the connection types were briefly described (by connection family) and the geometry of the edges of the components was indicated. The geometry of the parts indeed influence the assembly and disassembly.

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Figure 113: Connections between elements, kit 1 Green roof modular plastic. Extract of the working document as illustration

Finally, the last relevant diagram to produce was the assembly diagram. The sequence in which the components are assembled can give an indication of the order in which the components are disassembled, although not the reverse. The colours in this diagram depend on the assembly type: parallel, sequential, interlock, closed circle or gravity. The aim is a parallel or gravity type of assembly to facilitate disassembly.

Figure 114: Assembly direction, kit 1 Green roof modular plastic. Extract of the working document as illustration

This method was useful because it allowed to go into detail for the analysis of each system. However, it was rather laborious to apply because of the many steps required. In the following paragraph, are selected two schemes that were particularly relevant from the disassembly point of view:

- Connections between elements,
- Assembly direction.

3.2.4.2 Detailed diagramming method

Based on all the technical and market information gathered on the kits and their components, a schematic representation of each kit was drawn, representing typologies of components, materials and possible end of life, group of components, connections between components and/or group of components, energy/water/air flows.

The diagrams allowed to have a simple and complete view of the kits, helping identifying opportunities for DfD/A principles and interdependencies between (group of) components. First

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versions of diagrams were shared with the respective Kit developers to collect feedback, leading to a second diagram corrected of errors and complemented with the design advancement.

The figure below gives the legend of the diagrams showing all the types of information possibly available.

Figure 115 : Kit diagrams Legend

The figure below presents the diagram of the Kit 4 BIPV (Sunage).

Figure 116 : Diagram of the Kit 4 BIPV

3.2.5 Assessment of DfD/A implementation on kits

To conclude the work on DfD/A, a complementary quantitative assessment method was developed to be applied on INFINITE kits.

The objective was to evaluate quantitatively and yet simply the integration of the DfD/A principles in the design of the kits, and identify the strong or weak points of kits on the DfD/A aspect.

Previous works on DfD/A assessment methods for constructions developed:

- Connection type and accessibility type assessments (Alba Concepts, 2021), (Durmisevic, 2006) ;
- DfD/A assessment tool Drive 0 (ISSO, 2022) with 2 disassembly scenarios: maintenance and end-of-life.

These methods determine a score for the disassembly of constructions by giving the same weight to all connections.

The method proposed in the INFINITE project was inspired by those previous works and **enriched the approach** by considering two new parameters:

- The **mass** of the elements, in order to promote the reduction of non-reusable waste at the end of life of the kits;
- The **expected lifespan** of the kits as a whole and their components, in relation to the easiness of their maintenance interventions.

The evaluation method was based on 3 complementary criteria:

1. **Maintenance score:** DfD/A on use - Disassembly for maintenance
2. **Reconditioning score:** DfD/A end-of-life - Disassembly for reconditioning (reusing the parts)
3. **Recycling score:** DfD/A end of life - Disassembly for recycling.

An Excel tool implementing this method was created and presented to the kit developers (tool shown in Figure 117, Figure 118, and Figure 119).

3.2.5.1 DfD/A on use: Disassembly for maintenance

The first criterion focuses on the maintenance operations in use. This criterion leads to either choosing longer lifespan parts or improving the detachability and accessibility of wear parts.

The first step is to identify « wear parts » of the kits:

- Parts that need maintenance;
- Critical parts that are susceptible to fail or break.

The second step is to detail, for each wear part, the type of the hardest connection (if detachment needed at all) as well as the accessibility of the part / the connection during maintenance on site.

The more the connection is accessible or detachable, the easier the maintenance will be: thus, the kit will attain the expected lifespan. Conversely, if maintenance operations are made difficult, they may not be performed in the long term, which will affect the life of the kit.

The maintenance score therefore considers a fictive " lifespan " of the system which increases with the easiness of maintenance of the system. The criterion is expressed in years and as % of the

3.2.5.3 DfD/A end of life: Disassembly for recycling

This criterion focuses on end-of-life: the kit is entirely detached from the facade, and disassembled in factory and/or on deconstruction site.

The purpose is to recycle the materials.

The approach is to dismantle step by step the kits, until remain only:

- (d) Unitary recyclable components
- (e) Assemblies of components of the same recyclable material
- (f) Assemblies of or unitary components that are not recyclable

The criterion is expressed as % of mass of (a + b) on the total mass of the kit, the objective is to maximize it.

This criterion leads to choosing recyclable materials and allowing separability by material type.

Damaging the parts during disassembly is allowed if it is possible to separate materials.

END-OF-LIFE SCENARIO : Disassembly for recycling					
Total mass of the system (kg) :					
Product, element or assembly of elements	Mass (kg)	Type of connection of the element	Is the material recyclable ?	Connection score	END-OF-LIFE : Recyclable mass
Element 1		Choose type of connection	Choose yes or no	0	
Element 2		Choose type of connection	Choose yes or no	0	
				Recycling score	0%

Figure 119: Recycling score evaluation sheet (Table created for the DfD support approach in INFINITE)

3.3 Recommendations for kit developers

3.3.1 Determination of high value elements

The identification of high-value elements can give an economic purpose to the DfD/A approach, in addition to an environmental benefit to improve circular economy.

High value elements can:

- be made of precious and easily recovered materials, such as metals: they will be reused or recycled;
- represent a high added value by their technicality, for example electronic cards: increasing their durability, or even their reuse, can be an improvement opportunity.

3.3.2 Design with standardisation

Standard elements should be used when feasible. They have benefits at the end of life and during maintenance operations. Indeed, standard components have the advantage of being more easily replaceable in the case of an incident during the use phase. Technicians can procure components locally, which reduces maintenance time and costs. Components are more easily replaced, extending the lifespan of the whole kit and delaying the final dismantling stage.

Standard components are also easier to reuse because they are already well-known by the companies that handle them and because they will find a new use more easily due to their large-scale use. Not all components can be reused, but the issues concerning standard components are more widespread and recycling channels may already exist.

3.3.3 Design for best durability

Choosing best durability components allows to extend the lifespan of the kit as well as open end-of-life valorisation ways in reconditioning and reuse. The constraints upon each component must be carefully identified in order to choose the appropriate materials, thicknesses, and overall properties of the components.

3.3.4 Design of connection

The nature of the assembly is not directly related to disassembly. For example, a soldered joint is easy to do but not to dismount, and a chemical assembly can be easily disassembled in the case of wax that melts in the presence of heat. On the contrary, an embedding may be more difficult to dismantle. Sometimes, several assemblies are combined on the same interface for safety or specific needs (sealing).

It is necessary to avoid binding the components by hidden links, which are difficult to disassemble. In parallel to the project, NBK drafted a national guide on DfD, including principles and concepts regarding connections. They were used to assess the kits and support kit developers.

The analyse of the kits showed that not all their constitutive components were connected using easy dismountable connections. The connections that could be discussed and improved for more DfD/A were targeted.

In relation with the Rubner wood facade, there are several types of timber connections. The timber frame has a structural function and support assemblies are used for some kits. Wooden elements, to be dismountable, can be fixed:

- by interlocking,
- by metal elements/plates/bolts/screws/nails,
- by reversible electro-magnet.

Main part of the DfD/A is related to connections between components and/or group of components. Depending on the actual state of the kits, the interest of reusing/recycling the different components of the kits, connections can be targeted and proposed to be improved in terms of disassembly. Connections which are explicitly already ok are not targeted.

3.3.5 Maintenance

Depending on the systems in the building, maintenance is required on a regular schedule. This may be a simple check or a change of parts. During maintenance, dismantling should be minimised. Visible and accessible systems are therefore recommended.

Maintenance of facades has several advantages. It extends the lifespan of the systems and increases their performance. Simplifying the facade system by reducing the number of materials limits the number of interventions and maintenance steps. It is therefore preferable to use only one type of cladding for a building. If two claddings have the same maintenance frequency, they can be used together.

The following table shows the maintenance operations to be performed for each kit. Some maintenance operations seem to be quite similar for some kits, such as checking the hydraulic system (kit 1 and 5) or cleaning components (kit 2, 3 and 4). These operations of maintenance could be shared and done in only one operation of maintenance with the same technician, if the frequency of maintenance is the same too. The kit developers indicate that a technician with specific qualification is required. If the qualification needed is comparable, one operation of maintenance could be sufficient. This sharing of skills for several kits would have multiple advantages. On the one hand the maintenance cost is reduced. On the other hand, maintenance oversights for all components are reduced, and the life of the elements is extended, limiting disassembly operations during the use phase.

The durability of the whole facade element is determined by the condition of the timber frame. Regular checks of the framework can detect any disorders. For this purpose, the framework must be accessible. In rehabilitation, as in the case of Infinite walls, access from the inside is very complicated, if not impossible. The existing wall, usually concrete or masonry, cannot be dismantled to see the framework. The only solution in this case is to go through the outside. It is then essential to separate the load-bearing and structural elements from the enclosure. The envelope kits (Green facade, BIPV and BIST) have considered this problem with disassembly from outside. Kit 2 Air distribution and Kit 3 Smart window are the exception with access from inside, in windows frames.

3.3.6 Disassembling processes and tools

For a good tracking of the components until disassembly, it is necessary to manage the information until the end of life. Here are some recommendations for plastic parts. If they are marked, they can be identified quickly, which allows them to be sent to the appropriate recycling centre. As the service life is long, it is necessary to mark the parts by moulding or engraving. Labels and paint have a short lifespan and can contaminate the material to be recycled. Marking must be always clearly visible during the life cycle.

If a component is damaged, it must be easy to replace. This means:

- Having easily accessible fixings for the removal of the element.
- Having a replacement supply available.

The accessibility of the elements should therefore be considered in a much more extensive way than just the elements requiring maintenance. All elements must be accessible without damaging those nearby. In the case of damage (advanced and unforeseeable end of life), the dismantling of a series of components is accepted to reach the element to be changed. The provision of replacements can be facilitated by managing the products upstream. For example, for elements that are frequent or have a high probability of damage, building up a stock of products to be installed is a simple solution to put in place. This can also pose new problems of stock management (ensuring conditions of non-deterioration, involvement of the project owner, space required). The use of standard products is also a solution that allows for the rapid availability of replacement supplies.

The level of difficulty can be estimated according to the access, the visualization, and the operations to be carried out. According to these criteria, the necessary skills of the person in charge of carrying out the dismantling can also be chosen. The types of operations can be the following:

- Destruction,
- Drilling,
- Chemical removal,
- Take-off,
- Heating,
- Lubrication.

Tools for disassembly are necessary. Wherever possible, standard, and easy-to-use tools should be preferred, with the following in order:

- Hand,
- Easy tool,
- Specific tool.

After this first step, the components must be separated. To facilitate sorting, the materials should have different properties: magnetic, weight, ... Polymers of different nature should have a gap of 0.15g/cm^3 . Recycling a product is only relevant if it can be separated into a sufficiently pure material flow. Otherwise, no recovery route is possible. Some metal treatments reduce the recyclability of the product. For metal assembly parts, ferromagnetic metals should be preferred to allow magnetic sorting.

3.3.7 Valorisation sector at the end of life

After disassembly, the end-of-life stage allows the component's recovery options to be determined. Sometimes guidance is given by the manufacturer on the recyclability potential. If not, data on materials and function during use can help to determine the recycling sector. However, recycling is not carried out in the same way in all countries, and sometimes the recycling channels are missing. For recycling, it is therefore necessary to consider the location of the implementation, but also to project the recovery channel and estimate its sustainability in relation to the component's lifespan. The potential for reuse depends on two factors. On the one hand, the manufacturer can claim the component for reuse if the component's lifetime is longer than the time it is dismantled. On the other hand, a standard material can be reused and taken back by reuse platforms to be rehabilitated and then put back on the building market. In general, reuse is more relevant from an economic and environmental perspective as it does not require a major transformation of the material.

Reuse aside, the components or materials can also be remanufactured or reconditioned (that is integrated in the production process of new systems, with less manufacturing than a new material) or repurposed (that is used for an entirely different function than the initial use).

3.4 Evaluation of DfD/A implementation on kits

The DfD/A assessment method presented in section 3.2.5 was applied to the following kits: Kit 1: GREEN WALL / Climbing plants version, Kit 2: Air distribution, and Kit 5: BIST.

Those kits were chosen primarily because their designs were sufficiently advanced for a DfD/A assessment. Moreover, the differences between kits allowed to have feedback on the assessment tool itself.

Overall, the tool was deemed easy to use but somewhat little adaptable to the specificities of the kits (compostable elements, no reconditioning for electronics and equipment).

Also, core limits of the tool were identified, on which it would be beneficial to work on for improvement:

- The tool does not value the optimisation of the total mass of the kits, which should be considered to assist in the choice between two versions of the same kit.
- The tool does not discriminate between replacement and repair of components during the maintenance phase. There is no waste measurement during the lifespan of the kit. The production of waste during the exploitation phase of the kit is not penalised.
- Between recyclable materials, the tool does not discriminate on the efficiency of the recycling chains. Plastics, known to be far less recycled than metals, are being considered as recyclable material, whereas in fact, they often end up incinerated or buried.

Implementing these three remarks in a new version of the tool would be greatly beneficial to better integrate the kits' impact on material resources and waste production, both during and at the end-of-life of the kit.

3.5 DfD/A Conclusion and perspectives

Through this work, methodologies to implement Design for Disassembly/Assembly on INFINITE kits were researched and developed. The first step was to review the literature on the subject and find the methodologies appropriate for INFINITE cases.

The second step was to adapt and implement those methods to the INFINITE kits, challenging the designs and providing support to the kit developers. This work contributed to improve the kits as it allowed kit developers to focus on the connections and interfaces in a durability and scalability aspect, which is sometimes overlooked in technical design in favour of performance or cost. The benefits were multiple: optimisation of installation processes, reduction of maintenance needs, discrimination between multiple design possibilities.

The last step was to develop a DfD/A assessment tool to be used by the kit developers. The main objective behind the development of a new assessment method was to create a tool:

- simple to use,
- that highlights the connections and assembly features of the kit,
- and quantifies the implications of design choices on the reusability and recyclability of the kits through the DfD/A aspect.

The assessment tool was used on 3 of the kits, leading both to highlight the advantages and disadvantages of each kit and testing the tool itself. Axes of improvement to the tool were identified and can be addressed in a further development of the tool.

The overall iterative process proposed, consisting of analysing, assessing, and improving the kits, could be implemented in the design support services:

- In building conception, to improve scalability of buildings.
- In eco-conception of products and mechanical systems, to improve durability and circularity.

4. Overall Conclusion

Data collection, employing both primary and secondary sources, facilitated the creation of life cycle models using openLCA software. The conducted assessments offer valuable insights into the environmental and cost profiles of various kits, such as façades, roofs, energy distribution, smart windows, BIPV, and BIST. The analyses pinpoint critical areas for improvement and optimization, paving the way for enhanced sustainability and cost-effectiveness.

The environmental and economic performance of the different kits depends on various factors, such as materials, systems, and life cycle stages. For the RHB façade, the most impactful materials are insulation, cladding, and outer planking. For the green envelope, the main sources of impacts are metal profiles and maintenance needs. For the energy and fresh air distribution, centralized systems and polyethylene pipes have lower impacts than decentralized units and steel ducts. For the smart window, the main hotspots are electricity for module manufacturing and transport of ITO glass and inks, while recycling and reuse of IGUs and power bars are important for the end of life. For the BIPV, the most critical components are photovoltaic cells and solar glass, as well as aluminium brackets and back rails. For the BIST, the most contributing life cycle stages are manufacturing and installation of the panel, especially due to aluminium layers. The improvement areas which were identified by the LCAs show pathways for improvement and further product development.

Cost analyses highlight a general high cost of INFINITE kits, attributed to new technologies and suboptimal optimization processes in both development and installation phases. Data gathering efforts, initiated in early 2021, have encountered challenges due to unforeseen events such as the Ukraine war and material scarcity, leading to market instability. As a result, a review of data gathering involving technology providers is scheduled to ensure accuracy and relevance, particularly considering fluctuating market conditions affecting wood, electronics, and manufacturing costs.

In Section 3, methodologies for implementing DfD/A principles into INFINITE kits are explored. A systematic literature review identifies suitable methodologies tailored to the unique requirements of INFINITE cases. The adaptation and implementation of these methods to the kits involve challenging existing designs to prioritize durability, scalability, and recyclability. This iterative process not only enhances the functionality and eco-friendliness of the kits but also fosters optimization in installation processes and maintenance needs. Furthermore, the development of a DfD/A assessment tool provides kit developers with a user-friendly tool to evaluate design choices' implications on reusability and recyclability. The tool's application on select kits underscores its effectiveness while also identifying areas for further enhancement.

The integrated approach adopted in INFINITE, encompassing LCA/LCC and DfD/A methodologies, holds promise beyond the project scope. Insights gleaned from this endeavour can potentially inform building conception processes, driving scalability and eco-friendliness. Furthermore, the application of DfD/A principles can transcend INFINITE kits, influencing product eco-design across various industries to foster sustainability, durability, and circularity.

The INFINITE project serves as a beacon of innovation in sustainable building retrofitting, leveraging advanced methodologies to address environmental challenges while promoting economic viability and design adaptability.

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6. Annexes

6.1 Annex 1: Focus on glass recycling

Although building glass can be potentially indefinitely recycled, it seems that the building industry is still struggling with designing the end of life of glass in buildings, such as for Insulated Glazing Units. Especially, most of this glass is landfilled or downcycled as road aggregates and glass wool [20].

Two broad studies by ARUP [21] and Deloitte Sustainability [22] can be considered as the main references in the industry to get insights on the current trends and possibilities for glass EoL.

Small amount of glass waste is generated during production. Most of glass waste is produced during replacement and demolition [22]. Nowadays, different **recycling options** of glass cullet can be identified [22]:

- Glass wool industry (where treated glass content reaches up to 80%);
- Packaging industry (recycled glass content near 90%);
- Flat glass (recycled content around 25-50% due to high quality requirement);
- Aggregates for roads where quality is not important;
- Road paints.

Recycled glass and cullet can replace flat virgin glass up to 50% without affecting glass quality and manufacturing process [21]. Saint-Gobain, one of the leading companies in the sector, produces glass with up to 30% recycled cullets [23].

The main barrier to glass recycling is contamination of glass with other materials (such as ceramic, frames, bricks...) that could make separation very difficult or impossible. Building glass is often crushed with other materials at the EoL. Contaminated glass cannot be remelted and is instead used for road paint and aggregate production or just sent to landfill. This is why **disassembling is a crucial step in the EoL stage** and could be preferably done in a factory environment rather than at the building site [21]. Furthermore, **selective demolition, correct collection and sorting are important for glass recycling feasibility**.

Contaminated glass is classified to cullet with the lowest quality (**Class C**), such as in the case of **glass with spacer bars, printed and ceramic fritted glass** [21]. Specifically, edge seal of IGU should not be covered with ceramic frit because fritted glass cannot be recycled; printed glass shows a lower melting temperature than clear glass, thus preventing recycling [21].

Class B cullet includes **partly contaminated glass** (for instance laminated glass where interlayer materials are difficult to separate) [21]; this is usually recycled as insulation (glass wool) or container glass. In the event of **laminated glass**, it needs to be delaminated and the cullet obtained is too small for recycling in the float line, but still suitable for container glass [20].

Grade A cullet would be the best option as it can be remelted and reintroduced in the float line [21].

Typically, components of hermetically sealed IGUs are not easy to disassemble and recycle. **A major issue of IGUs is that their service life is 25 years, while individual panes have longer (even indefinite) life span** [21]. 60 years or longer is assumed for service life of frames [21]. The problem with the deterioration of IGU is associated with the **moisture** through the edge seals that compromises the

unit and shortens the service life. One option would be to use desiccant systems [20] within IGUs and to design windows for in-situ refurbishment. However, ARUP pointed out that the industry would not be able to move away from using sealed cavities for double and triple pane glass units in the near future [21].

Potentially, **IGUs are recyclable to float lines if removal of spacer bars and edge seals is possible and correctly done not to contaminate the glass panes**. The latter are subject to recycling limitations **depending on previous glass treatment** (e.g. lamination, ceramic fritting). See **Error! Reference source not found**. compiled by ARUP on recyclability of different glass processes [21].

Glass process	Recyclable to float line?	Notes
Annealed glass	Yes	Readily recyclable
Cutting and edge processing	Yes	No effect on recyclability
Laminating	Limited	Current methodology for delaminating reduces quality. Requires improved delamination processes to ensure stays in closed cycle level. Current methodology means laminated glass goes to container glass or mineral wool.
Heat strengthen	Yes	No effect on recyclability
Toughened (or tempered)	Yes	No effect on recyclability
Heat soak tested	Yes	No effect on recyclability
Glass coating (hard and soft)	Yes	No effect on recyclability
Ceramic printing and fritting	No	Current methodology does not allow for recycling of ceramic printed glass
Insulated glass units	Yes	Requires removal of the spacer bars and edge seals, limitations on processing of individual panes as noted above
Low iron glass	Yes	Specifying low iron glass may require float manufacturers to reduce the recycled glass content to ensure a clear product is achieved. Further discussion with glass supplier on a project basis is required.

Figure 120: Recyclability of different glass processes [21]

Environmental and economic benefits of glass recycling

The **glass recycling process does not come without burdens**, e.g. due to primary energy use. However, **energy for recycling glass is lower than manufacturing virgin one, as the melting temperature for glass cullet is lower than for virgin glass raw materials**. This leads to 3% energy saved for every 10% glass cullet and CO₂ emission savings [22]. From a manufacturing point of view, lower melting temperature of glass cullet results in **extended furnace life and lower maintenance** rate, hence affecting also **costs**.

Deloitte [22] has demonstrated that environmental benefits can be achieved with 100% glass recycling in comparison to the Business as Usual (BAU) scenario, which foresees 40% glass recovery and 60% landfilling, see **Error! Reference source not found**. . Recycling glass to flat glass industry (Option 1) shows lower climate change impact savings than recycling to glass industry in general (Option 2). **Transport** is an important aspect for environmental impacts of treating cullet. Transport impacts for recycling (Option 1 and 2) appear to be higher than option 3 where landfill plays a major role. Furthermore, recycling to other glass industries in addition to flat glass (option 2) shows lower transport distances. In view of architectural glass life cycle, Deloitte highlights that environmental impacts of window dismantling and cullet preparation could be negligible in comparison to transport and replacement of raw materials [22].

Origin of glass waste	Balance between CO ₂ emissions and savings, depending on the recycling scenario		
	Option 1	Option 2	Option 3
Glass waste originating from light renovations of residential buildings/ houses	-255 kg CO ₂ eq /t	-269 kg CO ₂ eq /t	4 kg CO ₂ eq /t
Glass waste originating from large renovation or demolition sites	-247 kg CO ₂ eq /t	-261 kg CO ₂ eq /t	

Figure 121: Overview of CO₂ eq. emissions per recycling scenario. Option 1: 100% building glass recycled to flat glass industry; 100% building glass recycled to glass industry (including flat glass industry); option 3: business as usual, 40% recycling and 60% landfilling [22]

For each ton of cullet in glass production [22]:

- 1 ton of glass is prevented from landfilling;
- 1,200 kg of raw materials can be replaced;
- 25% of energy is saved;
- 300 kg of CO₂ emissions (direct) are avoided.

In terms of resource depletion, **silica sand used for virgin glass production is considered as a scarce raw material** in different countries, such as in the Netherlands [20]. By replacing silica sand with glass cullet, impacts deriving from mining and quarrying activities can be notably reduced.

According to British Glass [24], carbon dioxide emission savings can be achieved with different recycling options, from glass containers to glass fibre insulation, except for aggregates and glass filtration. However, it should be noted that **impurities (metal, plastics, ceramic) in glass cullet can result in harmful air emissions when melting** [22]. A research by ARUP [21] has shown that recycling glass back to float line enables approximately as many CO₂ savings as glass recycling to containers, see **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 122: CO₂ emission savings for different glass recycling options [21]

Although the cost per ton of cullet is lower than raw materials [20] and landfill taxes are avoided with recycling, **the BAU scenario (a mixed approach of landfilling and recycling) still represents the cheapest option for glass EoL**, see **Error! Reference source not found.** However, cost difference between the 3 options presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** can be reduced, if technology advancements (for instance regarding optimization of transport, glass dismantling and separation), increasing demand for cullet and higher landfill taxes can be established [22].

Figure 123: Total costs for different glass EoL scenarios. Option 1: 100% building glass recycled to flat glass industry; 100% building glass recycled to glass industry (including flat glass industry); option 3: business as usual, 40% recycling and 60% landfilling [22]

Main costs for glass recycling derive from dismantling windows and separating glass panes from frames, see **Error! Reference source not found.** [22]. In addition, cost variables include building floor, skill of workers, tools and technique, size, weight and type of window, and labour cost. According to Deloitte research [22], to dismantle windows, the cost is around 296 EUR per ton of glass; to separate glass panes from frames, the cost is 50 EUR per ton of glass. Demolition waste, including glass, for public work (e.g. road construction) has very low cost, 1-8 EUR per ton. Cost of landfilling construction demolition glass is in the range of 10-180 EUR/t.

Figure 124: Cost of glass waste from demolition site [22]

Finally, the main glass waste collection initiatives in Europe are reported hereafter:

- **France:** REVALO project; glass is either manually separated at the renovation site (high quality and recyclability guaranteed) or manually broken at treatment site (with low quality and high landfill destination).
- **Germany:** Reiling Glas Recycling & Co GmbH (leading company); out of the total glass collected, 40% is sold to flat glass industry, 40% sold to hollow glass, and 20% to glass wool. Treatment sites are located close to the 12 German float lines. Other glass collection and treating companies include Komi, Schirmbeck, and Tönsmeier.
- **Italy:** Eurovetro; low quality cullet is sold to make road aggregates, while good quality cullet is used in the hollow industry. Italy has a public database, CoReVe, to collect the name and location of glass treatment centres and manufacturers.
- **Netherlands:** Vlakglas Recycling Nederland. Recycling facilities accept float glass, laminated glass and combination glass (mix of sheet glass types). Some materials, such as ceramics, cork, plastic, heat resistant and leaded glass are not accepted. Glass is landfilled if contamination is too large. 13% of collected glass is recycled to flat glass industry, 32% to glass wool insulation, 55% to packaging industry. Furthermore, this country shows a specific way of adding windows to the building structure: frames are usually already in the structure, insulated glazing units are added afterwards. This makes disassembling much easier.

6.2 Annex 2: Schematic diagram legend

